

Ice drift station FRAM-2014/15

Weekly Reports

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Ice drift station FRAM-2014/15 summary

Why ice drift stations?

An ice drift station is a logistic alternative to:

- i) explore areas of the Arctic Ocean not accessible to icebreakers,
- ii) carry out scientific field experiments which cover the full annual cycle and requires physical presence.

FRAM-2014/15 was an ice drift station using a medium-sized hovercraft as logistic and scientific platform operated by a crew of two persons. The hovercraft was equipped as a scaled-down modern research vessel. Work space for geologic and oceanographic work was set up on the ice separately. The station was deployed on first year ice from icebreaker **Polarstern** on 30 Aug. 2014 in the Makarov Basin, upstream of the target, the Lomonosov Ridge (Fig. 1). The drift during the next 12 months covered over 1.900 km with scientific data acquisition and includes an unprecedented five complete crossings of Lomonosov Ridge. The drift during November through April were in a part of the Arctic Ocean not accessed by diesel driven icebreakers unless assisted by a nuclear icebreaking vessel. The expedition was recovered by the sealing vessel **Havsel** at 81° N on 18 Aug. 2015.

Fig. 1 The drift track of FRAM-2014/15 (red line)

Fig. 2 Summary of science programs and camp logistics during the ice drift

The main science objective of the ice drift was to obtain geologic information which relates the geologic evolution and the paleoenvironment of the the polar continental margin of Europe prior to about 56 million years ago, now represented by the Lomonosov Ridge. The primary tools were seismic reflection measurements and short sediment cores from key locations (Fig. 2). Additional programs included measurements of incoming and outgoing radiation at the ice surface (Met.no), local weather (Univ. of Bergen), transfer of heat from the water to the underside of the ice (Univ. of Bergen), measurement of deep contour following currents (Univ. of Bergen), temperature and salinity measurements (Univ. of Bergen, Univ. of Århus), short sediment cores for studies of the presence of sea ice during past warm climate periods (Nordic Centers of Excellence), and bottom camera to explore life on the sea bed.

A logistic objective was to explore the use of hovercraft as a platform for a drifting ice station where camp mobility and a lean operation are a way to reduce the impact of destructive sea ice activity.

FRAM-2014/15 ice drift:

Total duration: 353 days

Total science days: 303

Total drift: 2.200 km

Data acquisition: 1.900 km

Final budget: NOK. 5.1 million (Euro 625 k)

Fuel consumption: 15.000 liter

Responsible institution: Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Centre, Bergen, Norway

Cooperating partners: A. Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Germany (deployment)

University of Bergen, Bergen, Norway

Field support: Norwegian Air Force, 333 Squadron (two support missions)

Danish Air Force (air drop and photography)

Sponsors: Blodgett-Hall Polar Presence LLT

Lundin Norway

The first week of ice drift (30 Aug. - 7 Sept. 2014)

Ice camp deployment

At 87°20.7' N, 153°58.8' E a large floe next to a lead was spotted from the bridge of the German icebreaking research vessel "Polarstern" in the early morning of Saturday August 30th 2014. The floe was inspected and the thickness found to be about 1.1 m. The location is within the Transpolar Drift which contains only first year ice and the only thing that will happen is that the ice will get thicker during the coming winter. In terms of the ocean floor landscape, we were in the Makarov Basin at the foot of slope of the Lomonosov Ridge; water depths were about 4.000 m. The weather conditions were low clouds and poor visibility. Preparation for offloading began at 0800 hours and the hovercraft was put on the ice at 0850 hours. At 1030 hours transfer of diesel from the vessel to fuel bladders on the ice started and the helicopter began moving slings of equipment from the ship to a location on the ice floe about 200 m from the ship. The ship's officers, deck and engine crew and all 50 scientist were involved in moving a total of about 7 tons of equipment, food and 14 tons of diesel onto the ice (Fig. 1). At 1430 hours, fuel transfer was completed. At a short formal meeting in the Captain's quarters at 1530 hours, the Sabvabaa crew, Yngve Kristoffersen and Audun Tholfsen, signed a paper declaring *...they dismiss the Master and Chief Scientist of RV "Polarstern" from their responsibility for the crew and supplies of the hovercraft "Sabvabaa"...* and that *... "Polarstern" can continue her voyage.*

At 1700 hours, "Polarstern" left and FRAM-2014/15 was on (Fig. 2 and 3). The moment was so overwhelming that even after more than six years of preparation, the imminent question came to mind; Now, what do we do? Where do we start? Although the total food supply (18 months) includes plenty of other options, the event was celebrated with a Drytec meal of concentrated food where you just add hot water. A glass of white wine was included.

Fig. 1 Ice camp deployment. Fuel bladders laid out to be filled.

Fig. 2 Farewell to *Polarstern*

Fig. 3. *Polarstern* has departed and the ice drift is on. The picture shows the total amount of cargo with the fuel bladders in the background below the flag.

Ice drift

The ice drift during our first week on the ice is shown in Fig. 4

Fig. 4 Screen shot showing the drift track during the first week .

Camp life

The activity during the first week has mainly been concerned with getting the camp organized. Building of the ice/snow hangar is a relatively large undertaking which probably requires one man month of work. This has low priority right now, except for the part which houses the work area for sediment sampling. As of now, one of three walls is up for this section. The technique using a sliding form (glideforskaling) works very well. There is of the order of 10 cm of snow on the ice and we get ice from using a chain saw to cut the surface of refrozen melt ponds which already have 15 cm thick ice on them.

The daily routine involves starting the 4.5 kW generator to charge the batteries and let it run for about one hour five times a day. The hovercraft cabin maintains a comfortable temperature of +18-24° C using one of its two diesel-fired ovens. The extensive on-the-ice experience of Audun Tholfsen and his attitude towards challenges of the frozen Earth, are huge assets to the FRAM-2014/15 ice drift. We maintain a Norwegian time schedule even though we are 8 hours ahead in reality. The midnight sun is still with us.

Science

The fact that the icebreaker did not reach its primary target, the Alpha Ridge, has significant implications for FRAM-2014/15. In short; the potential for scientific return (Mesozoic sediments) may appear similar, but the time in the target area is very different. Over Alpha Ridge, there would have been on the order of six months of drift to exploit potential geological sampling locations. Now, the drift upslope of the Lomonosov Ridge may be over in one to a maximum of two months and under challenging visibility conditions. When the large submarine mountain chain is passed, we are out of our prime geological sphere of interest and the rest of the drift over the deep basin and its abyssal plain of turbidites, will be devoted to oceanography and sea ice research.

Since the drift during the first week has kept us at the foot of the slope of Lomonosov Ridge (Fig. 4), priority has been given to other commitments. These are:

- i) setting up and initializing instruments for radiation flux measurements for Met.no. (Fig.5)
- ii) setting up and initializing a weather station for Geophys. Inst., Univ. of Bergen (GFI)
- iii) deploying current meters at 2000 and 800 m depth from the ice floe for GFI (Fig. 6)
- iv) testing and deploying five autonomous echo sounder buoys for Blodgett-Hall Polar Presence and WHOI.

Other oceanographic instrumentation, which has been pre-programmed to start logging on 15 September, will be deployed next week. These include an acoustic Doppler current profiler (ADCP) to scan ocean currents down to 500 m water depth and a 300 m long thermistor string to measure microstructure in the temperature field of halocline layer for estimation of turbulent heat transfer.

Fig. 5. Audun Tholfsen initializing the data logger for incoming and outgoing radiation on behalf of the Norwegian Meteorological Institute.

Fig. 6 Deployment of one of the current meters through a rectangular hole.

Other events:

In transit to the deployment area, *Polarstern* passed via the North Pole (Fig. 8). The event was celebrated with a short stop.

Fig. 8 Screen shot of the corner of the Furuno navigation display in the hovercraft at the North Pole

Wild life

Audun sighted a seal in the lead shortly after "Polarstern" left us. This is the only sign of life so far.

All is well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 1 September:

Position: 87 24.3' N, 158 23.5' E, temperature -1° C, air pressure 1014 hPa, wind 8 knots from NNE.
White-out, but good visibility for six hours during the late evening. Worked on organizing the camp

Tuesday 2 September:

Position: 87 21.9' N, 158 12.7' E, temperature -4° C, air pressure 1019 hPa, wind 15 knots from NNW.
White-out all day. Put up work tent and made a hydro hole for work. Started testing of autonomous buoys via instructions from Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, USA (WHOI).

Wednesday 3 September:

Position: 87 20.0' N, 157 04' E, temperature -5° C, air pressure 1025 hPa, wind 10 knots from NNW.
Measured up and marked 2000 m Kevlar line and deployed a current meter (10909) suspended from the ice at 2000 m depth and another current meter

(12313) at 800 m depth on behalf of the Geophysical Institute, Univ. of Bergen.

Thursday 4 September:

Position: 87 21.7' N, 156 36' E, temperature -7° C, air pressure 1024 hPa, wind 12 knots from the East. The drift was 3.6 nautical miles towards NW during the last 24 hours. White-out all day. Deployed the weather station on behalf of Geophysical Institute, Univ. of Bergen and the instruments for incoming and outgoing radiation on behalf of Meteorological Institute. Prepared a hole in the ice for the Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP).

Friday 5 September:

Position: 87 23.9' N, 155 48.7' E, temperature - 4° C, air pressure 1019 hPa, wind 5 knots from ESE. White-out all day except for 1.5 hours of useable visibility. Discovered extensive melting under the hull of the hovercraft. Put the craft on pallets to get some distance from the ice surface. Initialized logging at the weather station and the radiation instruments at 0820 GMT. Tests of autonomous echo sounder buoys finalized.

Saturday 6 September:

Position: 87 26.6' N, 155 50' E, temperature - 7° C, air pressure 1007 hPa, wind 19 knots from NNE. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards WNW. At lunch time all of a sudden the sky cleared and we saw the mighty sun from an almost clear sky. This was time for action; all five autonomous echo sounder buoys were deployed within a 6 km radius from the camp on behalf of Blodgett-Hall Polar Presence, the owner of the hovercraft. They will ping every six hours until the end of the FRAM-2014/15 and report the received bottom echo via Iridium to WHOI.

Sunday 7 September:

Position: 87 27.7' N, 152 56.6' E, temperature - 10° C, air pressure 999 hPa, wind 15 knots from W, light snow, water depth 3.800 m. Our prospective area for geological sampling is to the north and since we are now drifting south, priority is given to work on the ice hangar, particularly the section associated with the work area for sediment coring.

The second week of ice drift (8. - 14 Sept. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice drift after *Polarstern's* departure was first a 9 nautical mile(nm) loop to the east, then a 6 nm loop to the north and by Tuesday 9 Sept. we passed the position where *Polarstern* had left us. All this motion is driven by the local wind field and in general terms opposite or perpendicular to the long term ice drift. As of Sunday evening 14 Sept., we are in the Makarov Basin about 22 nm from the foot of the slope of Lomonosov Ridge, heading north (Fig. 1). The water depth is 4.000 m.

Fig. 1. The position of the ice camp at the end of week 2.

Camp life

The time spent drifting in the Makarov Basin is actually a gift to us, because it gives us time to build a base camp with work space for the winter. The base is a 80 m² area to house the hovercraft plus two annexes each 12 m²; one for geological sampling and one for storage (Fig. 2). In addition there will be

a small generator room. The ice and snow walls are 40 cm thick and 2 m high, and the top will be covered with a tarp. The building method is shown in a short time-lapse movie attached. After 8 days of hard work, the storage room is left to do. We had clear skies today Sunday. The temperature dropped to -17°C (-26°C considering the wind chill factor), so shelter is important for the work environment. Surprisingly enough, this simple form of camp construction has, to the best of our knowledge, not been reported by expeditions on drifting sea ice.

The hovercraft is parked on 10 x 10 cm lumber on top of a pallet in the front and one in the back. Heat from the cabin part of the hull turned out to melt the ice underneath. The problem was remedied by moving the support forward and towards the rear plus allowing cold air to circulate under the craft.

Fig. 2 The basic structure of the ice hangar

Science

Today, we made a hole in the ice 15 m away from the hangar and deployed the Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler about 2 m below the underside of the ice (Fig. 3). This instrument is programmed to start operating 15 September and will send and receive acoustic pulses which give information about ocean currents from the underside of the ice down to about 500 m depth. In addition we have one current meter hanging from the ice at 800 m depth and a second one at 2.000 m depth.

A 1 m x 1 m hole is made through the ice in preparation for geological sampling. So far only the 3.5 kHz echo sounder is in continuous operation. The penetration over the abyssal plain is about 20 m. Five autonomous echo sounding buoys are in operation on our ice floe (6 km in diameter) using data transmission directly to shore via Iridium. In the vicinity of 87 18.9' N, 159 21' E, the 3.5 kHz signal weakened and "disappeared" for about 10 hours, suggesting we passed over a narrow mountain peak coming out of the flat sea floor of the abyssal plain. This feature is not on any bathymetric map.

The sensors of the weather station and the radiation flux instruments are running well, but hoar frost is being continuously deposited. We visit the sites 2-3 times a day to check and clean.

Fig. 3. Deployment of the Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler.

Wild life

No form of animal life has been observed during the week.

All is well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 8 September.

Position: 87 22.6' N, 154 43' E, temperature -8° C, air pressure 1002 hPa, wind 15 knots from W.
Winds calmed down and clear skies from noon - a beautiful day in the afternoon. Worked all day cutting ice blocks and building the forward wall next to the hydro hole. Have drifted 6 nm south during last 24 hours.

Tuesday 9 September.

Position: 87 21.1' N, 155 10' E, temperature -9° C, air pressure 1001 hPa, wind 2 knots from WSW.
Overcast and white-out. Wind increased to 15 knots during the morning with blowing snow. At midnight, we passed the position where *Polarstern* dropped us off 9 days ago. Ice walls for the geological sampling area completed. Put out extension cable to rad-flux instrument so the battery is charged every time the generator is run.

Wednesday 10 September.

Position: 87 21.3' N, 157 18' E, temperature -6° C, air pressure 1002 hPa, wind 8 knots from SE.
Drifting due west at 0.2 knots. We are 7 nm from foot of slope of Lomonosov Ridge, water depth 4000 m. The sun has been breaking through the clouds all day. Completed aft ice wall on the port side.

Thursday 11 September.

Position: 87 21.7' N, 158 11' E, temperature -4° C, air pressure 999 hPa, wind 11 knots from W.
Overcast and white-out. Cleared later in the day and temperature fell to -13° C. The hovercraft is tilting 2° forward from melting of the ice below the cabin part of the hull. Started the engine and put the craft on the columns in order to position reinforced pallets as far forward and towards the rear as possible. Started work on long ice wall on starboard side

Friday 12 September.

Position: 87 19.0' N, 159 21' E, temperature -10° C, air pressure 1007 hPa, wind 5 knots from SSW.
Completed the long ice wall and three layers on the front wall. The 3.5 kHz signal weakened and "disappeared" about midnight and came in strong about noon. We must have passed a basement peak protruding out of the Makarov abyssal plain - a feature not shown on the IBCAO map.

Saturday 13 September.

Position: 87 16.9' N, 160 13' E, temperature -6° C, air pressure 1019 hPa, wind 1 knot from SSW, fog.
Completed the front ice wall and half of the forward wall on the port side.
Visited the weather station and the rad-flux instruments twice during the day to remove hoar frost from the sensors.

Sunday 14 September.

Position: 87 19.0' N, 161 49' E, temperature -15° C, air pressure 1017 hPa, wind 5 knots from ENE.
Sunshine from a cloud-free sky in the morning. After lunch, fog and white-out. The ice drift is 0.2 knots towards NE. Completed ice wall on port side.
Started on ice walls for the storage room on starboard side. Visited the weather station and the rad-flux instruments three times during the day to remove hoar frost from the sensors. Audun turned 42 years old today. The event was celebrated with rump steak for dinner followed by apple cake and coffee/tea.

The third week of ice drift (15 - 21 Sept. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice drift during the week has been 33 nm (60 km) due east - a direction which is roughly perpendicular to the long term direction of ice drift. High winds during Thursday 18 Sept. reached 35 knots (Strong Gale, Beaufort 7) with blowing snow and the ice moved at 0.4 knots (1 km/hr). This ice motion has been driven by winds from the sector between South and West associated with a persistent high pressure area between Alaska and the North Pole. To us, this ice drift is nothing but a huge benefit so far for two reasons; 1) it gives us time to build a camp for the winter, and 2) it takes us into the deep Makarov Basin across a linear trend of buried seamounts and ridges which are considered to be a large shear zone - a key element in the formation of the oldest part of the Arctic Ocean. We could not do better even if we were in command of an icebreaker.

Fig. 1 The drift track (thin line) during the third week of ice drift. The length is about 60 km.

Camp life

Getting the ice hangar finished has been given priority and occupied us all week. By Saturday, we had completed a total length of 42 m of 2 m high and 40 cm thick walls (see picture), only the bathroom walls are still unfinished. The main hangar was covered by a tarp on Sunday and left us too tired for any report writing. By next week, the winter camp will be completely finished and more particulars will be given.

On Friday after lunch, we moved 3 tons of fuel from the depot to a new location. This was done by pumping the fuel into the long range fuel tanks of the hovercraft, taking the empty fuel bladders on deck and later pumping the fuel back into the bladder on the ice at the new location, one ton at a time.

Fig. 2 Overview of the ice hangar and adjacent rooms.

The temperatures during the week have been mostly between minus 5 and minus 8° C because we have had persistent overcast and low clouds. Once the sky clears up, as in the morning of Wednesday 17 Sept., the temperature dropped by minus 10° C within a few hours. Even if the hovercraft keels sit on pallets over 20 centimeters above the ice, the warm weather gives us problems. The heat from the hull below the cabin part of the hovercraft melts the ice below and the front sinks in. This week we had to do another build up of support and also create openings for influx and circulation of cold air below the hull.

"We are under-staffed", Audun remarked shortly after *Polarstern* had left us; "we should have been six persons". Of course he was right, but the reality is that an operation like that could never become a reality because of costs. The penalty is during the start-up phase, as it will take us more than three weeks to get the camp and working conditions in order. Once we are there, two persons are enough.

The sun went below the horizon at midnight during this week - we will have no more midnight sun. Because of the persistent low clouds, there is not much difference between the light during day and night. Under these white-out conditions, there is almost no contrast in the landscape around us. We are acutely aware of that at times, as it would be very difficult to spot a white polar bear before the animal is something like 50-100 m away.

Science

With the Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler deployed on Sunday, Sept. 14th, we are continuously scanning the depth range from surface to 500 m depth for the velocity of ocean currents. Beyond that we have a current meter hanging from the ice at 800 m depth and another one at 2000 m depth. The instruments for measuring incoming and outgoing radiation are running, but need to be inspected for removal of ice from the sensors several times a day. The 3.5 kHz echo sounder gives about 20 m of sub-bottom penetration, and five remote autonomous echo sounding buoys provide supplementary bathymetry data. With the ice hangar up, priority will be given to getting the seismic gear up and running.

We are drifting over the abyssal plain in the Makarov Basin. The dimensions and properties of abyssal plains are spectacular and manifestations of leveling physical processes in the deep sea. We have drifted over 60 km into the Makarov Basin and the water depth has increased steadily by less than 5 m. In the global ocean, this is a small abyssal plain and we are less than halfway across it. Sediments are deposited in the deep ocean at a rate of about 1 cm per thousand years in two principal ways; i) as fall-out from the biogenic production in the surface waters, or ii) brought in by sediment-laden (turbidity) currents. The biogenic sediments produce an even drape of sediments over highs and lows, while deposits by turbidity currents are gravity flows which always seek the lowest areas and create a vast plain. Turbidite deposition dominates if an abyssal plain is adjacent to sediment sources on a continental slope; in this case the continental margin of the East Siberian Sea. In this way the shape of the sea bottom of the abyssal plain will always be perpendicular to the Earth's gravitational attraction in the same way as the sea surface; they are equi-potential surfaces.

Wild life

No form of animal life has been observed during the week.

All is well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 15 September.

Position: 87 22.9' N, 161 41' E, temperature -5° C, air pressure 1014 hPa, wind 10 knots from NNE. Worked all day cutting ice blocks and building the storage room. Hovercraft skirt segments were partly frozen in and had to be freed and strapped up. Radiation instrument checked twice for icing and IR skin temperature sensor brought in for cleaning and mounted back again.

Tuesday 16 September.

Position: 87 21.1' N, 163 50' E, temperature -10° C, air pressure 1018 hPa, wind 7 knots from SW. White-out. Ice drift 0.2 knots due East. North and east wall of storage room completed.

Wednesday 17 September.

Position: 87 20' N, 164 13' E, temperature -14° C, air pressure 1020 hPa, wind 8 knots from SE. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards East. Two walls on the wash room nearly completed. Moved the generator into the new generator room. Winds increased during the evening and by 1800 hours we stopped because of blowing snow.

Thursday 18 September.

Position: 87 21' N, 168 04' E, temperature -5° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 20 knots from SSE. Ice drift 0.4 knots towards ENE. Wind increased with gusts reaching 35 knots at 1500 hours and drifting snow, but came down to 18 knots one hour later. Later wind speeds about 20 knots. Removed ice from the radiation flux instruments twice during the day. Covered the new generator room with a tarp and tore down the old small shed.

Friday 19 September.

Position: 87 23.8' N, 169 45' E, temperature -6° C, air pressure 1021 hPa, wind 10-14 knots from SE. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards ENE. Started cleaning up after the snow storm. Prepared and moved the hovercraft out of the hangar by using the winch. Pumped fuel from 3 fuel bladders into the long-range tanks of the hovercraft, put the bladder on deck and moved to the vicinity of the hangar where the fuel was pumped back into the bladders. Moved 1 ton at a time. The parking stand inside the hangar had sunk and needed to be padded with more 2"x4" timbers. Also, the wall opening into the hangar had to be reinforced as 2 m of wall was knocked over while docking the hovercraft in a side wind. Removed ice from radiation instruments twice during the day.

Saturday 20 September.

Position: 87 26.2' N, 171 10' E, temperature -5° C, air pressure 1030 hPa, wind 2 knots from the S. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards NE. Worked on ice walls for the wash room. Checked radiation flux instrument three times for ice.

Sunday 21 September.

Position: 87 26.5' N, 171 36' E, temperature -8° C, air pressure 1030 hPa, wind 4 knots from S. Worked on putting a tarp over the 80 m² main hangar. We were pleased with the result. Checked radiation flux instruments for ice twice.

The fourth week of ice drift (22 - 28 Sept. 2014)

Ice drift

The camp drifted 38 nautical miles (70 km) during the last week, generally towards the north and partly perpendicular to the Lomonosov Ridge (Fig. 1). The ice moves at a speed of about 2% of the wind speed as observed by Nansen. Our motion during the week has largely been determined by a deep low pressure system which moved through the Fram Strait and was centered at the North Pole on Tuesday 23 September and our position the next day. Wind speeds were 30-33 knots during Wednesday afternoon, coming down to 20 knots through Thursday.

Fig. 1 Ice drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 4 is shown by white stippled track.

Camp life

Construction of the FRAM-2014/15 ice camp was completed on Saturday (Figs. 2 and 3). The direction of the ice drift relative to our target area has allowed us to invest about 2 weeks of full attention to obtain a net 128 m² area of protected working conditions at a reasonable price. All the building materials are locally derived, except for tarps from sail maker Iversen, Bergen, some 2" x 4" lumber and a few sheets of plywood.

We had to contend with establishing the camp on first year ice. The bearing capacity of a visco-elastic ice sheet is primarily dependent on temperature and ice thickness. Present temperatures are still high and the 1.2 m thick ice is relatively soft. The ice camp is about 200 meter from the nearest lead and the ice and snow walls represent an estimated 30 ton load over a 14 m x 14 m area. The weight of the hovercraft and equipment represent another 10 tons. From published load capacity curves it appears we are at the limit of safe loading. Changes in relative water levels, as the construction progressed, suggests a down-bending of the order of 10% of the ice thickness.

Fig. 2 Cutting ice blocks for construction of the ice hangar at an adjacent refrozen melt water pond.

Drifting snow comes with high winds. Snow storms have their own charm, their message being; ... "Nature Rules"! Unfortunately they tend to turn your attention away from planned useful work to upkeep of the camp facilities. To our great relief, the 126 m² tarp over the ice hangar held up really well in winds over 30 knots . However, the winter is long, and in hindsight, criss-crossed tie-down straps should have been attached to the canvas every meter to properly secure the large tarp.

Protection from the wind chill is considered essential, and we also have an independent back-up solution for covering the hovercraft during the winter. Another issue we needed to clarify was; could we run the hovercraft propeller under the tarp? The variable pitch propeller always turns with the engine and we need the engine running to get hydraulic power to the winch and to drive the compressor. This also appeared to be no problem at all.

Fig. 3 The Fram-2014/15 camp completed

Science

Our oceanographic equipment suspended below the ice continuously monitor ocean currents in the upper 500 meters of the water column and at depths of 800 and 2000 m. Water depth is monitored by a 3.5 kHz echo sounder which gives a sub-bottom penetration of about 20 m. Within a 6 km radius of the camp are five autonomous buoys which also monitor water depth. On the ice, the radiation flux instruments are running, but icing is a problem for the sun time monitor and snow for the vertical IR skin temperature probe. The weather station appears robust.

On Wednesday, we started work on the seismic gear, an endeavor associated with a string of start-up, non-cold and cold-related problems not overcome until the afternoon on Saturday. You need high pressure air, a working airgun and a data logging system. We first discovered that the engine mounted hydraulic pump which power the compressor, as well as the winch, had sprung a seal, a problem we cannot fix here. However, a potential misfortune of this nature was foreseen and we

connected a spare external belt-driven pump. The compressor did not like the cold and a heated enclosure had to be built. On the first try, the pump drive belt started screaming, because the load from the viscous cold oil was too large - we also needed to pre-heat the oil reservoir. Once we are in operation, you start the main engine every few hours and the pre-heat issue goes away. Getting the air-gun going was trickier. As air pressure was applied, the relatively new and little-used Bolt PAR 0.3 liter air-gun did not close, but started firing rapidly on the floor (auto-fire). We dismantled the device completely and changed every visible seal, put it together again, but the result was still auto-firing. At this point we consulted with external marine seismic industry expertise, all suggesting the problem was the solenoid valve which controls the air supply to the piston. However, Einar Gjestrum (retired), who last worked with Bolt air-guns over 30 years ago, was more specific; "It is an O-ring which has part number 640", he said, and that was correct! We also had to consult with our institutional expertise on communications port allocation issues related to the gun control box to get the data logging system to work right.

The air gun is giving a penetration of about 2 km below the seabed. Seismic lines from icebreaker surveys suggest this is the maximum sediment thickness in this part of Makarov Basin. During the short time we have been in operation, the ice drift has taken us parallel to the trend which is assumed to be a large fracture zone along the foot of slope of Lomonosov Ridge. The geologically significant issue is whether or not we can see any sign of deformation in the deepest sediments.

The sun will go below the horizon on Tuesday 30 Sept. at this latitude and be back about 15 March.

Wild life

No sign of animal life in any form during the week

All is well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 22 September.

Position: 87 25.3' N, 171 49' E, temperature -7° C, air pressure 1007 hPa, wind 7 knots from WSW.
Worked all day securing the tarp. Checked radiation flux instruments twice and removed ice.

Tuesday 23 September.

Position: 87 25.9' N, 173 44' E, temperature -10° C, air pressure 1004 hPa, wind 15 knots from SE. Ice drift 0.4 knots towards NE. Finished the last wall of the bathroom, and with that, all ice the hall construction work is finished. Drifting snow and 15-20 knot winds all day. Checked Met.no radiation flux instruments for ice twice during the day.

Wednesday 24 September.

Position: 87 31.5' N, 175 26' E, temperature -8° C, air pressure 990 hPa, wind 22 knots from E.
Drifting snow. Ice drift 0.4 knots towards NNE. Wind speeds 30-33 knots in the afternoon and evening.
Started preparations for seismic reflection measurements. The compressor needs to be pre-heated and an insulated enclosure had to be made. Worked on getting the data logging system up and had support from Bergen via Iridium to tackle computer communications port allocation issues. Audun worked all day securing the tarp over the ice hangar.

Thursday 25 September.

Position: 87 43.9' N, 174 43' E, temperature -13° C, air pressure 1003 hPa, wind 20 knots from NE.
Ice drift 0.3 knots towards NW.

Data logging system running. Discovered the hydraulic pump for driving the compressor and winch had blown a seal and hydraulic oil was routed into the main engine. Prepared spare belt-driven external pump. When pressure was put on the Bolt PAR airgun before being put in the water, the gun went into auto-fire and would not close. The gun was completely dismantled and all visible O-rings were changed. On the next try, the gun still went into auto-fire.

Friday 26 September.

Position: 87 47.9' N, 173 39' E, temperature -8° C, air pressure 1007 hPa, wind 8 knots from ENE.

Contacted old hands with long industry experience from marine seismic surveys. Most suggestions pointed to the solenoid valve which controls air flow, but Einar Gjestrum who last worked with Bolt air-guns for GECO about 30 years ago was more specific. It is "O-ring; part number 640", he said, and

that was really the problem. When started cold, the belt driven hydraulic pump struggles, because of the viscosity of cold oil. This means that we have to pre-heat both the compressor and the hydraulic oil reservoir every time we need to recharge the air tanks for the airgun. It is cumbersome, but not a logistical problem. Removed ice from the radiation flux instruments. Audun put up a tarp over the store room.

Saturday 27 September.

Position: 87 50.1' N, 173 35' E, temperature -6° C, air pressure 1006 hPa, wind 3 knots from NE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards NE. Two centimeter of new snow on the ground. Start up of seismic reflection measurements delayed by intermittent loss of the hydrophone signal. The problem was a defective power plug. At 1640 hours, we were finally acquiring seismic data. Put the generator on styrofoam pads to reduce the acoustic noise transmitted via the ice into the water. Checked radiation flux instrumentation and removed ice from the sun time sensor and snow from the IR-sensor. Audun worked on finishing the bath room.

The ice has sunken about 20 cm relative to the water level due to the load of the camp, probably augmented by regional compression during the recent days of strong wind and ice drift. In the annex for geology & geophysics, we have to recover the frozen-in floor and wood frame to adjust to the new level.

Sunday 28 September.

Position: 87 51.7' N, 173 59' E, temperature -10° C, air pressure 1006 hPa, wind 6 knots from SE. Acquiring seismic data. Penetration about 2 km below the seabed over the abyssal plain using the 0.3 liter air-gun fired every 25 meter. Audun worked on the bathroom.

The fifth week of ice drift (29 Sept. - 05 Oct. 2014)

Ice drift

The motion of the vast fields of sea ice in the Arctic Ocean is mainly driven by the surface winds. Passing low pressure systems are associated with strong and changing winds and this is certainly why our fifth week on the ice became more eventful than appreciated. The intense low pressure that passed Northern Norway in the early hours of Saturday 27 September reached Franz Josef Land the next day and moved onwards to the North Pole where it remained stationary for almost 3 days. The wind speed in our area increased to 26 knots (ice drift 0.5 knots) by midnight on Sunday, reached 42 knots on Monday morning (ice drift 0.8 knots) and remained over 30 knots (ice drift 0.5 knots) for the next 24 hours.

Fig 1. Position of FRAM-2014/15 (black triangle) as of Sunday 6 October.

Camp life

Drifting snow made outside work impossible. The high winds from East and South-East deposited a snow bank on the upwind side and two drifts about 70 m long on each side of the ice hangar. By coincidence, the position of one of the flanking drifts buried our outside storage area for equipment (Figs 2-4). Our conservative estimate of excess volume of snow is about 700 cubic meters which represents a load of about 200-250 tons, i.e. more than five times the weight of the ice hangar and the hovercraft. Relatively warm air with temperatures in the range minus 8° to minus 5° C persisted from Saturday 27th through Thursday October 2nd and kept the sea ice cover weak. The response of the visco-elastic ice sheet to the extra load was subsidence which implied 10 cm of sea water on top of the ice by Monday. By Tuesday the increase in water level relative to the ice surface reached 45 cm since the start of construction. Normal rubber boots were not high enough and survival suits were needed to move around. Our first priority was to get our equipment (estimated at 3 tons) out of the snow and water and move it about 30 meters. We also needed to temporarily move the hovercraft out of the hangar, as otherwise the skirt would freeze in. The hovercraft was parked at a new site 50 m away, a new 1 m x 1 m hole was made through 1.5 m of ice and the work tent put up over the hole. By Saturday, we had overcome most of the disruptions, but will in the near future have to contend with poorer working conditions and exposure to the wind chill. At this point, the ice drift had brought us within 6 nautical mile of the 3000 m contour at the foot of the slope of the Lomonosov Ridge and temperatures dropped to minus 18° C. We still had cold-related work challenges to sort out in order to be ready for the geological work (Fig. 4). It has been a busy week and we are still in the start-up phase. Officially, our working day has, to some extent, followed the time zone of our position in order to maximize the remaining amount of daylight. However, in reality it is floating through all time zones depending on what needs to be done, and at what time your body signals that now it is more than enough. In about two weeks, we expect the 0.5 m thick water layer on top of the ice will be frozen solid and we can move back into the ice hangar and settle in.

Fig. 2 Snow drifts formed on both sides of the ice hangar and on the up-wind side in the back (not seen).

Fig. 3 Scaling the snow drift on the east side of the ice hangar.

Fig. 4 Digging out sediment corers from the lower half meter of water-logged snow.

So the lesson from this week is that the weight you put on the ice is one thing, what really matters are the aerodynamic consequences of the obstructions you make.

Science

The autonomous oceanographic instruments, which include an acoustic Doppler depth profiler (0-500 m) and two current meters hanging from the ice (at 800 and 2000 m depths), are running. The surface instruments are the weather station and instruments for measuring radiation fluxes.

On Sunday, we started on the initial calibration run with the thermistors for the turbulence measurements, but aborted due to problems with the meter wheel.

Ocean depth is measured by a drifting array of echo sounders over a 6 km distance formed by the 3.5 kHz echo sounder suspended through the hydro hole by the hovercraft and 5 autonomous buoys. On the approach to the foot of the slope of the Lomonosov Ridge, we observed strong lateral amplitude variations in the upper 20 m of sediments penetrated by the 3.5 kHz echo sounder. This may be due to sheets of sandy sediments from small mass wasting events on the sediment-starved slope of Lomonosov Ridge. In contrast, the signal amplitudes of the echo return over the abyssal plain farther out in the Makarov Basin showed great lateral continuity.

Fig. 5 Deploying the airgun in the flooded hydro hole.

The seismic reflection measurements was in operation from the afternoon on Saturday 27 September using a 0.3 liter air-gun and recording with a single hydrophone. Sub-bottom penetration was about 2 km. The ice drift increased from 0.2 knots to 0.8 knots in the high winds in the early hours on Monday morning. In order to maintain one shot point every 25 m, the air-gun fired at 70

second intervals. At every shot, about 40 liters of air (pressure 1 atmosphere) is released into the water. At the high drift rate, we observed that all the released air missed the hole in the ice 5 meters above. Instead of venting through the hydro-hole, the air gets trapped and accumulated somewhere else below the ice. Some air will leak out, but a sub-ice air cushion will change the local stress field which in turn may become an attractor for regional ice crack propagation. In the past, use of air-guns have been blamed for ice camp break-ups, but the relation is probably in the category of myths. Cracking of the ice floe and lead formation does by no means represent a danger, but is an inconvenience. We pulled the gun up to 2 meters below the ice and the same thing happened. At this point, we stopped shooting.

Wild life

No form of animal life has been observed during the week.

All is well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 29 September.

Position: 87 57.5' N, 175 57' E, temperature -8° C, air pressure 997 hPa, wind 32 knots from E. Ice drift 0.8 knots towards NNE. Water depth is 3998 m. Stopped shooting the air gun as the released air did not hit the hole in the ice, but deflected and accumulated somewhere else under the ice. Water level in the hangar has risen 10 cm since yesterday. Have to use the survival suits to be able to move around. Worked to free frozen-in parts of the hovercraft skirt now under water.

Tuesday 30 September.

Position: 88 11.6' N, 179 50' W, temperature -5° C, air pressure 992 hPa, wind 27-32 knots from E. Ice drift 0.5 knots towards northeast. The water level has risen another 20 cm during the last 24 hours, total change is 45 cm. Increases have been stepwise and during periods of high winds. Snow drifts have formed upwind from the ice hangar with two about 70 m long ridges (crests at 1.5 m above the ice) on either side, and have enlarged earlier smaller accumulations. A rough conservative assessment of excess snow volume gives a figure of about 700 cubic meters which has a weight of about 200-250 tons. The area of visible water on the ice is elongated within the area covered by the snow ridges. Moved the generator one pallet higher.

Wednesday 1 October.

Position: 88 20' N, 176 28' W, temperature -5° C, air pressure 1003 hPa, wind 3 knots from ESE. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards northeast. The wind calmed down in the morning. Started excavating equipment and food supplies from the snow drift. Our day has changed a bit; had dinner at 0600 hours and went to bed at 0800 hours. Woke up and started a new day at 1530 hours. Moved equipment and food from the water-logged snow drift to a small ridge about 30 m away.

Thursday 2 October

Position: 88 26' N, 176 04' W, temperature -7° C, air pressure 1018 hPa, wind 9 knots from ENE. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards NNE. Worked from midnight to 0900 hours moving our equipment to the new location. Had dinner at 0900 hours and went to bed at 1200 hours. Started again at 1800 hours. Checked radiation flux instruments for snow and ice.

Friday 3 October.

Position: 88 29.5' N, 175 23' W, temperature -10° C, air pressure 1023 hPa, wind 10 knots from NNE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards NNE. Started preparation for moving the hovercraft to a new location. Had to use survival suits because of the water level in the ice/snow building. Backed the hovercraft out from the ice hangar

and parked about 50 m away on pallets. Noticed sudden loss of lift and established that the lift fan belt was broken. We are now exposed to the wind chill during all work outside of the cabin.

Saturday 4 October.

Position: 88 33.2' N, 176 14' W, temperature -13° C, air pressure 1035 hPa, wind 4 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards NE. We are 6 nautical miles from the 3000 m depth contour of the Lomonosov Ridge. Audun made a 1m x 1 m hole through the 1.5 meter thick ice. We put up and attached the work tent to the hovercraft. Moved geological equipment into the tent. All items were full of ice and snow. A heated box had to be made to thaw out everything.

Sunday 5 October.

Position: 88 34.5' N, 176 39' W, temperature -14° C, air pressure 1035 hPa, wind 2 knots from N. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards ENE. Worked on mounting the hydraulics for the winch. The winch and all hoses had to be thawed out. Started calibration run for the string of sea water temperature loggers, but aborted due to the problems with the meter wheel. Had problems with the signal from the 3.5 kHz echo sounder transducer, but then the signal came back - the cause of the problem remains unexplained. The water depth is 3988 m.

The sixth week of ice drift (06 - 12 Oct 2014)

Ice drift and camp life

The ice camp has drifted about 27 nautical miles (50 km) to the north-northwest during the week. The weather situation has been characterized by a persistent high pressure, calm winds, but low temperatures reaching minus 26 C on Friday morning. Being temporarily forced away from the ice hangar, the hovercraft is now unprotected against the wind chill where temperatures reached -35° C several times this week. Inside the cabin we have a comfortable 20-27° C, and the condensation problems are eliminated by covering parts of the superstructure with insulating Glava winter mats, normally used for temporary protection of a worksite during construction.

Fig. 1 Drift path of FRAM-2014/15 during the sixth week on the ice

However, working conditions outside are demanding. Audun has built a small lee wall around the work tent to provide some protection. The hydraulic winch and take-up drum work fine under these conditions, but it is clear that it is not practically feasible for us to rig the hydrostatic corer under these tough circumstances; in the more spacious ice hangar yes, but not here. We have had to stay with a smaller gravity corer and the dredges. We expect to move back into the hangar in a week or so and have measured the ice thickness by drilling in several places; in most cases the ice appears to be 1.5 m thick.

On Sunday 13 Oct. we were drifting over the intra-ridge basin plain in 2500 m water depth shooting seismic reflection and things were running well. At this point we declared Sunday a day of rest; the first of its kind since *Polarstern* left us six weeks ago.

Fig. 2 Current location about 50 m from the ice hangar

Science

Having partly recovered from the disruption cause by the weather situation the week before last, we finally deployed Ilker Fer's 300 meter long vertical array of 30 thermistors. First a calibration run was made. His motivation is to quantify processes leading to vertical transport of oceanic heat; how efficient is oceanic heat transport for melting the ice?. This "thermistor string", combined with the acoustic Doppler current profiler enable characterization of the background internal wave-field. Ilker Fer has made short visits (2006-2008) to the Russian ice station Barneo at 89° North to carry out similar experiments including hiring a helicopter to obtain ocean microstructure across the Lomonosov Ridge. The presence of the large Lomonosov Ridge could possibly enhance vertical mixing

processes. The FRAM-2014/15 deployment, which traverses the Lomonosov Ridge and continues more than 1000 km towards the Fram Strait, will greatly enhance his observational data base.

The autonomous oceanographic instruments; an acoustic Doppler depth profiler (0-500 m) and two current meters hanging from the ice (800 and 2000 m depth), are running. The surface instruments are the weather station and instruments for measuring radiation fluxes.

Ocean depth is measured at six locations within a 6 x 6 km area by the echo sounder at the camp and 5 autonomous buoys reporting via Iridium.

We were concerned that the deep (2000 m) current meter would hit bottom where the Lomonosov Ridge topography shallows to about 1100 m. The Kevlar line going through the ice was protected by a 2 mm long orange plastic tube picked up from the roadside in Longyearbyen. Audun poured 3 liters of hot water into the tube and it was freed from the ice in no time. Reminiscent of Nansen's men pulling the sounding line over their backs, we man-hauled the 2 km line with the current meter at the end for about 150 m to connect up with the geology winch at the hovercraft. The current meter was then lifted to 1050 m depth and will be lowered again once the ridge is crossed.

The main objective of FRAM-2014/15 is geology. The original plan targeted Alpha Ridge which represents a vast area with many known and unknown localities for recovery of Mesozoic sediments. Earlier ice drift observations suggested the ice camp would stay within the area of interest on the order of several months to half a year and even more. As the icebreaker was not able to reach the fringes of Alpha Ridge, Lomonosov Ridge became the alternative, and it presents a raw deal. As the drift direction is directly across the ridge, potential targets would be present over a drift distance of only 12 nautical miles which would be covered in 2-3 days. Beyond that, no second chances! There are only a few hours of twilight at local noon, and it is too risky to drive upstream to look for second chances at this time of the year.

Fig. 3 The data logging system onboard *Sabvabaa*

Our drift path crossed the Lomonosov Ridge where an intra-ridge basin is present. As we passed the 3000 m depth contour on our way upslope, we inferred the presence of steep inclines from multiple diffraction hyperbolae. We deployed the small gravity corer, which must have hit something hard as the recovery was a mere 5 cm of sediments beyond the core catcher. We then lowered the dredge in 2324 m water depth. We lifted off the bottom 2.5 hours later, but it came up empty. Passing the ridge crest, we attempted another dredge haul in 1383 m water depth and let it stay down until the water depth increased to 1690 m. The recovery was only two fist size rock specimens which may just be glacial erratics. From the echo sounder record no outcrops were encountered downslope into the intra-ridge basin.

The operational cold problems with the seismic reflection measurements were overcome and now run smoothly. We keep heat on the compressor at all times and pump air at two hour intervals to prevent the hydraulic oil driving the compressor from being too cold. Sub-bottom penetration in the intra-ridge basin (2500 m water depth) is over 3 seconds (> 3 km) two-way travel time using a 0.3 liter (20 in³) air-gun and recording the signal from a single hydrophone.

Fig 4. Screen shot from seismic data acquisition across the intra-ridge basin.

Wild life

Audun observed fresh tracks of one adult and one or possibly two cubs near the camp on Friday. They kept at a distance probably due to the noise from the generator.

Life is treating us well beyond the trivial problems of the cold environment. We have passed 89° North and the direction of drift is more or less due north.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 6 October.

Position: 88 36' N, 176 15' E, temperature -13° C, air pressure 1038 hPa, wind 3 knots from NNE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards NNE . The 3000 m Kevlar line has so far only been hand-spoiled onto the take-up drum and left about 150 m of line which did not fit. We had to redo the job, but now with a small weight and all 3000 m in the water. The drum was originally designed to be laid down horizontally on the deck to distribute the weight, but we started off using it in a vertical position as spooling became more convenient. This was a mistake because of the pressure exerted on the sides. As a result, it took the whole day to get the job done. Completed calibration down to 300 m depth of Ilker Fer's thermistor chain.

Tuesday 7 October

Position: 88 39' N, 177 03' E, temperature -16° C, air pressure 1041 hPa, wind 8 knots from NNW. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards NW. Prepared a small gravity corer for the first coring run to be made. We have, so far during the whole 6 weeks on the ice, been in water depths beyond the reach of our 3000 m long kevlar line. We passed the 3000 m contour by mid-day. At 1900 hours, the corer hit bottom in 2470 m water depth. It came up with only 5 cm of brown mud behind the core catcher - we must have hit something hard and the 3.5 kHz echo sounder showed a confused pattern of diffraction hyperbolae. All sensors on the weather station completely covered with rime - removed all. On the radiation flux instrumentation, the sun time sensor was covered with rime and IR sensor with snow - remove all.

Wednesday 8 October.

Position: 88 44.6' N, 178 26' E, temperature -15° C, air pressure 1028 hPa, wind 14 knots from N. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards NW. Based on the anticipated hard bottom from the coring attempt and the 3.5 kHz image of the seabed, we lowered the dredge in 2325 m water depth. Increased ice drift gave a wire angle and during ascent the Kevlar line cut into the side of the hydro hole. When the dredge came up under the ice we could not recover it, but could see that it was empty. We had to cut the line and leave the dredge until time allowed recovery. As the water depth shallowed relatively fast, our immediate concern was the current meter hanging from the ice at 2000 m depth would soon hit the bottom topography. The Kevlar line had a plastic tube (2 cm diameter) protection through the ice and with 3 liters of hot water it came loose. We man-hauled the line the first hundred meters and hooked on to the geology winch. Raised the current meter (10909) to 1050 m and secured. The job took 4 hours. Deployed Ilker Fer's string of 30 thermistors, one for every 10 meter down to 300 meter depth.

Thursday 9 October.

Position: 88 47.4' N, 177 01' E, temperature -14° C, air pressure 1020 hPa, wind 6 knots from the NNE. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards NW. Lowered the dredge in 1383 m of water - put out 2000 meter of line. Kept the dredge out until 1690 m water depth ten hours later and recovered. The dredge was 1/3 full of brown mud and two fist sized rock specimens; one angular and one rounded. The Knudsen 3.5 kHz echo sounder signal disappeared in the morning. We can hear the trigger signal at all four transducers, but no power. Put in the 12 kHz transducer instead. The output signal also weakened after a while. Sounds like we have a short somewhere, but unable to locate exact spot in the electronics. Prepared a heated enclosure for the compressor.

Friday 10 October.

Position: 88 50' N, 177 21' E, temperature -19° C, air pressure 1017 hPa, wind 4 knots from N. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards NNW. Minimum temperature during the night was -26° C. Started shooting seismic after preheating oil reservoir and compressor. The compressor is kept heated at all times and if we refill air at least every two hours the oil for the pump keeps sufficient temperature without preheating every time it is used. We have now descended the southern rim of the intra-ridge basin and are at the foot of slope. The water depth is about 2400 m and the seismic signal has a sub-bottom penetration over 3 seconds. Audun discovered polar bear tracks near the camp; one adult and one or two cubs. They had wandered around by our fuel storage area, and ignored the food stored nearby, probably frightened by the sound of the generator.

Saturday 11 October.

Position: 88 54' N, 177 22' E, temperature -23° C, air pressure 1017 hPa, wind 7 knots from N. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards N. Shooting seismic continuously. A horrible 50 Hz noise signal appeared, and the source was most likely the generator which we need on continuously. We grounded the lines at both ends and the problem disappeared. Audun restored continuous power for charging the battery of the radiation flux measurements. The power had been interrupted when we moved out of the ice hangar. Cleared rime and snow from the weather station. At the radiation flux site, the sun time detector was covered with rime and the IR detector with snow while the radiation detectors were fine.

Sunday 12 October.

Position: 88 58.6' N, 175 47' E, temperature -19° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 10 knots from N. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards N. Shooting seismic reflection continuously. We pump the 40 liter air reservoir up to 200 bar every two hours. A constant 130 bar pressure on the airgun is maintained via a pressure reduction valve. All instruments work well. As we are over a deep plain and the operation runs well, we declared Sunday as a day for rest - the first in six weeks. We passed 89° North by mid-day and the drift direction is near due north.

The seventh week of ice drift (13- 19 Oct. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 20 nautical miles (37 km) during the week (see picture). A strong high pressure cell covered the whole Arctic Ocean during the week until Saturday when our location started to feel the effect of a low pressure system arriving from east of Svalbard. In the high pressure situation, the ice drift was towards the east and parallel to the Lomonosov Ridge. It turned southeast and across the Lomonosov Ridge when the low pressure system arrived. This suddenly gave us new opportunities - a gift in spite of the adversities associated with low pressure passages such as high winds and blowing snow.

Fig. 1 FRAM-2014/15 drift track (red) 13-20 October 2014.

Sea ice dynamics

Our environment involves a spectrum of physical processes operating on time scales ranging from seconds to millions of years. Formation and destruction of sea ice are parts of this picture. The activity at the FRAM-2014/15 ice camp this week was dominated by fighting the effects of sea ice dynamics; cracking, shear motion, subduction and pressure ridge formation, we had it all. Since sea ice represents an elastic plate overlying a fluid, sea ice dynamics represents an attractive analogue on a readily observable time scale for the interaction between the "rigid" geologic plates which form the Earth's surface. Certainly, an attractive analogue for a desk scientist, but the attraction gets partly lost when you have your "boots on the ice" dealing with the consequences of sea ice dynamics.

On Monday morning, Audun observed a 10 cm wide crack that went straight through the middle of the deserted ice hangar (see picture). By Thursday, the crack had become 7 m wide and the eastern half of the hangar had moved about 20 m along the direction of the crack. Our current operation is about 35 m away to the west of the crack. At the same time, another crack opened on the other side of the hovercraft the same distance away and widened to a few meters. Forty meters to the south of the hovercraft, ice belonging to the floe we were sitting on was being thrust under the ice to the south and a 3 m high pressure ridge formed on Thursday. Since then, there has been no ice motion in our immediate area. We evaluated the situation and decided to stay where we are for the time being. We are currently shooting seismics which is an around the clock operation and bi-hourly surveillance of the ice conditions in the surroundings is part of the routine.

Fig. 2 An ice crack going right through the middle of the ice hangar.

All ice deformation processes are relatively slow. In the fast case, a crack may become half a meter wide in about 15 minutes. The potential damage is rupture of cables, but it does in no way represent a life threatening situation. Anything that directly affects the hovercraft is noticed instantly and we can relocate within minutes. The need to move away from a crack is most often not immediate, but a longer term consideration. Local ice divergence may later turn to ice convergence and the thin and weak ice of a refrozen lead will then be the site of pressure ridge formation. Continued pressure ridge formation may ultimately consume part of an ice floe and whatever items are left on the floe.

Sea ice dynamics is a fundamental process of the sea ice cover. Undisturbed sea ice reaches a thickness of about 2.5 meter by thermodynamic processes. If the ice is much thicker, it is because it has been involved in ice deformation during its life time. If you want to do science from drifting sea ice, you do that with the full knowledge that sea ice deformation may involve your location sooner or later, and perhaps even several times. A deformation event at your location is not an unforeseen disaster, but the consequence of a calculated risk you must be prepared for. This time, we lost the ice hangar and the work invested in that gamble, but lessons were learned.

Camp life

Fig. 3 The low sun and the red horizon

We now need a head lamp to do any work outside the hovercraft. On days with overcast, we have complete darkness, while on the rare clear days we are reminded of the sun by a red horizon (Fig. 3). At 89° North, the difference in sun elevation is about 1 degree between mid-day and mid-night which makes only a minor difference in light conditions. On days with overcast, it is completely dark while we are reminded about the presence of the sun only on relatively clear days. To the left of the hovercraft is the lit work tent behind a lee wall of snow blocks. The walls of the ice hangar are to the right.

Science

As stated in earlier reports, the autonomous oceanographic instruments, which include an acoustic Doppler depth profiler (0-500 m) and two current meters hanging from the ice (800 and now 1050 m depth), are running. The surface instruments are the weather station and instruments for measuring radiation fluxes. Ocean depth is measured by a drifting array of five autonomous echo sounders over a 6 km distance. We have problems with weak power output from the camp echo sounder, giving no bottom return in deep water. However, water depth information at the camp is obtained from the seismic data. The seismic reflection measurements run well.

The influence of the low pressure system arriving from Svalbard changed the ice drift from being parallel to the Lomonosov Ridge to across the ridge. By late Sunday night, the water depth had shallowed from 3300 m to 2600 m. We are shooting seismic and the bottom dredge is out.

The crack which opened through the ice hangar passed about 5 m from the thermistor string. We therefore decided to relocate the string and started to pull it up on Thursday. In the process, we discovered that our hydrophone would soon be lost to an advancing pressure ridge and had to deal with the latter problem immediately. On the third attempt, we managed to melt the hydrophone out on Friday when the site was 2 meter away from the advancing pressure ridge. Subsequently, the thermistor string was redeployed, the highest thermistor being 1.3 m below the underside of the ice.

On Monday, we deployed a GoPro camera and lights in pressure cases mounted on a sled to obtain video shots of the seabed some 2650 m depth below the ice camp. We obtained useful footage, but the field of view is limited as one of the lights failed. A short video segment is attached to this report.

Other activities

No signs of animal life was been observed during the week. However, we had visitors in the form of a submarine which surfaced about 3 nautical miles from our camp. Good neighbors pay visits to each other. Our attempt to visit failed as the vessel of unknown identity submerged when less than 100 m away from us (Fig. 3).

Fig. 4. The submarine in the process of submerging as we approached.

Life is treating us well, except for the merciless sea ice dynamics.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 13 October.

Position: 89 04.5' N, 175 57' E, temperature -17° C, air pressure 1021 hPa, wind 22 knots from NNE. Ice drift 0.4 knots towards North. Checked the radiation flux instruments after midnight. Sun time detector covered with rime and IR detector with snow. Shooting seismic reflection all day. At 1030 hours, Audun discovered a 10 cm wide crack in the ice right through the middle of the ice hangar. Two boxes of food needed to be moved away from the crack. We lowered a GoPro camera and lights mounted on a camera sled down to the bottom at 2650 m depth and obtained video images of the sea floor.

Tuesday 14 October.

Position: 89 08,9' N, 177 35' E, temperature -14° C, air pressure 1031 hPa, wind 11 knots from ENE. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards NNE. Stopped the air-gun at 0517 hours as we had a new crack through the ice widening several meters on the port side about 20 m away from the hovercraft. Another parallel crack 10 cm wide passes 5 m away from the craft. Hovercraft maintenance all day - replaced broken lift fan belt. Also removed the four jack-up legs and placed the hovercraft on four pallets. Felt a jerk of the ice floe. Audun observed a single 3 meter high pressure ridge about 30 meter to the south of the hovercraft. We evaluated the ice situation and decided to wait it out.

Wednesday 15 October.

Position: 89 17.6' N, 179 36' W, temperature -9° C, air pressure 1031 hPa, wind 11 knots from ENE. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards east. We are drifting along the bathymetric contours of the Lomonosov Ridge. Hovercraft maintenance all day; adjusting the lift fan belt. No ice activity observed.

Thursday 16 October

Position: 89 19' N, 174 51' W, temperature -8° C, air pressure 1036 hPa, wind 5 knots from E. Ice drift 0.1 knots toward east. Started recovery of the thermistor string as it is only 5 m away from a crack that has widened 3 m. The thin ice on refrozen leads are likely sites of future pressure ridge formation. Having recovered half (150 m), we discovered that the hydrophone was about to be consumed by the pressure ridge south of the hovercraft. Started to melt out the hydrophone, but was not successful. The 12 kHz echo sounder is giving us problems with weak or no bottom returns ; recovered the transducer. In the evening. we spotted lights in a distance. Turned out to be a submarine on the surface in position: 89 17.5' N, 172 42.9' W. We were not able to identify it.

Friday 17 October.

Position: 89 20.6' N, 168 43' W, temperature -13° C, air pressure 1036 hPa, wind 3 knots from NE. Ice drift 0.15 knots towards east. Finally able to recover the hydrophone. Redeployed the 300 m long thermistor string in the vicinity of the radiation flux instrument. The radiation flux instruments have been without power for several days. Laid out a cable across the lead and started charging. Cleaned all detectors. Also the weather station was completely covered with frost, cleaned all detectors. A small crack is going in between the guide wires, but no significant movement seen.

Saturday 18 October.

Position: 89 20.4' N, 164 41' W, temperature -13° C, air pressure 1034 hPa, wind 6 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards east. Shooting seismic all day. Audun moving food box away from the large crack (7 m wide).

Sunday 19 October.

Position: 89 18.7' N, 157 08' W, temperature -17° C, air pressure 1028 hPa, wind 12 knots from ESE. Ice drift 0.3 knot towards ESE (back across Lomonosov Ridge). Blowing snow all day. Acquiring seismic reflection data all day. The dredge is out with 3000 m Kevlar in anticipation of shallower water early Monday morning.

The eighth week of ice drift (20 - 26 Oct. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 35 nautical miles (65 km) during the week (Fig. 1) and of all things possible brought us back across the Lomonosov Ridge - what more could we ask for?. This was a result of a very pronounced high pressure system over the Arctic Ocean from the North Pole towards Alaska which must have expanded the Beaufort Gyre. This ice motion was augmented from Wednesday on by a low pressure trough which extended up from the Fram Strait. We drifted across Lomonosov Ridge and a few kilometers into the abyssal plain in the Makarov Basin, before the drift weakened and we turned back towards the ridge on Saturday. This development was a huge bonus to us, because it gave us new possibilities and three crossings of the ridge rather than one. A similar drift path was experienced by the legendary Russian ice drift station NP-28 which operated over 2.5 years from an ice floe and crossed Lomonosov Ridge three times in 1987.

Fig. 1 Drift track of FRAM-2014/15 across Lomonosov Ridge during week 8

Sea ice dynamics

The ice has been relatively calm all week, although Audun discovered a new crack which became 3 m wide about 5 m away from the back of the hovercraft. After a while it closed with some shear motion and has since been quiet. We watch the situation closely; some cracks may represent a potential problem, others not, even if they are close. The dilemma is that relocation takes time; we are here to do science, and prefer to wait and see rather than jump for every new crack in the neighborhood. We have to be ready when we pass a potential target on the seabed, otherwise the opportunity is lost.

Camp life

Since we now have complete darkness, we have reverted back to follow Norwegian time. However, our day is determined by what we see on the sea floor and what action is needed. Sometimes the ice drift is 200 m per hour or less. You get a feeling of having plenty of time as you will not be home for Christmas anyway. Doing seismic reflection measurements 24 hours a day creates a special routine. Depending on the drift rate, a bang goes off in the water 3 m below the ice every 2-6 minutes and the hovercraft shakes. Your sleep cycle now becomes determined by the need to run the compressor every two hours 24/7. As a reward, your PC screen gives you a visual presentation of the acoustic layering in the sediments up to 2 km below the seabed.

We survive well because Audun is doing the cooking. Fish and meat alternate for dinner during weekdays. Saturdays are reserved for porridge (risengrynsgrøt).

Science

We are overseeing the following suite of continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- five autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.
- seismic reflection (0.3 liter air gun & single hydrophone), sub-bottom penetration ~2 km.

Oceanography:

- Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler 0 - 500 m depth.
- two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.
- thermistor string with 30 thermistors, from the surface to 300 m depth.

Atmosphere:

- measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.
- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station (wind, temperature and humidity).

Fig. 2. Seismic section across upper Makarov-facing flank of Lomonosov Ridge showing core location. The bubble pulse in the seismic signal is very pronounced when shooting under a flexing ice sheet.

Fig. 3 Sediment recovered at the unconformity at the base of the Cenozoic section.

The seismic reflection measurements are running really well and are our main tool in the search for bottom sampling targets. Sub-bottom penetration is sometimes over 2 sec two-way travel time (~2 km). Coming over the top of Lomonosov Ridge, we recognized in the seismic data the key features of the sediment cover on the ridge; a ~300 meter thick upper section of flat-lying sediments resting with an angular unconformity on underlying stratified rocks (Fig. 2). Scientific (ACEX) drilling on Lomonosov Ridge in 2004 showed the upper section to be younger than 56 million years. We dropped the sediment corer where we saw the potential for exposure of rocks below the unconformity and got 20 cm of very cohesive, light cream colored sediments - something we have not seen so far from the Arctic Ocean (Fig. 3).

Fig. 4 Sediment drift at the foot of slope in the Makarov Basin

The upper part of the slope of Lomonosov Ridge below the unconformity shows a prograding section towards Makarov Basin. However, a terrace at about 2000 m water depth is associated with a major change in tilt; in the deeper water towards the slope. The whole lower part of the slope appears to be formed by a large rotated fault block. At the foot of the slope, we observe a deposit with seismic characteristic of a sediment drift (Fig. 4). This observation carries an interesting message about sediment supply and past contour-following bottom currents strong enough to generate sediment drifts.

We deployed the rock dredge several times in anticipation of possible outcrops of more competent rocks, but with negative results. The few fist-sized rocks recovered are most likely glacial erratics.

We deployed the camera sled on top of Lomonosov Ridge in 1390 m of water and obtained about 30 minutes of video footage. A short video segment of reduced resolution is attached to this report. We would appreciate feedback from marine biologists regarding identification of the creatures observed by our bottom photography.

Being away

Field work requires you are away from home and from the office. How you cope with being away from home is a personal thing; coping with being away from the office is more of a perceptual issue (you imagine yourself being indispensable?). Modern communication helps to almost eliminate the distance to a remote field location; the satellite phone is next to you and so is the e-mail.

It has been a busy week in the *Sabvabaa* office on the drifting sea ice over Lomonosov Ridge. This report was delayed, because the priority was to submit the final revision to AGU's Journal of Geophysical Research of our paper which reports the results of two seasons of vibroseis exploration of the sub-ice geology in Antarctica's Dronning Maud Land. This is a first on the Antarctic continent using vibroseis technology and another joint cutting-edge science venture with our German colleagues at AWI. A huge volume of volcanic rocks, about 250 km wide, extends for 1.700 km below the floating ice shelves along the Dronning Maud Land continental margin and has its age and compositional equivalent in similar volcanic rocks in South Africa (the Lebombo and Mwenetzi-Save Monoclines).

Today, your PC can do extensive scientific data analysis. Beyond that you need a library. John K. Hall, the owner of the hovercraft, has generated an continuously updated digital library containing nearly 20.000 .pdf files of the published scientific literature for the Arctic Ocean in the fields of atmosphere, ice, oceanography, geology and solid earth physics, all stored on a small hard disc. So the work place is as complete as possible for an ice-going scientific platform which has the scaled-down capabilities of any modern research vessel, but is only twice the size of a life boat.

Wild life

No signs of animal life have been observed during the week

Life is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 20 October.

Position: 89 13.8' N, 149 23' W, temperature -14° C, air pressure 1030 hPa, wind 5 knots from ESE. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards southeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Replenish high pressure air supply by running the main engine for fifteen minutes every two hours. Recovered dredge #3 at 0500 hours - came up empty. The water depth was 2325 m. Lowered the rock dredge again. Checked the radiation flux instruments. Sun time detector covered with rime and IR detector with snow.

Tuesday 21 October.

Position: 89 11.5' N, 146 06' W, temperature -14° C, air pressure 1029 hPa, wind 10 knots from ESE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards the southeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Recovered dredge # 4 at 1900 hours. Twelve fist-sized rocks and one platy fragment in the bag, probably all glacial erratics. Deployed camera sled in 1390 m water depth on top of the Lomonosov Ridge at 2300 hours

Wednesday 22 October.

Position: 89 06.6' N, 140 44' W, temperature -16° C, air pressure 1017 hPa, wind 15 knots from SE. Ice drift 0.4 knots towards southeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun discovered a new 3 m wide crack in the ice only 5 m behind the hovercraft in the morning. The crack stopped widening and closed later in the day with some shear motion. Audun packed up the 3.5 kHz echo sounder in case we had to relocate. We are on top of Lomonosov Ridge approaching the edge on the Makarov Basin side.

Thursday 23 October

Position: 89 01.8' N, 137 5.3' W, temperature -17° C, air pressure 1023 hPa, wind 8 knots from SE. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards the southeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day. We could see on the seismic record that the top cover of sediments (~200 m thick) was thinning, and that sediments below an underlying angular unconformity were likely to be exposed at the sea bed. Dropped the small gravity corer at 1000 hours, targeting a suspected exposure..Had problems with the capstan drum so the core was not recovered until 8 hours later. Recovery was 20 cm of very cohesive light brown sediments. No significant ice activity observed today.

Friday 24 October.

Position: 88 55.2' N, 134 37' W, temperature -11° C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 23 knots from SSE. Ice drift 0.5 knots towards SSE. Dropped dredge # 4 to the seabed at 2400 m depth just after midnight, just in case any rock exposures would appear. Shooting seismic reflection all day. No significant ice activity observed .

Saturday 25 October.

Position: 88 49.6' N, 134 32' W, temperature -10° C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 13 knots from the NNE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards northeast. Shooting seismic all day. We just reached the foot of slope of Lomonosov Ridge in the Makarov Basin. The ice drift now turns back up the flank of the ridge. Dredge #4 returned empty.

Sunday 26 October.

Position: 88 57.7' N, 132 22' W, temperature -21° C, air pressure 1022 hPa, wind 4 knots from NE. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards northeast (back across Lomonosov Ridge). Acquiring seismic reflection data all day. We are moving upslope. Dropped the dredge in 2660 m of water. Audun is working on getting our sauna finished.

The ninth week of ice drift (27 Oct. - 2 Nov. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 25 nautical miles (46 km) during the week (Fig. 1). We moved from the foot of the slope in the Makarov Basin with water depth 4000 m to the upper slope of Lomonosov Ridge with water depths of about 1700 m. The weather situation has been characterized by a weak high pressure and very weak pressure gradients. No low pressure system reached into the central Arctic Ocean. As a result, the ice drift has been slow (0.2 knots) and from Wednesday 29 Oct. about 0.1 knots on a steady course towards the Fram Strait. To get the seismic reflection data, we fire a shot every 25 m, and with the slow ice drift, we needed 16 minutes to cover that distance.

Fig. 1 Drift track of FRAM-2014/15 across Lomonosov Ridge during week 9

Sea ice dynamics

We have not noticed any sea ice activity, formation of new cracks, or motion of pressure ridges during the week.

Camp life

Temperatures were -17° C to -21° C during the first part of the week, but fell to -27° C to -29° C after Thursday 30 Oct. When the temperature approaches minus 30° C, and there is 10 knots wind, the wind chill makes the felt temperature below minus 40° C. Work outside gets more difficult. We run the generator around the clock, because it gets difficult to start below minus 15° C, but more importantly, we need to keep the compressor warm at all times and also to heat the main engine. The main engine always starts on the first turn; it is needed for providing the hydraulics to power the winch and the compressor.

Science

We are overseeing the following suite of continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- five autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.
- seismic reflection (0.3 liter air-gun & single hydrophone), sub-bottom penetration ~2 km.

Oceanography:

- Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler 0- 500 m depth.
- two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depth, respectively.
- thermistor string with 30 thermistors; from the surface to 300 m depth.

Atmosphere:

- measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.
- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station (wind, temperature and humidity).

The seismic reflection measurements continue to run well in spite of air temperatures approaching minus 30° C. The operation has stabilized for the critical parts which are the hydraulic drive of the compressor and the compressor itself. The temperature in the water is of course stable at minus 1.7° C. We may at times get a misfire about every 20th shot, but injection of alcohol into the air line appears to cure the problem

A characteristic opaque seismic reflection event appears in the area near the foot of the slope of Lomonosov Ridge (Fig. 2). The acoustic image suggests an irregular upper surface and possible internal stratification remains unresolved. However, it does not have the characteristics of a hard rock interface, and deformed sediments are our favored preliminary interpretation of the unprocessed data (Fig. 2). One of the main scenarios for opening of the Amerasia Basin is shear along the foot of the slope of Lomonosov Ridge in the Makarov Basin (see Fig. 1). Evidence of deformed sediments is found on several other seismic profiles reaching beyond the foot of the slope and intersecting the main linear features of the partly buried topography.

Fig. 2 Sediments at the foot of the slope in the Makarov Basin

Fig. 3. Canyon on the lower Lomonosov Ridge slope facing Makarov Basin

On the lowermost part of the slope, we were drifting into a canyon which had one significant ledge along its western side (Fig. 3). We had the rock dredge out, but the dredge came up empty except

for two fist-sized rocks, most likely glacial drop stones. Moving out of the canyon over its more gently sloping eastern side, we dropped the core over a small ledge, but recovered only 1 meter of brown mud, most likely all recent sediments.

The sediments below the slope of Lomonosov Ridge along our drift track appear almost transparent deeper than about 0.4 sec below the sea bed. One possible explanation is a very homogenous sediment package which is kind of unusual for a continental margin.

Wild life

No signs of animal life has been observed during the week

Life is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 27 October.

Position: 88 54.1' N, 129 32' W, temperature -17° C, air pressure 1022 hPa, wind 8 knots from NE.

Ice drift 0.1 knots towards northeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day. The rock dredge is out.

Tuesday 28 October.

Position: 88 53,8' N, 124 32.7' W, temperature -19° C, air pressure 1024 hPa, wind 9 knots from E.

Ice drift 0.2 knots towards east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. We are moving along the lower slope and start crossing a canyon. The rock dredge is out.

Wednesday 29 October.

Position: 88 53.1' N, 122 55' W, temperature -19° C, air pressure 1019 hPa, wind 8 knots from SE.

Ice drift 0.4 knots towards southeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Recovered the rock dredge at 0200 hours. The dredge contained two small rock pieces, most likely glacial erratics. We drifted out of the canyon during the evening. Dropped the corer on a ledge in 2930 m water depth and recovered 1 meter of brown mud, probably all recent sediments. Submitted and uploaded via the internet the final revision of our paper to AGU's Journal

of Geophysical Research on the first vibroseis exploration of the sub-ice geology on the Antarctic continent.

Thursday 30 October

Position: 88 52.7' N, 121 48.7' W, temperature -18° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 3 knots from ENE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards east. Shooting seismic reflection all day.

Friday 31 October.

Position: 88 53.8' N, 120 18' W, temperature -23° C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 10 knots from NW. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards northeast. Cleaned the deck area and put the cover over the insulation mats over the cabin part of the hovercraft's superstructure.

Saturday 01 November.

Position: 88 56.2' N, 117 47.8' W, temperature -27° C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 16 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards east. Shooting seismic all day. We are passing 1800 m water depth on our way up the slope of Lomonosov Ridge. The ice drift is very slow as it takes 16 minutes to move the 25 m between air-gun seismic shots.

Sunday 02 November.

Position: 88 57.0' N, 115 58' W, temperature -27° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 2 knots from NNW. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards east. Checked radiation flux instruments. Radiation sensors are fine, sun time and IR skin temperature detectors completely covered with frost. Took sun time detector inside to thaw out.

The weather station sensors were also completely covered with frost.

The tenth week of ice drift (03 - 09 Nov. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 35 nautical miles (65 km) during the week (Fig. 1). In terms of sea bed topography, we moved across the top of Lomonosov Ridge for the third time during this expedition. At the beginning of the week, the surface air pressure was very uniform over the entire Arctic Ocean through Tuesday. The rapidly moving low pressure system that passed Northern Norway on Monday became stationary over the New Siberian Islands on Wednesday and slowly merged with a low pressure trough extending from the Bering Strait. The result was an Arctic Ocean characterized by a low pressure region on the Siberian side and high pressure on the Alaska, Canada and Greenland side. Winds at our position were less than 10 knots during the week except on Thursday (>20 knots) and during the weekend (15 knots).

Fig. 1 Drift track of FRAM-2014/15 across Lomonosov Ridge during week 10

Sea ice dynamics

We have not noticed any sea ice activity during the week. The ice drift speed has varied very little.

Camp life

We experienced the coldest week so far during the FRAM-2014/15 ice drift. Temperatures were below -30°C during the entire week and below -35°C Monday through Wednesday with a maximum on Wednesday 5th Nov. below -40°C . If we consider the wind chill, the felt temperatures were in the range of -55°C to -60°C (Fig. 2). It was rather amusing to discover that temperatures below -40°C were off-scale for our AirMar weather station on the hovercraft. Work outside was difficult. The seismic data acquisition was not interrupted, but the lowest temperature interval pushed our make-shift heat box for the compressor to the limit. The main engine started instantly as always and the engine pre-heat is continuously switched on. When the temperature came back above -30°C again on Sunday, it felt kind of warm being outside.

Fig. 2 Upper: Screen shot of the weather station display before it got out of range.
Lower: Audun getting some fresh air.

This cold spell was actually an important reality check for us as it posed several questions; i) is the hovercraft suited for this kind of harsh environmental conditions, and ii) are you physically and mentally prepared for this. The answers to both questions are; Yes. We are impressed with how well the hovercraft lives up to our expectations of providing comfortable accommodation and data logging facilities for our science program; the main issues being cabin temperature and condensation. One oven keeps the cabin temperature at +20 to +25° C for outside temperatures down to -30° C. When it gets colder than -30° C, the second oven is fired up and is capable of driving the cabin temperature beyond +30° C even if the outside temperature goes below -40° C. The water-borne heat from the radiator circuit on the floor around the cabin perimeter even makes it possible to comfortably walk with bare feet on the cabin's floor mat. Dripping water from the roof and windows due to condensation can be a serious threat to all instruments and the living comfort. Condensation problems inside the cabin are practically non-existent. The insulation of the cabin below deck level is provided by the approx. 20 cm thick air layer contained in the flotation tanks. Above deck, the cabin walls have 5 cm thick insulation built-in and windows of the same kind as in aircraft. We have covered the outside of the cabin and windows by 5 cm thick Glava winter mats. Above that is a form-fitted wind-tight cover which extends over the deck and over the skirt; only the two access doors are free.. In the rear of the hovercraft, we have left exposed everything from the air intake aft (Fig. 3).

As to the second question; we have both been exposed to similar conditions in the past and know what is involved. We have the necessary cold weather gear, and most importantly a comfortably heated safe heaven to retreat to.

Fig. 3. The hovercraft *Sabvabaa* dressed up for the cold at 89° N.

Fig. 4. The full moon shining 24 hours a day.

The low temperatures are associated with clear skies. We have a beautiful full moon which lightens up the landscape 24 hours a day - a "mid-night moon" so to speak. This is an incredible sight and gives you the feeling of being on another planet - an icy one.

Science

We are overseeing the following suite of continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- five autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.
- seismic reflection (0.3 liter air-gun & single hydrophone), sub-bottom penetration ~2 km.

Oceanography:

- Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler 0-500 m depth.
- two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.
- thermistor string with 30 thermistors from the surface to 300 m depth.

Atmosphere:

- measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station (wind, temperature and humidity).

The seismic reflection measurements continued to run well, unaffected by the cold spell. We crossed the top of Lomonosov Ridge and passed the level of the out-cropping(?) unconformity between the Cenozoic sediments and the older sediments below on both sides of the ridge (Fig. 5). While the level of the unconformity here is similar to the area where the scientific drilling (ACEX) took place in 2004, about 300 km away towards the Siberian side, the Cenozoic section is about 100 m thinner. On the Makarov Basin side, we first tried to obtain a core below the projected unconformity level, but the core catcher was mysteriously lost in the process and the core barrel returned empty. The rock dredge was immediately deployed, but hooked on to excess wire laid down as it hit bottom and came up backwards. Working in -35° C on Monday, these misfortunes were really low points and hard to accept. On Saturday, we drifted over the outcrop level on the Amundsen Basin flank of the ridge. We got cold-related winch problems and missed out on the steepest slope below the unconformity. When the corer returned, it was empty with only stains of mud on the core catcher. It must have hit something hard. Because of the darkness and the severe cold, we considered it too risky to leave our camp and drive upstream to make another attempt at sampling.

Fig. 5 Screen shot of the stratigraphic relationship below both flanks of Lomonosov Ridge

The acoustic image of rocks below the regional unconformity at the top of Lomonosov Ridge remains a mystery. The reflection pattern is a maze of randomly distributed diffractions with no apparent coherent reflections (Fig. 6). We have no velocity information to narrow down possible options.

Fig. 6 Characteristic acoustic image of rocks below the unconformity at the top of the ridge.

As we passed the top of the ridge towards the Amundsen Basin, we saw a huge block of back-tilted stratified sediments with younger sediments on top, resting on an unconformity (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 The sediment package below the Amundsen Basin flank of Lomonosov Ridge

Moving along the slope, we made the first trial deployment of a special corer to recover sediments for the Ice2Ice project of the Bjerknes Centre and cooperating Nordic centers of excellence. The corer has no core catcher, but a shutter mechanism in order to minimize core disturbance. We recovered a 30 cm long sample which would represent something of the order of thirty thousand years. The aim of this EU-funded five year project is to investigate the possible connection between the state of the Greenland Ice Sheet and the Arctic and sub-Arctic sea ice cover. The focus is on abrupt events.

On Sunday, we made our third deployment of the camera sled (Fig. 8) and obtained 80 minutes of monitoring the biological activity at the sea bed. The water depth was 1700 m. We now have video footage from the sea bed at three depth levels on the Lomonosov Ridge; 1390 m, 1700 m and 2650 m, respectively. Each depth level is represented by at least 30 minutes of video. This project had no proponents from the Norwegian community of marine biologists. However, we considered it important to use the FRAM-2014/15 opportunity to obtain this information, and are open to requests to use the data for scientific studies of the marine life in the deep polar ocean. The self erecting camera sled was constructed from a discarded hot water tank picked up at the junk (resource) yard and worked very well. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first video footage ever made from the sea bed on the Lomonosov Ridge, a submarine mountain chain of proportions that surpasses the European Alps.

Fig. 8 . The self erecting camera sled.

Wild life

No signs of animal life have been observed during the week

Life is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 03 November.

Position: 88 57.55' N, 115 06.1' W, temperature -35° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 2 knots from NNW. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards northeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Deployed the corer below the level of the unconformity. Found core catcher missing upon recovery. Serious winch problem as the Kevlar has worn a groove in the POM capstan from friction heat and the extra turns of cable on the capstan refuse to move sideways. Took four hours to get the corer up. Solved the problem by turning the winch 180 degrees and the groove moved out of the critical area.

Tuesday 04 November.

Position: 88 57,9' N, 113 58.4' W, temperature -37° C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 6 knots from N. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Deployed the rock dredge, water depth 1485 m. Unfortunately, Kevlar had been paid out too fast as it hit bottom and the cable got caught by the teeth of the dredge and it was pulled with the frontal opening facing backwards. Fired up the second oven in the rear of the hovercraft cabin to increase the temperature in the floor heat radiators.

Wednesday 05 November.

Position: 88 58.7' N, 111 31.1' W, temperature <-40° C, air pressure 1017 hPa, wind 13 knots from NNW. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. The diesel generator had a cracked fuel line which needed repair at 0400 hours. The air compressor is struggling as the pre-heating is getting marginal at these low temperatures

Thursday 06 November

Position: 89 00.8' N, 106 59.0' W, temperature -30° C, air pressure 1011 hPa, wind 22 knots from N. Ice drift 0.3 knots toward east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun started work to improve the outside work space. We removed snow from the store room in the remains of the ice hangar to provide a temporary storage space. We lost the e-mail connection. Most likely a problem of time variable satellite constellations. Audun went on a moon-lit ski trip to inspect the closest bathymetry buoy (#3). It had 10 cm of snow on top of the box.

Friday 07 November.

Position: 89 03.1' N, 102 59' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 1012 hPa, wind 9 knots from WNW. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Our internet connection is restored.

Saturday 08 November.

Position: 89 06.2' N, 99 36.4' W, temperature -30° C, air pressure 1018 hPa, wind 14 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards northeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day. We are passing the projected outcrop level of the major unconformity on the Amundsen Basin side of Lomonosov Ridge. Deployed the sediment corer in 1460 m water depth. Returned empty with only stains of mud in the core cutter - must have hit something really hard at the sea bed. At midnight, we deployed the light corer to obtain undisturbed surface sediment for the Bjerknes Centre, water depth 2006 m. Recovered 30 cm of core.

Sunday 09 November.

Position: 89 09.9' N, 93 38.5' W, temperature -22° C, air pressure 1007 hPa, wind 18 knots from N. Ice drift 0.3 knot towards northeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Deployed camera sled in 1700 m water depth and obtained 80 minutes of video from the bottom.

The eleventh week of ice drift (10 - 16 Nov. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 35 nautical miles (65 km) during the week (Fig. 1), exactly the same distance as last week. By now the ice camp has drifted a total distance of 340 nautical miles. For comparison, it is equivalent to the distance along the road from Oslo to Trondheim plus another 80 kilometers. We moved from the top of Lomonosov Ridge to the area beyond the foot of the slope in the Amundsen Basin. With that, our primary target for geology and geophysics was behind us and the current weather situation suggests there is little hope for a second return to the ridge. A strong high pressure cell over Banks Island in the Canadian Arctic on Monday developed into a continuous high which extended along the continental margin from Alaska to Svalbard until Friday morning. The associated wind field drove the ice towards the Fram Strait. From Friday onwards, a low pressure trough moving out from the Laptev Sea towards Ellesmere Island had much of the same effect on the sea ice motion. What is needed to drive us back over the Lomonosov Ridge is a strong low pressure moving past Northeast Greenland and into the Arctic Ocean. We have, by the way, slowly gotten an increased affection for low pressure systems - they makes things happen for better or worse.

Fig. 1. Drift track of FRAM-2014/15 across Lomonosov Ridge during week 11.

Sea ice activity

On Tuesday, a two meter wide crack opened between the radiation flux instruments and the hovercraft, cutting past our storage area and the fuel pillows. On Sunday it widened to 15 meters, more cracks developed and most of the fuel pillows became isolated on a separate floe. After that it became quiet.

Camp life

We had a brief warm spell on Sunday 9th November and early on Monday with temperatures around -20°C . After that air temperatures were between -25°C and -30°C . The logistics of a simple camp on sea ice is more labor intensive than a scientist would like to acknowledge. Set-backs driven by ice dynamics are the rule and not the exception. Also, just the trivial task of keeping equipment and supplies from disappearing in the shifting snow drifts becomes a full day job at times. At very low temperatures, all tasks become more tedious. If you want to use a piece of equipment, you often have to take it inside and heat it before you get any use of it.

Lomonosov Ridge is only about 80 km wide. Even if the ice drift is slow, the geological tidbits pass by below relatively fast when you are only two people to manage everything. Late Friday night, as we drifted over the lower slope of the ridge, the air-gun started to fire irregularly. I had the choice between working through the night to fix it or getting the first full night of sleep in five weeks - I chose the latter. The gun was in the water the next day at 1400 hours. Under these circumstances, we have still not caught up with getting ourselves a decent work area, so this week Audun worked on and off on temporary improvements.

Science

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Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

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- seismic reflection (0.3 liter air-gun & single hydrophone), sub-bottom penetration ~ 2 km.

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- Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler 0- 500 m depth.
- two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.
- thermistor string with 30 thermistors from the surface to 300 m depth.

Atmosphere:

- measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.
- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station (wind, temperature and humidity).

The seismic reflection measurements continued to run well for the fifth consecutive week, but the air-gun started triggering irregularly on Friday night. Shooting continued after lunch Saturday.. Three of the five autonomous echo sounding buoys have stopped reporting for unknown reasons. The other two continue to make soundings and report every three hours as long as we are over ridge topography.

Earlier, we reported on large back-tilted blocks of Mesozoic sediments below the slope on the Makarov Basin side of Lomonosov Ridge. A similar situation is also seen on the Amundsen Basin side as shown in figure 7 in the report for the last day of week 10 and now also the first days of week 11.

During the middle of the week, we crossed an area with abrupt termination of the sub-bottom strata above the unconformity (Fig. 2). This is most likely a slide scar. We have earlier published on the discovery of seven similar slide scars on both edges of Lomonosov Ridge in the central part (ACEX area). The triggering mechanism of these slides remains unknown as Lomonosov Ridge is aseismic, at least within the time frame covered by instrumental earthquake monitoring history.

Fig. 2. A possible slide scar at the edge of Lomonosov Ridge

Fig. 3. Location of coring and dredging attempts within the slide scar.

We first attempted coring in an area of rough bottom topography considered to be within the slide scar (Fig. 3). The corer came up with only mud stains on the core cutter so the bottom must have been hard. Subsequently dredge # 6 was deployed. To our great surprise, the dredge came up empty.

Fig. 4. The edge of Lomonosov Ridge facing the Amundsen Basin

On Friday November 14 we passed over the edge of Lomonosov Ridge and moved down-slope towards the Amundsen Basin (Fig. 4). Diffraction hyperbolae suggested a scarp, but dredging down a slope is not optimal. Dredge # 7 returned a single sharp-edged platy rock specimen.

A fourth deployment of the camera sled was made in 1450 m water depth on top of Lomonosov Ridge Wednesday November 12. The sled sat on the bottom for a while until the tow line tightened up from the slow drift. The video shows an abundance of copepods. At one point a half-meter long fish comes into the field of view. Both sequences are attached to this report. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time a fish of this size has been reported from the central Arctic Ocean.

Wild life

No signs of animal life have been observed on the ice surface during the week

Life is treating us well apart from the unpredictable ice dynamics

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 10 November.

Position: 89° 10.41' N, 88° 56.5' W, temperature -26° C, air pressure 1028 hPa, wind 5 knots from NE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun is putting up improved walls for the work area.

Tuesday 11 November..

Position: 89° 08.2' N, 88° 10.7' W, temperature -27° C, air pressure 1033 hPa, wind 4 knots from NNE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards southeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun discovered a new 2 m wide crack between the radiation flux instruments and the hovercraft continuing past our storage area and the fuel pillows. Some shear motion.

Wednesday 12 November.

Position: 89° 06.2' N, 83° 42.0' W, temperature -26° C, air pressure 1035 hPa, wind 15 knots from NNE. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Deployed the camera sled at 0130 hours in 1450 m water depth. Obtained about 30 minutes of video with sled moving. A half meter long eel-like fish came into view. During the afternoon, we moved over an area looking like a slide scar. Deployed the corer and let it hang at 1000 m in anticipation of a suitable target.

Thursday 13 November

Position: 89° 06.34' N, 79° 01.3' W, temperature -26° C, air pressure 1034 hPa, wind 19 knots from NNW. Ice drift 0.2 knots toward east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Start the decent from the top of Lomonosov Ridge down the slope towards Amundsen Basin. Dropped the corer to the bottom in 2050 m water depth. The corer was recovered with only mud on the core cutter. Dropped the dredge in 2170 m water depth. The new ice crack in the camp area had widened to about 3 m.

Friday 14 November.

Position: 89° 09.0' N, 71° 44.5' W, temperature -20° C, air pressure 1027 hPa, wind 27 knots from WNW. Ice drift 0.4 knots towards east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. This is the position of the outcrop of the major unconformity. Recovered the dredge; only one rock specimen with sharp edges recovered. The Kevlar line had disintegrated between 100 and 200 m; we had to cut the line after recovering the dredge. Air-gun started to fire only occasionally; had to recover the gun for maintenance. The through-going 3 m wide crack had come together again with build-up of a small pressure ridge. Could now reconnect power to the radiation flux instruments. The radiation

instruments are fine, but the sun time and IP sensors had to be cleared of frost and snow.

Saturday 15 November.

Position: 89° 13.59' N, 66° 18.48' W, temperature -30° C, air pressure 1009 hPa, wind 13 knots from WNW. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards northeast. The air-gun in the water at 1400 hours and resume shooting seismic reflection. Checked the GFI weather station; all covered with frost, but the wind speed rotor was working well. Also checked radiation flux instruments and removed rime from sun time sensor and snow from IR sensor. Audun again determined the present direction of our initial North-South orientation of our ice floe.

Sunday 16 November.

Position: 89° 11.24' N, 61° 11.8' W, temperature -30° C, air pressure 1009 hPa, wind 13 knots from NNW. Ice drift 0.3 knot towards southeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Continue work on the wall to improve work space. The large through-going crack has widened to 15 m and pressure motion started. Most of the fuel pillows are now isolated on a separate floe with a 15 m wide lead in-between.

The twelfth week of ice drift (17 - 23 Nov. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 22 nautical miles (41 km) during the week (Fig. 1). During the first part of the week, the motion was parallel to the Lomonosov Ridge and later perpendicular. This was caused by a large ridge of high sea-level pressure extending from the Beaufort Sea to the New Siberian Islands area, and a subsequent shift of 90° in trend to between the Beaufort Sea and Franz Josef Land. With this development, we are well underway towards the top of Lomonosov Ridge from the Amundsen Basin side for the second time.

Fig. 1. Drift track of FRAM-2014/15 over Lomonosov Ridge during week 12

Sea ice dynamics

The very appearance of the sea ice surface testifies to the intensity and scales of sea ice dynamics. *Polarstern* offloaded us on a floe of level ice separated by a long northwest-trending lead. The area on the other side of the lead had the appearance of a vast field of ice rubble. Our camp was established about 200 m away from the lead. Since then, the lead has closed and opened several times. It is our impression that cracking and pressure ridge formation on our floe has gradually moved towards our location from the southeast and this week it consumed our camp.

As there is total darkness, the beam of your head lamp determines the bounds of your microcosmos; the rest becomes extra-galactic ice space. The combination of a dynamic ice situation and total darkness gives you the feeling of not knowing what is going on, because you lack the overview. A sudden increase in ice activity on Sunday night widened the lead between the radiation flux instruments and the hovercraft to 15 m. This lead appears to be perpendicular to the main lead *Polarstern* used. On its way, the lead graced the front of our line of equipment and food boxes. Subsequently the lead turned into a major shear zone which built up piles of ice rubble several meters high. The intensity of deformation peaked on Wednesday. Cracks developed as splays from the shear motion, fragmenting a major part of the camp area, including where most of the fuel, food and equipment were located (Fig. 2). One crack went through the remains of the ice hangar and the water level on top of the ice in the old storage room increased by another 0.5 m. The highest priority became moving the fuel bladders in relay, by pumping into empty bladders sitting on still unbroken ice; however this operation went smoothly (Fig. 3). The next challenge was to move more than one ton of food and over 2 tons of equipment. We quickly realized that using the hovercraft as a power plant for the hydraulic geology winch with the 3000 m of Kevlar line, we had a way to pull a load in any direction by use of an anchored extra idler. We had earlier built a sled from a full sheet of coated plywood with a 15 cm steel pipe forming a curved front. To reduce friction, we sacrificed an empty fuel bladder to line the sled underneath. With these resources, we moved the food and equipment, more than 3 tons in total, by about 200 m in the course of one 25 hour and a subsequent 20 hour work period.

There was nothing one could do except wait and see with regard to instruments like the current meters, the ADCP and the thermistor string suspended from the underside of the ice. Each site had been marked with a 3 m long plastic pipe which enabled us to monitor the state of the site as ice deformation progressed. The current meter (presently at 1050 m depth), the 300 m long thermistor string, and the radiation flux instruments are on the same ice floe and seem unhurt. For the moment, the big unknown is the situation with the ADCP, which is only about 2 m from the main shear zone where under-thrusting of the ice is very likely. We will explore the site using an underwater camera, before undertaking the major task of cutting a hole. The radiation flux instrument has since been moved because the site was out of reach of our power cords.

Camp life

Temperatures this week were below -30° C, except for Wednesday (-25° C) and during the weekend (-21° C). The ice activity occupied our minds the whole week. Much agony went into decisions; what

should you consider a safe place for the time being, particularly with respect to the bulk of our cargo? At one point on Thursday, we started to carry special equipment items to the store room in

Fig. 2. Overview of part of the camp area on Sunday 23 November. The only woman in town, a snow lady created by the *Polarstern* science crew is marked by a red X.

Fig. 3. Fuel bladders before rescue.

the abandoned ice hangar, among them the Zarges boxes belonging to the Meteorological Institute and the Geophysical Institute. However on Saturday the shear zone encroached on the remains of the ice hangar. The next thing we discovered was another 50 cm of water on top of the ice in the store room; the boxes were floating around and the walls were caving in - we could not get the boxes out. By Sunday, the destruction was complete. We spotted the boxes in the remains and after some digging were able to pull them out of the icy slush before they were frozen in. Some minor equipment items were lost. This mistaken perception of a "safe place" had limited consequences. However, the more nagging question was: where should the next camp be? Having wandered around with our head lamps in the neighborhood (extra-galactic ice space), we want to move everything another 150 m, and make it Camp IV.

Coming out of an intense week-long work period in -30°C , we faced the reality that first we have to continue cleaning up what is behind us and then start from scratch preparing work facilities for the third time in four months. Also, the ice drift is bringing us back to Lomonosov Ridge, our primary science target, which presents new science opportunities that should not be lost. You never win them all, but we will do the best we can.

One lesson from our short stay on the sea ice so far is that the solution for your work facilities should not be ice hangars, but a relatively light-weight work space that is easy to mobilize and demobilize. A double walled tent held up by pressurized air-filled beams is one possibility being considered.

Science

This week, the following suite of continuous measurements has been unaffected by the ice activity:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- two active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.

Oceanography: - Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler 0-500 m depth???

- two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.
- thermistor string with 30 thermistors from the surface to 300 m depth.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station (wind, temperature and humidity).

The destruction of our camp area made it impossible to carry out any additional science tasks during the week.

Wild life

We have a new visitor. Audun caught a glimpse of a polar fox running across the abandoned camp. The tracks of the animal are shown in Fig 3.

Fig. 3. Tracks of a visiting polar fox.

There is hardly a dull moment, but life is treating us well apart from the unpredictable ice dynamics.

Daily reports

Monday 17 November.

Position: 89° 09.6' N, 57° 53' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1010 hPa, wind 5 knots from NNE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards south. Shooting seismic reflection, but recovered the air-gun in the afternoon. Audun made GPS survey of the leads and pressure ridges in the area of our camp. We inspected the fuel cache and discovered a crack had dumped a fuel bladder into the water. We secured the bladder and pumped all its contents into an empty bladder. Started to disconnect the hovercraft, but the skirt control did not respond. As the temperature had fallen to -34° C, we applied heat overnight to warm the hydraulic reservoir.

Tuesday 18 November..

Position: 89° 06,9' N, 57° 03' W, temperature -38° C, air pressure 1017 hPa, wind 6 knots from ENE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards south. Skirt control repaired. Had problems getting the hovercraft off the bed created by six weeks of idling in the same spot.

Wednesday 19 November.

Position: 89° 04.2' N, 56° 37' W, temperature -25° C, air pressure 1017 hPa, wind 12 knots from NE. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards south. The ice activity was very high all day. The lead between the radiation flux instruments and the hovercraft turned into a major shear zone which built piles of ice rubble several meters high. Cracks developed as splays from this shear motion and fragmented a major part of the camp area, including where most of the fuel was located. The highest priority became moving the fuel bladders in relay by pumping into empty bladders laying on still unbroken ice. By early Thursday morning, seven full bladders had been moved. Two were spotted in a pressure ridge and the last two were missing.

Thursday 20 November

Position: 88° 59.4' N, 56° 44' W, temperature -31° C, air pressure 1020 hPa, wind 10 knots from E. Ice drift 0.1 knots toward south. Emptied and recovered two fuel bladders caught in a pressure ridge. Kept moving the fuel farther away from the active area. Also started moving food and equipment.

Friday 21 November.

Position: 88° 58.4' N, 56° 27' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1027 hPa, wind 7 knots from ESE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards south. The priority was getting all the food out of the active zone. Used the geology winch to pull a sled to speed up the

process. Worked continuously until Saturday noon. Relay pumping of fuel went in parallel with this activity.

Saturday 22 November.

Position: 88° 55.8' N, 60° 54' W, temperature -21° C, air pressure 1003 hPa, wind 28 knots from E. After resting from 1200 hours to 2000 hours, moving cargo and pumping fuel continued non-stop until Sunday at 1500 hours.

Sunday 23 November.

Position: 88° 52.8' N, 62° 32' W, temperature -20° C, air pressure 996 hPa, wind 4 knots from WSW. Ice drift 0.4 knot towards south. Had to stop working at 1500 hours - we were exhausted. Audun spotted a polar fox. Went to sleep until Monday at 0800 hours.

The thirteenth week of ice drift (24 - 30 Nov. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 28 nautical miles (52 km) during the week (Fig. 1). The ice drift was for the most part towards the west and brought us over and along the top of Lomonosov Ridge. An elongated and strong high pressure cell extended from Novaya Zemlya to past the New Siberian Islands during the first part of the week, but from Thursday on the surface air pressure gradients were weak over the entire Arctic Ocean. We experienced a short period of strong winds late Tuesday and early Wednesday morning with gusts over 40 knots due to a low pressure trough extending north from the Fram Strait. During this event the ice drift increased from 0.1 knots to 0.5 knots.

Fig. 1. Drift track of FRAM-2014/15 over Lomonosov Ridge during week 13.

Sea ice dynamics

There has been some minor divergence and shear motion in the main deformation zone through our abandoned camp area. We searched the neighborhood for a site and decided to establish the new camp about 300 m away from where the bulk of our supplies are currently located. We have no illusions about this location being better than any other, but the area surrounded by "old" pressure ridges appears relatively free of small incipient cracks and the distance to a large lead is over 200-300 m. We will use the light from the next full moon to further explore the area.

Camp life

Temperatures were below -30°C on Monday and Tuesday, but later between -23°C and -14°C except Thursday (-30°C). It is clear that the effort required to complete the recovery of all the different pieces of supplies from the abandoned camp was far more exhaustive than we initially thought. Two weeks have now passed since the camp was disrupted, and we are not anywhere near the point where we are up and going again. We still have no hydro-hole through the ice, and a new work space still needs to be made and supplies to be moved. The locations of the two current meters and the thermistor string seem unharmed, but the radiation flux instrument and the weather station will be moved. The priority is moving fuel and food towards the new site.

Science

This week, the following suite of continuous measurements has been unaffected by the ice activity:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- two active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.

- thermistor string with 30 thermistors from the surface to 300 m depth.

Atmosphere: - Aanderaa weather station (wind, temperature and humidity).

The destruction of our camp area made it unrealistic to carry out any additional science tasks during the week.

We tried to recover the Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler by drilling a hole 2 m away from the line where it was attached (Fig. 2). At 4 m depth, the length of our drill, we had still not penetrated the stack of multiple ice layers. We made another hole 7 m away through 2 m thick ice and lowered a camera, but were not able to see any sign of the ADCP. The visibility in the water was very poor from ice crystals in suspension.

Fig. 2. The ADCP site marked with a pole. We are making the camera ready to be lowered. Note the front of the pressure ridge in the background.

Fig. 3. The polar fox, our companion on the ice near the North Pole.

Wild life

Our new visitor has made him/herself familiar with the new and easy access to food. The animal is more confident and frequently comes to within a few meters of our activities (Fig. 3).. Early on, Audun discovered droppings which have been collected so as to be handed over to people who can investigate the diet of a polar fox roaming the central Arctic Ocean. Our friend needs a name and suggestions so far are; Slikkepott, Mikkel or Putin.

Life is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 24 November.

Position: 88° 45.3' N, 59° 07' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 1008 hPa, wind 13 knots from NNW. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards south. The generator would not start and repairs took all morning. Continued to haul equipment out of the demolished storage area and to move fuel by pumping. Rescued the large 14 m x 9 m tarp from the remains of the ice hangar.

Tuesday 25 November..

Position: 8° 44,0' N, 58° 22' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 7 knots from the E. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards west. Recovered the radiation flux instruments and moved three loads of equipment from our abandoned hydro hole. A 15 cm wide crack had opened right through the hole.

Wednesday 26 November.

Position: 88° 40.8' N, 63° 31' W, temperature -18° C, air pressure 995 hPa, wind 28 knots from ESE. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards west. The strong wind with gusts up to 40 knots had created snow drifts around the hovercraft and filled the lift fan intake completely. Dismantled the work space around the abandoned hydro-hole and moved the materials to the temporary storage area. Mobilized the hovercraft to move to a better site, but could not achieve sufficient rpm's.

Need advice to tackle the problem.

Thursday 27 November

Position: 88° 41.5' N, 64° 21' W, temperature -30° C, air pressure 1008 hPa, wind 10 knots from ENE. Ice drift 0.2 knots toward south. Attempted to recover the ADCP. Drilled a hole 2 m away from the wire to 4 m depth which was the maximum length of our drill. Hit several layers of ice with water in between, but were unable to reach all the way through. Drilled a second hole 7 m away through 2 m thick ice. Lowered a camera, but were unable to see the ADCP on the monitor. The visibility in the water was poor due to large quantities of ice crystals in suspension. We will revisit the site later to see if the instruments could show up in a pressure ridge and be recovered. At this point, we have to accept the loss.

Friday 28 November.

Position: 88° 35.8' N, 64° 52' W, temperature -14° C, air pressure 995 hPa, wind 12 knots from NE. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards south. Had problems with getting the hovercraft engine to respond to the throttle position. Consulted Griffon Hoverwork. Problem was a loose wire and later on also a parted pipe connection to the intercooler. Moved the hovercraft to a site 300 m away where the new camp will be. To bed at 0330 hours.

Saturday 29 November.

Position: 88° 32.7' N, 66° 07' W, temperature -21° C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 13 knots from SE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards west. Demobilized the hovercraft.

Sunday 30 November.

Position: 88° 33.5' N, 70° 59' W, temperature -23° C, air pressure 1017 hPa, wind 10 knots from S. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards northeast. Made a ski sled and moved the generator and some materials to the new site. Put up a new generator shed.

The fourteenth week of ice drift (01 - 08 Dec. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 27 nautical miles (50 km) during the week (Fig. 1). During Monday through Wednesday, the drift was due east and later turned south. The driving force was an elongated high pressure cell which extended from Franz Josef Land to past the New Siberian Islands. Peak pressures exceeded 1050 hPa. After Wednesday the axis of this cell shifted and went from the East Siberian Sea to the Beaufort Sea. The major event of the week was a low pressure coming north from the Canadian Arctic Islands which gave us winds over 35 knots all Monday, Tuesday and into Wednesday. Gusts were over 40 knots and drove the ice fields to a speed of 0-6 knots on Tuesday. Winds were calm (<12 knots) during the last part of the week.

Fig. 1. Drift track of FRAM-2014/15 over Lomonosov Ridge during week 14

Sea ice dynamics

Only small relative ice movements affected our neighborhood this week. Exceptions were some minor ridging in the old camp area and widening of the crack by 0.5 m between our camp and the temporary depot area 300 m away.

Camp life

The low pressure system brought in warm air and high wind speeds. Temperatures on Monday and Tuesday were warmer than -10°C with a maximum of -3°C on Monday. Temperatures on Wednesday through Saturday were -22°C to -25°C and on Sunday we were back to -30°C .

This is the third week spent on logistics in order to get back on track at the new camp location. We have been moving food, fuel and equipment. The new work space is half-finished and the hydro-hole nears completion. Starting-up after a break is most often not straightforward as indicated by the following example. We opened the enclosure made over the compressor to keep it warm with the expectation that we only needed to turn on the heat. The whole box was now packed with hard wind-blown snow - a result of the snow storm at the beginning of the week (Fig. 2). To get it ready required a couple of days of thawing after most of the snow was removed. A hydraulic hose is like a steel rod, do not try to move anything before you have used the heat gun to warm the essential parts.

The full moon came over the horizon on 1 December, but was not visible to us until the 5th due to overcast. The light of the full moon makes it possible to see the ice landscape and walk around without a head lamp. However, the lamp is needed for any work to get done. The beauty of the ice surface in moonlight is awesome.

Fig. 2. The snow filled compressor enclosure (left). The diving air compressor is located behind the blue air bottles in the foreground (right).

Science

This week, the following suite of continuous measurements has been unaffected by the ice activity:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- two active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.

- thermistor string recovered on Wednesday.

Atmosphere: - Aanderaa weather station recovered on Thursday.

The priority this week was to re-establish camp facilities and made it unrealistic to carry out any additional science tasks.

The thermistor string was now about 7 m from the main shear zone. During ice ridging, parts of one ice floe often get thrust under another as was the case for the ADCP site mentioned in our last report. We feared this could happen at the site of the thermistor string and decided to recover the string. A hole was drilled next to the chain and we were able to hook on to the chain under the ice and recover all the gear safely except for the weight (Fig. 3). The thermistor data loggers have records of the microstructure of the temperature field within the upper 300 m below the ice for almost four complete crossings of the Lomonosov Ridge. We are awaiting instructions on how to download the data before redeployment.

On Thursday, the weather station was moved as the field of pressure ridges was about 15 m from the site. Unfortunately, the wind cross was broken in the process. A replacement is expected with the planned air drop before Christmas.

Fig. 3. Recovering the thermistor string. The supporting chain was hooked under the ice by a shackle attached to a strong rope taped to the end of the red pole. The front of the pressure ridge is barely visible in the dark background.

Air drop by the Norwegian Air Force

There was no multi-year sea ice spotted from *Polarstern* at the time of our initial camp deployment. The repeated disruptions by sea ice deformation in the domain of first year ice forced us to change strategy in terms of ice camp logistics. Ice hangars may be a good idea on stronger multi-year sea ice floes, but less so on weak first year ice. The Operational Headquarters of the Norwegian Air Force has generously allocated an P-3C Orion flight to the FRAM-2014/15 ice camp if their flight schedule and weather permit. The supply mission will take place either before Christmas or after 5 January. The purpose is to bring out work tents to provide for swifter and safer camp relocation and to serve as a general safety contingency. The air drop also includes other minor essential items and spare parts.

Wild life

Our visitor, the unnamed polar fox, continues to keep us company by overseeing our outdoor activities. He has started to move in on particular items of his/her liking. First a green cargo strap disappeared, and then theft of a second was attempted, but abandoned and recovered by us. Next, a yellow and red cutting head for our 10 cm ice auger disappeared. We suspect it is a male fox from the way the animal urinates. The name of the fox is still not settled and new suggestions are; "Prestrud's sendebud" and "Inspektør Snusen".

Life is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 01 December.

Position: 88° 33.9' N, 73° 32' W, temperature -4° C, air pressure 1012 hPa, wind 30 knots from SE. Ice drift 0.5 knots towards west. No outside work today.

Tuesday 02 December.

Position: 88° 08.38' N, 78° 37' W, temperature -11° C, air pressure 1028 hPa, wind 37 knots from SE. Ice drift 0.6 knots towards west. Stayed inside most of the day, but picked up radiation flux instruments and battery box and stored them at new camp site. Minor ice ridging in old camp area.

Wednesday 03 December.

Position: 88° 36.6' N, 84° 08' W, temperature -23° C, air pressure 1038 hPa, wind 28 knots from ESE. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards west. A new crack has opened 0.5 m half-way between the new and old camp areas. The thermistor string is now 7 m from the major zone of ice ridging and we mounted an attempt to get

it out. Drilled a hole next to the frozen-in upper chain and was able to hook onto it and recover the 300 m string safely. Lost the weight at the end because of a corroded shackle. Will await instruction on how to download the data before redeployment. Moved 6 Zarges boxes of food from the old camp to the new.

Thursday 04 December

Position: 88° 34.7' N, 85° 58' W, temperature -24° C, air pressure 1043 hPa, wind 8 knots from the E. Ice drift 0.1 knots toward south. Moved two large wooden boxes and six Zarges boxes of food to the new camp area and moved five fuel bladders across the recent crack in our temporary storage area. The weather station was now 15 m from a pressure ridge and was disassembled and moved to the new camp area.

Friday 05 December.

Position: 88° 31.5' N, 84° 09' W, temperature -22° C, air pressure 1025 hPa, wind 8 knots from NE. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards south. Repair work on the portable diesel pump. Mounting new hydrophone for the seismic measurements - we have lost two hydrophones to the ice, but still have two spares. Audun started to build a new work space for the seismic and geological work, and work on making a new hydro-hole was initiated. Ice thickness is 1.5 m. The half-way crack widened another 0.5 m.

Saturday 06 December.

Position: 88° 27.3' N, 84° 17' W, temperature -23° C, air pressure 1014 hPa, wind 15 knots from the E. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards SSE. Work on the new work space and hydro-hole continued. Found the compressor compartment totally packed with windblown snow. Cleared out the snow and put heat on.

Sunday 07 December.

Position: 88° 24.6' N, 84° 14' W, temperature -30° C, air pressure 1013 hPa, wind 9 knots from the NE. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the south. Work on the work space and hydro-hole continued. Moved a fuel bladder from the old camp area to the new.

The fifteenth week of ice drift (08 - 14 Dec. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 39 nautical miles (72 km) during the week (Fig. 1). The ice drift was in general southward along the slope of Lomonosov Ridge facing the Makarov Basin. The surface air pressure pattern during the week was a high extending from the East Siberian Sea to the Beaufort Sea with relatively weak gradients towards the Pole, giving us calm weather (wind speeds <7 knots from the west) Monday through Friday, and a little higher (<16 knots) during the weekend.

Fig. 1. Drift track of FRAM-2014/15 over Lomonosov Ridge during week 15

Sea ice dynamics

No known ice movements affected our neighborhood this week.

Camp life

Temperatures were below -30°C Monday through Friday, but $5\text{-}10^{\circ}\text{C}$ (-23°C to -27°C) warmer during the weekend.

Three and a half weeks after the last camp disruption, we could resume our scientific duties. There is still more cargo and fuel to be moved as we go along. The new work space over the hydro-hole is $2.5\text{ m} \times 3\text{ m}$, has an inner shell of a mixture of plywood and tarps and a surrounding 2 m high lee wall of snow blocks (Fig. 2). Covered annexes include the deck space with the compressor and also an addition on the ice for the sauna.

Fig. 2. The new work space over the hydro hole.

Audun has finally made the sauna operational and tested it out on Sunday. Past camp disruptions and the need to prioritize had left the project unfinished up until now. A cut-off hot water tank serves as reservoir where the snow is melted and the water heated to the right temperature (Fig. 3). The water is fed to a regular shower head by a small pump and the result is a shower no different from the bathroom at home.

Fig. 3. Audun putting snow into the hot water tank.

Science

This week, the following suite of continuous measurements has been operating during build-up of the new camp:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- two active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.

Atmosphere: (from Friday)

- measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.
- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

We are finally back on track to get more science done. The fact that our drift track once again was approaching the slope of Lomonosov Ridge on the Makarov Basin side, presented a deadline for resumption of seismic reflection measurements. Failure to do so would be an inexcusable defeat. This slope is considered to represent the polar continental margin of Europe before c. 60 million years, and the bathymetric trough along the foot of the slope holds a clue as to how the oldest part of the Arctic Ocean was formed. Once seismic profiling got underway it did not take long before acoustic evidence of sediment deformation of the deeper strata showed up on the monitor. Along-slope continuity of acoustic reflections was replaced by a chaotic pattern of families of hyperbolic diffractions. In places, the sub-bottom topography is due to sediment deformation, later capped by a 0.3 sec thick sediment drape. This is certainly not showing the acoustic characteristics of a rifted continental margin. Shear motion is very difficult to define acoustically, apart from features such as folds, thrusts and acoustic "flower structures". To the best of our knowledge, this is the first documentation of deformation along the lineament represented by the trough between Lomonosov Ridge and Marvin Spur, a possible Mesozoic shear boundary. Crossings by the Soviet ice drift station NP-28 in 1988 lacked the seismic resolution (one shot every 0.5 km), and a short line segment on the south side acquired by *Polarstern*, accompanied by a nuclear icebreaker in 1998, apparently did not capture deformation features.

Fig. 4. Sample of monitor record showing a chaotic pattern of diffractions interpreted as evidence of sediment deformation.

Wild life

Our visitor, the unnamed polar fox, continues to keep us company by overseeing our outdoor activities. He has started to move in on particular items of his/her liking. First a green cargo strap disappeared, and then theft of a second was attempted, but abandoned and recovered by us. Next, a yellow and red cutting head for our 10 cm ice auger disappeared. We suspect it is a male fox from the way the animal urinates. The name of the fox is still not settled and new suggestions are; "Prestrud's sendebud" and "Inspektør Snusen".

The polar fox (Fig. 5), shows up at dinner time almost regularly, apparently expecting some form of treat from Audun. We are curious as to how long he will stay around when we later start to drift towards the Fram Strait. In an e-mail to us, David Mosher, Chief Scientist on the Canadian icebreaker expedition last summer, reports the sighting of a polar fox at 86° N.

Fig. 5. The polar fox under the full moon.

The moon went below the horizon on Sunday and we will enjoy complete darkness for the next 17 days.

We have been informed that every effort is being made for the FRAM-2014/15 cargo to arrive at Andøya air base no later than 18 December in time for the resupply flight by a P-3C Orion plane from the 333rd Squadron of the Norwegian Air Force.

Life is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 08 December.

Position: 88° 22.3' N, 85° 11' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1027 hPa, wind 4 knots from N. Ice drift 0.5 knots towards west. We worked on building new work space; putting on the roof and building enclosing lee walls of snow blocks. The sauna is housed in an annex. The 24-hour full moon makes a very special outdoor working environment.

Tuesday 09 December.

Position: 88° 21.50' N, 85° 02' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 1017 hPa, wind 5 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.0 knots. Continued moving equipment and fuel to the new camp area. Our current fuel inventory is about 8 tons. Penetrated the final thin layer of ice left at the bottom of the hydro-hole. E-mailed orders for smaller items and spares to be air dropped.

Wednesday 10 December.

Position: 88° 21.0' N, 84° 55' W, temperature -30° C, air pressure 1017 hPa, wind 5 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards south. Moved more equipment from the abandoned camp to the new camp. Continued to improve the work space.

Thursday 11 December.

Position: 88° 19.9' N, 84° 02' W, temperature -26° C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 7 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knots toward south-southeast. Moved more equipment to the new camp. Heated the hydraulic oil reservoir and started the compressor. Deployed the hydrophone through a 75 mm plastic pipe filled with anti-freeze.

Friday 12 December.

Position: 88° 18.7' N, 83° 17' W, temperature -33° C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 4 knots from NNW. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards southeast. Installed the air-gun in the hydro-hole and started seismic reflection measurements. Audun determined and then marked directions for North and South. Put the radiation flux instrument mast to a new location and also the weather station. Moved more equipment to the new camp area.

Saturday 13 December.

Position: 88° 10.4' N, 82° 04' W, temperature -23° C, air pressure 1008 hPa, wind 18 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.4 knots towards south. The air-gun stopped in the early morning. Also, the hydrophone signal got swamped by noise trains. Serviced the air-gun and also the air pressure reduction valve. Resumed seismic

shooting at 1830 hours. Ambient noise levels still too high, pulled the hydrophone to just below the underside of the ice to obtain good results.

Sunday 14 December.

Position: 88° 06.3' N, 80° 54' W, temperature -27° C, air pressure 1013 hPa, wind 16 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards the southeast. We are moving along the foot of the slope on the Makarov Basin side and are getting excellent seismic reflection data.

The FRAM-2014/15 ice camp under the full moon.

All photos by Audun Tholfsen

The sixteenth week of ice drift (15 - 21 Dec. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 23 nautical miles (42 km) during the week (Fig. 1) along the slope of Lomonosov Ridge facing the Makarov Basin. The drift speed was relatively high on Monday (0.4 knots), slowed down on Tuesday (0.2 knots), but came to a complete standstill on Friday. At its slowest, the camp moved 25 m in 9 hours, and the next 25 m took 17.168 seconds (4.7 hours). The ice drift remained slow during the weekend. This speed change is remarkable because the wind speed remained between 10 and 14 knots from the north and northeast, slightly higher than before the slowdown. As during the previous week, the surface air pressure pattern was a high extending from the East Siberian Sea to the Beaufort Sea with relatively weak gradients towards the Pole, giving us calm weather (wind speeds <10-14 knots from the sector NW to NE).

Fig. 1. Drift track (red) of FRAM-2014/15 during week 16 (15-21 December, 2014).

Sea ice dynamics

Again this week, no known ice movements affected our neighborhood.

Camp life

Temperatures stayed at -28-29° C Monday through Wednesday, with a warm spell on Thursday (-14° C) and then falling to -34° C on Saturday. The week has been characterized by an atmosphere of great expectations in anticipation of the forthcoming air drop by the P-3C Orion of the 333rd Squadron, generously provided by the Norwegian Air Force. The flight was initially scheduled for Friday 19th December, but delayed until after the weekend. Expected are 24 pieces including work tents (2), heaters and miscellaneous spares. A 700+ meter long drop zone has been checked out to be marked with lights. There appears to be no open water areas in our neighborhood at the moment.

The expected arrival of new work space facilities has made us hold off any activities like sediment coring or deployment of the camera sled. Besides, we are drifting in about 2.100 m water depth with a 500+ m thick cover of Cenozoic sediments, where no specific targets present themselves.

Part of the excitement about the air drop is simply the fact that wear and tear have done away with our supply of mittens suitable for work in very low temperatures. Constantly losing the feeling of your finger tips is very painful and tiring.

Science

This week, the following suite of continuous measurements has been operating:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- four active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.
- continuous seismic reflection measurements (2 km sub-bottom penetration).

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.

Atmosphere: (from Friday)

- measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.
- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station (no wind speed at the moment).

We continue the continuous seismic reflection profiling. As the drift path turned slightly east of south, we moved higher on the slope of Lomonosov Ridge and out of the zone of deformed sediments (Fig. 2). The deepest section (below the 1 sec two-way travel time sub-bottom) shows a

southerly component of dip in contrast to the overlying infill of material with horizontal acoustic layering.

Fig. 2. Screen shot of the raw seismic data recorded along the slope of Lomonosov Ridge at the end of week 16. The upper part (shallower than 3.4 sec) probably correlates with the Cenozoic drape on the top of the ridge. South is to the right. The shot spacing is 25 m.

On Friday we uploaded to an ftp-site all the data (16 Mb) logged so far by the radiation flux instruments for the Meteorological Institute, Oslo. This was our first case of direct delivery of raw data and demonstrates the potential of an ice station as an active science platform. The facility was set up by graduate student Gaute Hope and Lars-Gunnar Persson, NERSC.

Wild life

Visits by the un-named polar fox have been more irregular this week. On Friday, Audun had planned a close-up photo session where the bait was an empty egg shell filled with olive oil. The fox had a quick sniff at the egg shell, and then went straight for the camera, grabbing it and running off. Audun caught up with the thief after about a hundred meters and recovered the camera - end of photo session.

Winter solstice is Sunday 21 December; from now on the light will increase. The moon comes above the horizon on 29 December and will help us along the way until mid-January.

Life is treating us well in the High Arctic.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 15 December.

Position: 88° 01.8' N, 78° 05' W, temperature -29° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 15 knots from NW. Ice drift 0.4 knots towards southeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day.

Tuesday 16 December.

Position: 88° 00.0' N, 76° 21' W, temperature -25° C, air pressure 1008 hPa, wind 13 knots from the WNW. Ice drift 0.2 knots due east. Problems with irregular seismic triggering during the early morning hours. Acquiring seismic reflection data all day.

Wednesday 17 December.

Position: 87° 58.1' N, 73° 57' W, temperature -28° C, air pressure 1013 hPa, wind 12 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards southeast. Acquiring seismic reflection data all day. Audun moved more food from the abandoned camp to the new camp. Maintenance work on the winch. 18 pieces of cargo arrived at Andøya Air Base from Bergen.

Thursday 18 December.

Position: 87° 55.3' N, 73° 17' W, temperature -23° C, air pressure 1010 hPa, wind 10 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards south. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun extracted the memory card from the data logger of the radiation flux instrument. All cargo (24 pieces) for the ice have arrived at the air base of the 333rd Squadron, Andøya.

Friday 19 December.

Position: 87° 51.2' N, 73° 18' W, temperature -22° C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 14 knots from ENE. Ice drift 0.0. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun picked up another two loads of food from the old camp. Connected the cabin stove heat exchanger with the engine so heat from the extended radiator loop in the cabin also heats the engine. The drift is extremely slow. During the day it took over 8 hours to move 25 meters; the next 25 meters took nearly 5 hours. Audun uploaded all the radiation flux data to a NERSC ftp site.

Saturday 20 December.

Position: 87° 51.1' N, 73° 13' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1018 hPa, wind 7 knots from the ENE. Ice drift 0.0. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Re-adjusted the lift fan belt - a very cold job. The belt moved to the forward end of the pulley, so another adjustment is needed, but we need a warmer day. Audun moved another three loads of food from the old camp.

Sunday 21 December.

Position: 87° 49.7' N, 73° 01' W, temperature -26° C, air pressure 1013 hPa, wind 13 knots from the NNE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards the south. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Searched out a drop zone for the P-3C Orion flight coming tomorrow.

The FRAM-2014/15 ice camp as the daylight dwindled at the end of October.

The seventeenth week of ice drift (22 - 28 Dec. 2014)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 26 nautical miles (48 km) during the week (Fig. 1) - a distance roughly equivalent to the distance between Oslo and Gardermoen Airport. The ice drift was generally slow with a maximum of 0.3 knots on Thursday. The direction was due east across the Lomonosov Ridge. The wind speeds have been less than 10 knots all week except on Monday (18 knots). The wind from the north during Monday and Tuesday changed direction to the south during the last half of the week. The driving force at the start of the week was an elongated high pressure ridge extending from the Canadian Arctic to the East Siberian Sea. Wednesday through Friday the region of high air pressure at sea level was along the coast of the Canadian Arctic islands, and at the end of the week more centered over the Beaufort Sea

Fig. 1. Drift track (red) of FRAM-2014/15 during week 17 (22-28 December, 2014).

Sea ice dynamics

No known ice movements affected our neighborhood during the last full week of 2014.

Camp life

Temperatures were below -31°C on Monday. It got gradually colder towards the end of the week and below -40°C from Saturday night onwards. The major event was the air drop on Tuesday at noon under the light of millions of stars in the sky and over a 700 m long line on the ice surface marked by LED lights every 100m. The weather conditions were perfect for the season. Captain Marhaug and his crew on the P-3C Orion of the 333rd Squadron dropped 16 well-packed pieces of cargo, 2 boxes of Christmas snacks from NERSC, and a small special request from Norwegian TV2. The result is illustrated in figures 2 and 3. The light sticks attached to the cargo were of little help, but reflex tape greatly helped us to spot the items in the drop zone. Except for one tent, we located all items the first afternoon. The two high priority tents were dropped first and unfortunately landed in an ice rubble field 200 and 400 m before the start of the drop zone (Fig. 4). The reason was probably a combination of their heavy weight (50 kg) and relatively rapid decent, and the need to fine-tune timing of the drop. The plane cruises at almost 400 km/hour about 150 meter above the ice as the cargo is dropped. The heaviest items of well-packed cargo had only a few small impact related issues to be dealt with. The top of the multi-fuel oven was slightly deformed, but Audun could fix that. However, the boxes of Christmas snacks suffered; the much-wanted supply of fruits turned to mush, but they still tasted great, and the "pepperkakene" (gingerbread) turned into fine brown sand.

We sincerely thank the Norwegian Air Force, the 333rd Squadron, and the flight crew for an excellent job. An e-mail of 26 December to this effect was sent to "Forsvarets Operative Hovedkvarter", the Maritime Air Support Center at Andøya, and to the parties directly involved in execution of the flight. A special thanks also to Ola Johannessen and Jørn Thiede for assistance.

Fig. 2. The drop zone

Fig. 3. Christmas presents brought by the 333rd Squadron P-3C Orion.

Fig. 4. Bringing home the last tent.

Tuesday December 23rd also included another small event - Yngve's 73rd birthday. Age may be expressed in several ways beyond the physical fact in your birth certificate. Most important is the basic premise of being blessed with good health. Your perception of age also has a mental aspect to do with your mindset and level of curiosity, and a physical aspect regarding your capability to tackle physical challenges. Both aspects override the age number derived from the birth certificate as the age issue is of marginal relevance to our endeavor. Fresh cod is our traditional birthday dinner. We learned that a TV2 reporter would be on the flight for the air drop, and submitted a special request for fresh cod in addition to Audun's plea for pork roast. Both were delivered and the scene of unpacking the cod was recorded and e-mailed back to TV2. As the work of locating and moving the cargo to our camp had priority, the cod dinner didn't occur until midnight, following a short discussion on whether we should skip the dinner altogether. We were rather exhausted from a long day in temperatures below -35°C .

The 24th of December was spent searching for the missing tent which was located in the early afternoon. By a stroke of luck, both tents hit the sea ice on small flat surfaces within an extensive field of ice rubble. To get them out took some effort (Fig. 4). The Christmas evening meal was therefore a late, basic cold buffet feast on the contents of the NERSC boxes (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. The Christmas evening meal.

The Christmas days were spent unpacking the cargo. Audun first repaired the damage to the multi-fuel oven, and on the second day we cleared space for the tent to be connected to the existing work

space. The PVC tent was difficult to unroll in the cold (-36° C), but the air-filled arches inflated rapidly. However, after a few minutes, the structure folded and fell to the ice surface. The problem could either be related to damage from the air drop or caused by the low temperature. We located a leak in the hose connection between the arch and the top beam, and suspected the O-ring seals. The problem was circumvented by construction of supporting frames of 2"x4" lumber which now hold the tent up nicely (Fig. 6). We then moved the 14 kW multi-fuel oven inside and fired up (Fig. 7). At half power, it brings the inside temperature down to a pleasant working temperature of -15° C while the outside is -40° C.

Fig. 6. The new tent added to the existing work space

Fig. 7 Audun firing up the multi-fuel oven assisted by the ever present heat gun.

Science

This week, the following suite of continuous measurements has been operating:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- four active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.
- continuous seismic reflection measurements (2 km sub-bottom penetration).

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

The seismic data acquisition had been going well all week, but on Saturday night the air-gun stopped triggering. The solenoid was serviced, but the gun was leaking and had to be retrieved once more. As our inventory of firing seals is exhausted, we flipped the O-ring before putting the gun back into the icy -1.7° C water. The trick worked for now.

The unconformity/correlative conformity at the base of the Cenozoic section does not appear to outcrop on the Makarov Basin side of the ridge along our drift track (Fig. 8). A possible explanation is that the slope is less steep and the ridge is wider than elsewhere. The absence of faults in the sediment section on the upper slope in this area is also conspicuous.

Fig. 8 Screen shot of the raw seismic data recorded across the slope of Lomonosov Ridge.

Fig. 9. Screen shot of the raw seismic data from the top of Lomonosov Ridge.

On top of the ridge is a 0.3 sec (two-way travel time) thick acoustic unit considered to be Cenozoic overlying 0.8 sec of older strata over undulating infilled acoustic basement (Fig. 9).

On Sunday, Audun changed the battery on the data logger for the radiation flux measurements and also put in the newly-arrived wind cross on the weather station.

Wild life

Our friend, the polar fox has not been seen this week.

We welcomed the new moon as it moved above the horizon on 28 December.

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 22 December.

Position: 87° 48.7' N, 72° 54' W, temperature -31° C, air pressure 1020 hPa, wind 14 knots from N. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards south. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Sent situation report to Maritime Air Support Centre, Andøya (MASC) and Forsvarets Operative Hovedkvarter (FOH) at 0240 GMT for expected supply mission. Air drop delayed by 24 hours - information received at 0530 GMT.

Tuesday 23 December..

Position: 87° 47.1' N, 72° 30' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1033 hPa, wind 5 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.1 knots southeast. Acquiring seismic reflection data all day. Submitted situation report to MASC and FOH at 0354 GMT. First contact with the Orion plane of the 333rd Squadron of the Norwegian Air Force at 0954 GMT, about 45 minutes out. The plane arrived at 1040 GMT and made 8 passes dropping 16 pieces of cargo, all except two arriving within the prepared drop zone. We had located 15 pieces before midnight.

Wednesday 24 December. Christmas Eve

Position: 87° 46.8' N, 71° 22' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1032 hPa, wind 4 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards the east. Acquiring seismic reflection data all day. Located the last item, a tent in an ice rubble field about 400 m before the start of the drop zone. Moved the remainder of the items from the drop zone to camp. The Christmas eve dinner was a cold buffet as we were too tired to arrange anything traditional.

Thursday 25 December Christmas day

Position: 87° 47.3' N, 69° 16' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1026 hPa, wind 7 knots from the south. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards the east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Unpacked some of the received cargo. The multi-fuel oven had its top deformed, but seems repairable. Keeping the hydro-hole from freezing is a problem as venting of the air-gun creates a turnover every few minutes which introduces new cold water. A 2 kW heat stick in the water or a fan heater on top makes no visible impact. The ice chisel is the only solution.

Friday 26 December.

Position: 87° 47.5' N, 66° 41' W, temperature -35° C, air pressure 1025 hPa, wind 8 knots from south. Ice drift 0.2 due east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun repaired the multi-fuel oven. Burned garbage from the packing material of the cargo. We burn all trash regularly and collect metal cans and glass in a bag for back-haul to shore in due time.

Saturday 27 December

Position: 87° 47.4' N, 64° 42' W, temperature -36° C, air pressure 1023 hPa, wind 10 knots from the southeast. Ice drift 0.1 due east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Cleared a place for the tent which for now will be an addition to our present work space. This was a cold day and we had to take the tent floor inside the cabin to heat it before it was laid out. The tent was difficult to unpack, but doable. We connected it to our air supply and the air-filled support arches inflated nicely, but after a few minutes the structure folded from loss of air pressure. After several tries, we located a leak where the hose joins the end cap of the center roof beam. It appears to be a problem related to the cold and O-rings not sealing well enough. Also, the air-gun stopped firing. It was recovered and its solenoid taken apart and cleaned. Back in the water, the gun was leaking air. We took it inside for the night as the ice drift was very slow. Now, the moon is again visible over the horizon.

Sunday 28 December.

Position: 87° 46.4' N, 63° 58' W, temperature below -40° C, air pressure 1024 hPa, wind 3 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards the south. Disassembled the air gun, but our inventory of firing seals are exhausted so the O-ring was flipped over and re-used. Back in the water, the gun was still leaking air, but giving good data and shooting continued. Audun replaced the battery for the data logger for the radiation flux measurements, and also the broken wind cross of the weather station. We constructed an inside support frame for the tent out of 2"x2" and 2"x4" lumber and now it stood up nicely. The multi-fuel oven was put in and fired up for a test. The result was good and the next task is to connect the tent to the existing work space by the hydro-hole. When that is accomplished, we should be back in business.

The eighteenth week of ice drift (29 Dec. 2014 - 04 Jan. 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 27 nautical miles (50 km) during the week (Fig. 1). The drift was slow all week and stalled completely on Saturday. The wind speeds have been less than 7 knots except for mid-week (21 knots). There was high surface air pressure over the Beaufort Sea (winds from the NW) on Monday, changing to an elongate regional high between the Siberian coast and the Beaufort Sea mid-week (winds from the ENE), and again centered over the Beaufort Sea at the end of the week.

Fig. 1. Drift track (red) of FRAM-2014/15 during week 18 (29 December 2014 - 04 January, 2015).

Sea ice dynamics

We observed intense pressure ridging about 250 meter to the north of our camp during Friday and Saturday. The noise was like being close to a large water fall, but no cracks were discovered in our neighborhood

Camp life

Temperatures were below -40°C from Monday afternoon until Wednesday morning (Fig. 2), but got 10°C warmer during the rest of the week except Saturday (-35°C). It was a quiet week as it was too cold in the beginning for outside work and we spent the time getting the items received in the air drop in place. Also a 2014 summary report for the activities during the first four months of drift was being drafted. The air-dropped pork roast, courtesy of TV2, was prepared for a New Years Evening meal, guided by instructions from home. To our great relief, the result was a success (Fig. 3).

The problem of loss of power from the generator, as well as a faulty fan heater for the compressor, kept us busy for two days but solutions were found. The air drop was supposed to include another spare generator, but the 333rd Squadron decided against; without a parachute the heavy item (20 kg) would most likely be demolished upon impact.

Fig. 2. Screen shot of the weather station before it goes off scale (i.e. below -40°C).

Fig. 3. Enjoying the pork roast dinner on New Years Eve.

Science

This week, the following suite of continuous measurements has been operating:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- four active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.
- continuous seismic reflection measurements (2 km sub-bottom penetration).

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Fig. 4. Screen shot of seismic record from the top of Lomonosov Ridge

The seismic data acquisition has been going well even as the air temperature goes below -40°C . The key to this is keeping the compressor and hydraulic reservoir heated.

Lomonosov Ridge is considered an aseismic continental fragment. An instrumental record more than fifty years long shows no evidence of earthquakes occurring on this ridge. However, a number of major submarine slide scars have been observed along the edge of the ridge. Also, we have in a number of places observed vertical displacements in the flat-lying acoustic section on top of Lomonosov Ridge - offsets which we consider unlikely to be artifacts of the data acquisition, but rather vertical faults with small throws ($<10\text{ m}$). In Fig. 4 is another example of what may be a deformation structure. We would appreciate suggestions for other possible interpretations.

A summary report of the activity on FRAM-2014/15 in 2014 was distributed on January 7th 2015.

Below is an image by Audun of the ice drift station under the full moon at the end of 2014.

Wild life

No sign of any wild life this week

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 29 December.

Position: 87° 45.3' N, 63° 34' W, temperature -35° C, air pressure 1026 hPa, wind 4 knots from NW. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards SSW. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Put up the inner tent and fired up the multi-fuel stove. Improved the heat box for the hydraulic oil reservoir and put in a fan heater

Tuesday 30 December.

Position: 87° 44.4' N, 63° 42' W, temperature -43° C, air pressure 1026 hPa, wind 2 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.1 knots due south. Acquiring seismic reflection data all day. Too cold to do any work outside.

Wednesday 31 December. New Years Eve

Position: 87° 40.7' N, 64° 47' W, temperature -38° C, air pressure 1028 hPa, wind 12 knots from the ENE. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards the SSW. Acquiring seismic reflection data all day. Rigged up the electric oven in the new tent and called home for instructions on how to prepare a pork roast. Had a successful meal of pork roast, red cabbage and cloud berries for dessert.

Thursday 01 January 2015 New Years Day

Position: 87° 36.8' N, 65° 04' W, temperature -28° C, air pressure 1020 hPa, wind 21 knots from ENE. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards southwest. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Problems with hydrophone noise in the early morning - recovered the hydrophone and put it out again.

Friday 02 January.

Position: 87° 34.2' N, 65° 05' W, temperature -27° C, air pressure 1020 hPa, wind 10 knots from ENE. Ice drift 0.1 knots southeast. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Noticed strong jerks repeatedly over several hours. The reason was active pressure ridging about 250 m to the north of us. The area seems otherwise intact. At 1400 hours the generator suddenly lost AC-power output. Hauled out the new spare generator and started it. It run for about 2 hours and suddenly stopped. The cause is no compression as one valve lifting rod is unseated. This is not repairable here.

Saturday 03 January.

Position: 87° 33.9' N, 64° 47' W, temperature -35° C, air pressure 1023 hPa, wind 3 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.0 knots. Continued repair of the used generator and found the brushes worn. Replaced them with brushes from the other newly broken one and we have power back again. Started heating the compressor

again. Periods of intense pressure ridging - sounds like standing next to a large water fall.

Sunday 04 January.

Position: 87° 33.9' N, 64° 34' W, temperature -28° C, air pressure 1030 hPa, wind 7 knots from the NNE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards the east. Resumed seismic shooting after midnight. Audun moved more fuel to the camp. Our inventory is about 7.000 liters left. Have finally thawed out my personal clothes after they got submerged in seawater on the ice when the ice hangar had to be abandoned in the beginning of October

The nineteenth week of ice drift (05 - 11 Jan. 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved about 17 nautical miles (31 km) during the week; the shortest distance experienced thus far (Fig. 1). For comparison, our maximum distance was 39 nautical miles during week 15. In general, the sea level air pressure over the Beaufort Sea was high and gave us winds from the northeast sector and ice drift to the south. The change in ice drift to the east Monday and Tuesday was forced by a low pressure trough extending north from the New Siberian Islands. Shortly thereafter, another low pressure moved north through the Fram Strait and gave us winds up to 40 knots on Thursday with blowing snow both Wednesday and Thursday. On Saturday morning the wind was down to 6 knots and the southward ice drift stopped completely until Sunday morning. During this period it took (up to) over 5 hours to move the 25 meters between air-gun shots.

Fig. 1. Drift track (red) of FRAM-2014/15 during week 19 (5-12 January, 2015).

Sea ice dynamics

At 0100 hours on Monday morning Audun discovered a new 20 cm wide crack 25 m away from the hovercraft. The crack went exactly through the hydrophone hole and passed about 1 m away from three of our food boxes (Fig. 2). The hydrophone was secured and left in the crack. There has been no motion since. Again on Saturday, we heard intense pressure ridging to the north of our camp. Audun made a reconnaissance on Sunday and discovered a lead of indeterminate width aligned with a pressure ridge. So pressure ridging and then extension had taken place.

Fig. 2. A new friendly? crack in the neighborhood.

Camp life

Temperatures were below -30°C at the beginning of the week and got 10°C warmer during the end of the week. This has been another quiet week as we have hardly been moving along over the top of Lomonosov Ridge in the direction of the Makarov Basin. There are a few small but significant issues to fix - one is the capstan liner of hard plastic (POM). Our past use of the winch to pull the cargo out of the disintegrating camp wore grooves in the POM cap on the drum. The Kevlar line no longer slides easily sideways on the drum when we pull in equipment. Ideally, you need a lathe to remove the grooves, but it is fixable here with more primitive means.

The last day of the week was remarkable; very quiet, no wind, just the air filled with falling snowflakes.

Science

This week, the following suite of continuous measurements has been operating:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- four active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.
- continuous seismic reflection measurements (2 km sub-bottom penetration).

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Fig. 3. Screen shot of seismic section on top of Lomonosov Ridge

The seismic data acquisition has been going well as usual. The solenoid valve seems to freeze up every now and then and ask for service.

Acoustic basement on top of Lomonosov Ridge has an indeterminate character (Fig. 3). The lack of a distinct reflective interface remains intriguing. What we assume to be basement shows piecewise internal stratification with dips diverging from local basement highs. Possible alternatives are partly eroded anticlines of old sediments or partly-eroded effusive volcanic centers.

Audun has downloaded the data from the chain of 30 thermistors; the 26 smaller (Model 56) went easily, but the larger ones with pressure sensors (Model 39) were more intricate (Fig.4). The total volume is about 150 Mb. The data logging will be restarted and a new deployment made.

Fig. 4. Downloading data from the temperature data loggers

Wild life

No sign of any wild life this week

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

The stars keep us company. The planet Jupiter appears just to the right of the propeller housing.

Daily reports

Monday 05 January.

Position: 87° 34.2' N, 64° 05' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1029 hPa, wind 2 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards E. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun discovered a 20 cm wide crack going right through the hydrophone hole and 1 m away from three of our food boxes. Secured the hydrophone and let it remain in the crack.

Tuesday 06 January.

Position: 87° 35.4' N, 62° 55' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 17 knots from the WSW. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards ENE. Acquiring seismic reflection data all day. Audun downloaded the data from the thermistor probes. One probe had a crack and the electronics were fried.

Wednesday 07 January.

Position: 87° 34.4' N, 63° 23' W, temperature -24° C, air pressure 1008 hPa, wind 19 knots from the ENE. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards the SSW. Acquiring seismic reflection data

all day. Had problems with triggering of the air-gun in the afternoon and also around midnight. Serviced the solenoid and the problem was fixed.

Thursday 08 January.

Position: 87° 27.9' N, 64° 12' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 1006 hPa, wind 34 knots from NE. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards SSW. Shooting seismic reflection all day. The air-gun stopped triggering around midnight - serviced the solenoid again.

Friday 09 January.

Position: 87° 23.7' N, 64° 03' W, temperature -18° C, air pressure 1014 hPa, wind 17 knots from ENE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards SSE. Put the air gun back in the water at 0200 hours, but the short section of air hose attached to the gun burst. The gun fired at a depth of half a meter in the hole and we were soaked and the whole room sprayed with ice water. Changed the hose and continued seismic reflection measurements all day.

Saturday 10 January.

Position: 87° 22.7' N, 63° 58' W, temperature -21° C, air pressure 1021 hPa, wind 14 knots from the E. Ice drift 0.1 knots due south. The ice drift stopped completely during the day. To move 25 meter took more than 5 hours. Acquiring seismic data all day. Had to end seismic line 2014-12 before midnight and reboot the acquisition computer.

Sunday 11 January.

Position: 87° 22.8' N, 63° 57' W, temperature -18° C, air pressure 1001 hPa, wind 6 knots from the south. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards the northeast. The ice started moving again in the early morning. Started seismic line 2015-13.

The twentieth week of ice drift (12 - 18 Jan. 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved only 8 nautical miles (15 km) during the week. Most of the motion was back and forth within an area of 1.5 nautical miles (Figs. 1 and 2). The drift was extremely slow Wednesday through Saturday even though the wind speed reached 17 knots on Saturday. The surface air pressure field has been dominated by an elongated high between Beaufort Sea and the East Siberian Sea throughout the week, with a high pressure ridge extending from there towards the North Pole Wednesday through Saturday. Winds were less than 5 knots until Thursday and >10 knots during the last part of the week.

This week included another very special event in the High Arctic with the arrival of the Norwegian Polar Institute's research vessel LANCE at 83° 15' N, 21° 32' E, northeast of Svalbard (Fig. 2). This is the starting point for an ice drift with an extensive program to study processes within the young ice. See the web site: www.npolar.no/en/expedition-field/n-ice2015,

Fig. 1. The drift track (red) of FRAM-2014/15 during week 20 (12-18 January, 2015).

Sea ice dynamics

An ice floe is a relatively flat area surrounded by recently active pressure ridges or open leads. The interior of a floe may contain older subdued pressure ridges, but no open cracks. The floe where our camp is located is bounded 200 meters to the north by a pressure ridge with an open lead behind it. The lead is now closing, but no consequences have so far been felt in the camp. In the dark the lack of overview of the area and ice activity around us is frustrating. The recent crack mentioned in the last report has been inactive. We have made reconnaissance trips to the old disrupted camp area and there are no signs of recent ice activity.

Fig. 2. Overview of current drift ice stations present in the Arctic Ocean.

Camp life

Temperatures this week have been ranging between -25°C and -35°C until Saturday afternoon. From then on it went below -40°C . The week has been dominated by two issues; the slow drift, on the average 500 meters a day, and the break-down of our generators. We started out with two new identical 4.5 kW diesel generators and now both are down for the same fatal reason; one valve rod on each is unseated, and the adjustment screw on the valve rocker arm broken. Metal pieces came out when the oil was drained. One generator had over 3.000 hours and the other 2 hours. The loss is very inconvenient, but will not hamper our continued operation. We have a small 800 W generator, but it does not seem to hold any load. We also started out with two 1 kW wind mills as back-up. One wind mill got buried by ice blocks during the last camp break-up and our effort to recover it failed. The other got submerged by overwater on the ice and is still not tested. Our ultimate back-up for charging of batteries is a 90 W fuel cell which consumes 1.5 liters of ethanol a day. The daily supply of electric power is provided by the 440 horsepower hovercraft engine which has to run for twenty minutes every two hours. During idling, it consumes 3 liters/hour. So far, the engine has started instantly in temperatures below -40°C even in cases where it has not been in operation for at least 24 hours. Our AC power comes from an inverter which changes 28 volt DC into 230 volt AC with a maximum permissible load of 500 Ws.

In practical terms, the loss of the generators means; no melting of snow by electric heating (i.e. no showers), no use of the electrical oven for cooking, no electric heat on the compressor (Fig. 3) and hydraulic oil reservoir, no use of the heat gun, and no outside lighting. The most inconvenient issue is loss of heat on the compressor, but this will be compensated for using a diesel-fired stove.

Fig. 3. The compressor (240 liters/min) and air bottles (40 liter capacity) mounted on the port deck of the hovercraft for supply of air to the air-gun.

Science

During the week, the following suite of continuous measurements has been operating:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- four active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.
- continuous seismic reflection measurements (until Wednesday morning).

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

The seismic data acquisition continued until Wednesday morning. We moved only a kilometer over the top of Lomonosov Ridge on the Makarov Basin side from Sunday night until Wednesday morning.

Audun finished resetting the 30 thermistor probes and the 300 m long string was redeployed on Thursday (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Deploying the 300 m long thermistor string

Wild life

Audun discovered fresh tracks of a polar fox. This individual came up from our down-wind side and just passed through our camp. The animal did not dwell on anything in particular and probably got

scared from human presence - a behavior which is very different from our previous visiting fox four weeks ago. We think two separate individuals are involved.

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 12 January.

Position: 87° 22.8' N, 63° 52' W, temperature -25° C, air pressure 999 hPa, wind 3 knots from the ESE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards W. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun was occupied with restarting the data loggers for the thermistor string. Checked the radiation flux instruments. Data logger battery is 12.9V, the large battery for ventilator is 14.3 V. Cleaned all sensors and also the weather station sensors. A lead, about 200 m to the north of the camp, has been present since we came to this site 1.5 months ago. The lead is now closing.

Tuesday 13 January.

Position: 87° 23.4' N, 63° 57' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 1009 hPa, wind 3 knots from the NE. Ice drift 0.1 knots due south. Acquiring seismic reflection data all day. At 2200 hours, the generator suddenly stopped. The cause was loss of compression. Adjustment screw on valve rocker arm broken and valve lifting rod unseated - metal parts came out when the oil was drained. We had two identical 4.5 kW diesel generators and now both are down with the same fatal fault. One generator had over 3.000 hours and the spare only 2 hours before break-down.

Wednesday 14 January.

Position: 87° 22.5' N, 63° 47' W, temperature -30° C, air pressure 1019 hPa, wind 1 knot from the SSW. Ice drift 0.0 knots. Acquiring seismic reflection data until 0815 hours as we were out of air from loss of heat on the compressor. Started work on the generator to see if there was any hope of repair. The engine has to be opened from the generator side and the generator axle is pressed on to the engine drive shaft so special tools would be needed. Further pursuit of repair was considered futile. Audun made a hole for deployment of the thermistor string. The hole is to be lined with three plastic core liners bundled together and partly filled with ethanol. This will make recovery easy and avoid the fishing operation needed to catch the top of the string.

Thursday 15 January.

Position: 87° 22.3' N, 63° 46' W, temperature -24° C, air pressure 1021 hPa, wind 5 knots from the south. Ice drift 0.0 knot. Deployed the thermistor string about 70 m from the hovercraft. Took down the old generator shack and started to make preparations for rebuilding the heat box for the compressor. Heating would now be by a diesel stove. Fresh tracks of a polar fox were spotted by Audun.

Friday 16 January.

Position: 87° 22.1' N, 63° 51' W, temperature -33° C, air pressure 1022 hPa, wind 12 knots from the east. Ice drift 0.1 towards NNW. We started the small 800 W generator and ran it for three hours. Went down to the old camp area, dug out one drum of gasoline and hauled it to the new camp. Checked the radiation flux instruments and cleaned all sensors. Ran the small generator again, but it is unable to handle the load when charging the hovercraft batteries. The generator engine runs, but power is lost. This means we are permanently out of 230 V power, except for what can be derived from a 500 W, 28 Volt DC to 230 Volt AC inverter. In practical terms it means; no melting of snow by electric heating, no use of the electrical oven for cooking, no electric heat on the compressor, no use of the heat gun, and no outside lighting. The most serious issue is loss of heat on the compressor.

Saturday 17 January.

Position: 87° 22.0' N, 63° 55' W, temperature -29° C, air pressure 1012 hPa, wind 17 knots from the south. Ice drift 0.0 knot. We built a new tunnel of plywood to route intake of air to the lift fan from the top of the superstructure and not from the inside of our work space. Audun prepared an aluminum Zarges box to serve as the bay for the diesel stove and an attachment to the existing heat box for the compressor.

Sunday 18 January.

Position: 87° 22.0' N, 63° 23' W, temperature <-40° C, air pressure 1012 hPa, wind 14 knots from WSW. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards the east. We put the air box in place and closed all openings between the work space and the hovercraft superstructure. Also connected the Zarges box with the stove. It is very cold today, so between jobs you often have to go inside and warm up.

The twenty-first week of ice drift (19 - 25 Jan. 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved only 21 nautical miles (39 km) during the week. The motion was south-southeast along the top of Lomonosov Ridge on the Makarov Basin flank (Fig. 1). The major surface air pressure event of the week was a low moving up through the Fram Strait on Thursday, which settled over the North Pole and deepened on Friday, and later moved onwards to Severnaya Zemlya. Winds were less than 16 knots. A more inconspicuous low pressure cell over the Canadian Arctic Islands generated winds over 20 knots and blowing snow from the afternoon of Sunday the 25th. With that the ice drift changed 300° and our camp was once again moving towards the Makarov Basin at a speed that increased to 0.6 knot.

Fig. 1. The drift track (red) of FRAM-2014/15 during week 21 (19-26 January, 2015).

Sea ice dynamics

This week we have only heard a short event of ice ridging somewhere in the distance in the darkness.

Camp life

The week started with temperatures below -40°C on Monday. On Tuesday, the air got gradually warmer, the warmest being -29° on Thursday, and then fell to -38°C on Sunday. Work this week has focused on how to compensate for the break-down of the two generators. First task was changing the heating system for the compressor, and then trying to get the smaller generator, the wind mill, and the fuel cell up and running. The modifications of the heat box were finished on Thursday and tested on Friday. It became a better solution than what we had with electric heating; providing more heat and better service access. Audun worked on the small generator; the engine runs, but power is intermittent and the problem remains. He then turned to the fuel cell. The message he got from the display of a cell tested before departure was: Error code 75 - Call Service! The oracle at the company hot-line said; Press Reset three times - and then nothing more? The cell works for a short while and then quits. Next in line is the wind mill that was submerged by overwater on the ice and needs to be taken apart before start-up.

The new moon came over the horizon on Friday, but has so far mostly been hidden by clouds. The total darkness has a considerable impact on your energy to get the daily work done - you're constantly feeling tired even though the food variety is good and you dutifully slip down a few vitamin pills and a mouthful of cod liver oil. You have to mobilize what will power you have to keep on track with a regular daily schedule. Depending on the weather situation and ice activity, your work day priorities in total darkness change constantly. Much of the work has to do with preparedness or compensation for not being prepared. Snow drifts grow and change constantly. To avoid losing gear and supplies in the snow may at times be a full time job for one person.

At the North Pole, the sun was 23° below the horizon on 22 December and at present it is about 14° below during mid-day. The darkest day of the year in Longyearbyen, Svalbard (22 Dec.), when the sun is 11° below the horizon, will be equivalent to the light we will experience on February 10th.

Science

During the week, the following suite of continuous measurements has been operating:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- four active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.
- continuous seismic reflection measurements (from early Saturday).

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

With heat back on the compressor, the seismic data acquisition is up and going again. But first we had to open the refrozen hydro-hole which was closed by 0.5 m thick ice in the middle and narrowed on the sides over the whole 1.5 m ice thickness . For this particular task we have constructed a hydraulic chain saw which is capable of making 1.2 m deep vertical cuts in the ice (Fig. 2). The saw performed very well and this was its first real test.

Fig. 2. The new hydraulic chain saw invented for making vertical cuts in the ice. This prototype, made from junk yard resources, works well.

The seismic results show another variety of what we consider acoustic basement on top of Lomonosov Ridge (Fig. 3). The sharp reflective segment and abrupt terminations are suggestive of a volcanic flow or a sill intrusion into the sediment pile. If so, it provides among other things a way to date the sediments as it may be related to the extensive volcanic activity that took place in the Eastern Arctic around 90 million years ago. Other occurrences of volcanics, as interpreted from seismic data, are known from the central part of Lomonosov Ridge and from the ridge plateau near Ellesmere Island.

We have retagged the Kevlar rope at one hundred meter intervals as the original 3.000 m length has now been shortened to about 2.800 m due to wear. The intent is to take some short cores as we make the final crossing (??) of the ridge on our return drift from the present excursion into the Makarov Basin. Strong persistent northeasterly winds from Sunday onwards are suddenly taking us one more time towards the Makarov Basin and maybe all the way across the postulated sheared continental margin of polar Europe in the late Mesozoic.

Fig. 3. Screen shot of seismic monitor to show possible presence of lava flow or volcanic sill as part of acoustic basement on top of Lomonosov Ridge. Some traces are noisy as the winds were 25-30 knots during acquisition.

In the absence of suitable generators, our temporary reduced capacity for charging of batteries is a concern unless we run the main engine for extended periods. One of the implications is insufficient power for the fan on the radiation flux instrument. We hope to find a solution in the coming week.

Wild life

There has been no sign of animal life in our neighborhood during the week.

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 19 January.

Position: 87° 21.8' N, 63° 03' W, temperature below -40° C, air pressure 1012 hPa, wind 5 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards E. A very cold day. A Zarges box is used as cabinet for the diesel stove and was attached to the compressor box. We run the main engine for 15 to 30 minutes every two hours to charge the batteries.

Tuesday 20 January.

Position: 87° 21.6' N, 63° 00' W, temperature -37° C, air pressure 1020 hPa, wind 3 knots from the SW. Ice drift 0.0 knots. Continued work on the compressor box. Moved the hydraulic oil tank which is to be included in the compressor box. Re-routed some of the air hoses. Tested the stove, but it would not burn properly.

Wednesday 21 January

Position: 87° 21.3' N, 62° 59' W, temperature -33° C, air pressure 1021 hPa, wind 9 knots from the E. Ice drift 0.1 knots due east. Checked the radiation flux instrument; cleaned sensors. Fan had stopped due to a flat battery. Put in replacement battery. Audun downloaded data for the last month (since 19 Dec. 2014) from the memory card. The weather station is fine. Moved one fire extinguisher to the tent where the multi-fuel stove is going.

Thursday 22 January

Position: 87° 20.5' N, 63° 04' W, temperature -29° C, air pressure 1000 hPa, wind 11 knots. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the SSW. Finished the compressor heating box and started warming it up. Audun worked on the small 800 W generator to see if we could get power from it - the engine runs, but power is only sometimes there, but most often not.

Friday 23 January

Position: 87° 13.4' N, 61° 38' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1006 hPa, wind 10 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.4 towards SE. The hydro-hole had frozen up after not being used for 8 days. It now has 0.5 m thick ice in the middle and was narrowed on its sides over its whole 1.5 m ice thickness. Mobilized the newly-invented hydraulic chain saw to make vertical cuts down-hole. This worked very well, but it still took most of the day to get the hole cleared.

Saturday 24 January

Position: 87° 08.6' N, 60° 17' W, temperature -37° C, air pressure 1028 hPa, wind 6 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the southeast. The air-gun went into the water after midnight and seismic shooting resumed at 0253 hours. However, the seismic data logger started intermittent self-triggering during the day. The problem was cured with advice from Ole Meyer. Audun started the fuel cell. Error code 75 Call service, was the response. Submitted an inquiry to the factory by e-mail.

Sunday 25 January

Position: 87° 08.3' N, 60° 00' W, temperature -38° C, air pressure 1029 hPa, wind 3 knots from ESE. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards the south during the first part of the day. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Prepared the winch and Kevlar drum. Started remarking the 2.800 m Kevlar rope we have left. The wind increased dramatically in the evening and the ice drift increased to 0.6 knot.

The twenty-second week of ice drift (26 Jan.- 01 Feb. 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved 31 nautical miles (57 km) during the week. The motion was to the west over the slope of Lomonosov Ridge into the Makarov Basin (Fig. 1). During the first four days of the week a ridge of high surface air pressure extended from the Bering Strait to the North Pole, but the effect of a low pressure cell over the Canadian Arctic Islands set the ice in motion to the west. Winds from the northeast were up to 36 knots and the drift speeds exceeded 0.6 knots. The time between seismic shots at 25 meter intervals was less than 80 seconds. The low pressure weakened on Thursday and was replaced by a surface air pressure high between Greenland and the Beaufort Sea. From Thursday onwards, the winds were less than 10 knots. On Sunday morning, our drift direction turned south for a while.

Fig. 1. The drift track (red) of FRAM-2014/15 during week 22 (26 Jan. - 02 Feb. 2015).

Sea ice dynamics

We have not noticed any evidence of ice activity in our neighborhood during the week in spite of the period of fast drift early in the week.

Camp life

The low pressure activity early in the week brought in relatively warm air and we experienced temperatures of -22°C to -24°C on Monday through Wednesday. From Thursday it became colder, the lowest being -39°C on Saturday. The period of strong winds, blowing snow and fast ice drift kept us busy up through Wednesday. On Thursday it was time to dig out equipment from the snow drifts and the rest of the week we were occupied with maintenance. We clearly made the right decision with parking the hovercraft with the front pointing northeast which turned out to be the prevailing wind direction. Snow drifts accumulate off to the sides of the craft and behind the work space (tent and snow hut). Blowing snow creeps in everywhere and one of the early worries was getting the hovercraft engine compartment filled with snow. Fortunately, this turned out to be totally unfounded.

The one wind turbine that was rescued when the camp broke up was taken apart and checked for salt deposits. Audun mounted it on a pole on Sunday (Fig. 2), but we are not quite satisfied with the power output. We have also replaced the six 110 Ahr. batteries in the hovercraft with the new ones brought as spares, but in the meantime used heavily for other needs. They hold the charge better and represent a considerable improvement. Also, the radiation flux instrument needs extra power to drive the fan which keeps the sensors clean. In the cold, a car battery gets flat after 2-3 days. This is now solved by supplying 12 volts directly from the hovercraft via a 50 m cable.

Fig. 2. Audun working on the wind turbine. The work tent is in the foreground behind a snow drift.

Our hydro-hole through the 1.5 m thick ice was about to freeze up again and required a new effort with the vertical ice saw. In the process on Friday, we discovered that the air-gun was hanging just from the air supply hose and the signal cable, an uncomfortable situation which easily could have resulted in loss of the air-gun. The wire end had corroded and broken off. The air-gun was recovered and seismic shooting stopped temporarily, because the ice drift was near zero from Friday through the rest of the week. On Sunday the seismic data logging PC crashed and would not reboot normally except in "Safe Mode" - we are working on the problem guided by expertise from NERSC.

On Sunday, we checked through the conductivity-temperature-depth (CTD) instrument and made it ready for deployment next week. The intent is to take CTD measurements from the surface to the bottom on a regular basis for the remaining time of ice drift.

The length of Lomonosov Ridge (~1.800 km) is roughly equal to the length of Norway. We have now spent 5 months drifting over the Lomonosov Ridge and been able to get new scientific data over a section which constitutes 1/4 of the total length of the ridge. Our drift shows a pattern with periods of very slow ice drift interrupted by events with fast drift. The fast drift is forced by cells of low surface air pressure moving into the Arctic Ocean over the Canadian Arctic Islands as of late or through the Fram Strait. As they move in, the wind direction drives the ice to the west. These events, unpredictable on a time scale of months, make it impossible to estimate with some degree of confidence where we will be when it is time for Audun to rotate off in late March/April, or when we will approach the ice edge in the Fram Strait.

Science

During the week, the following suite of continuous measurements has been operating:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- four active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.
- continuous seismic reflection measurements.

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 m depths, respectively.

- 300 m long string with temperature data loggers suspended from the ice.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

The strong northeasterly winds starting on Sunday 25 January drove the ice to the west. This enabled us to obtain a seismic profile across the transition between Lomonosov Ridge and the Makarov Basin, where no seismic data exists for the first quarter of the length of Lomonosov Ridge north of the Canadian Arctic. The drift track is just as straight as that of a ship in open water (Fig. 1).

The acoustic basement of Lomonosov Ridge dips steeply ($\sim 30^\circ$) into a graben more than 2 sec. (two-way travel time) or >3 km (?) deep (Fig. 3). Acoustic basement is formed by multiple diffractions with no clear transition between the overlying sediments and basement. We are inclined to believe that acoustic basement may constitute deformed sediments with intervals of intact dipping layers as seen in the lower right part of Fig. 3. The graben is filled with more than 3 km (?) of undisturbed sediments. The ridge-to-basin transition is considered to be part of the continental margin north of Svalbard-Franz Josef Land before c. 60 million years ago, and the key issue is; is it a rifted or sheared margin? The new data obtained from this region, which is presently inaccessible to icebreaker surveys, are going to be among the most significant scientific results obtained during the FRAM-2014/15 ice drift. There will be another opportunity for more data on the return drift towards the Fram Strait.

Fig. 3. Screen shot of seismic profile across the transition between the Lomonosov Ridge and the Makarov Basin (Fig. 1).

The work done to compile and update the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean (IBCAO) represents a fundamental prerequisite to improved understanding of the evolution, past, and recent geological processes in the polar basin environment. Bathymetric maps are the starting point of any study that involves the sea bed, the sub-bottom geology, and the influence of bottom topography on water mass dynamics. As we are drifting over sea bed that mostly is known from depth soundings made during helicopter landings or from drifting ice stations, bathymetry is an important component of FRAM-2014/15. We use four autonomous echo sounding buoys within a 6 km area of the camp and the seismic reflection measurements in camp to obtain more depth information. Figure 4 shows a typical example of the reality. The map suggests we were drifting over a small high, which seems to imply that a small peak of hard rock had to come near the sea bed

where it could be draped by sediments and form a small hill. The seismic data show a flat sea bed and no indication of any disturbing topography within the upper 1.5 km below the sea bed.

Fig. 4. Drift track over a small hill appearing on the latest version of the IBCAO-map. Below is a seismic profile which shows a flat sea bed and no disturbing basement topography in the upper 1.5 km below the sea bed.

Wild life

There has been no sign of animal life in our neighborhood during the week.

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 26 January

Position: 87° 07.7' N, 61° 16' W, temperature -24° C, air pressure 1021 hPa, wind 23 knots from the NNE. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards W. Blowing snow. Shooting seismic reflection all day.

Tuesday 27 January

Position: 87° 08.9' N, 64° 33' W, temperature -24° C, air pressure 1017 hPa, wind 27 knots from the NE. Ice drift 0.5 knots towards W. Blowing snow. Shooting seismic reflection all day. The shot interval was 80 sec. at mid-day. We had to service the air-gun in the early morning. Checked the radiation flux instruments, cleaned sensors and changed battery (110 Ahr. 12.8 V) for the fan.

Wednesday 28 January

Position: 87° 10.1' N, 67° 28' W, temperature -22° C, air pressure 1010 hPa, wind 33 knots from the NE. Ice drift 0.5 knots towards W. Blowing snow. Shooting seismic reflection all day. By 1400 hours, the drift slowed down and the direction turned back east towards Lomonosov Ridge. Audun worked on the wind turbine taking it apart and checking for salt.

Thursday 29 January

Position: 87° 08.3' N, 68° 54' W, temperature -27° C, air pressure 1025 hPa, wind 10 knots from NE. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the E. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Cleaning up after several days of blowing snow. The wind turbine installed on a pole, and the power line needs to be connected

Friday 30 January

Position: 87° 07.5' N, 68° 12' W, temperature -31° C, air pressure 1025 hPa, wind 7 knots from the NE. Ice drift 0.1 towards E. Checked radiation flux instruments; cleaned sensors, changed fan battery (80 Ahr., 13 Volts), changed memory card and battery on the data logger. The used battery measured 12.2 Volt. Checked the weather station. Worked on cleaning the hydro-hole using the vertical ice saw. Discovered the air-gun hanging from the air hose and the signal cable - the tow wire had broken. Recovered the air-gun. Insufficient wind to test the wind turbine.

Saturday 31 January

Position: 87° 07.4' N, 67° 45' W, temperature -39° C, air pressure 1029 hPa, wind 3 knots. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the east. PC for seismic data logging crashed, but came up again. Laid out 12 Volt power from the hovercraft to the radiation flux instruments to avoid problem of maintaining batteries out in the cold.

Sunday 01 February

Position: 87° 06.8' N, 67° 40' W, temperature 37° C, air pressure 1029 hPa, wind 10 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards east. Audun connected up the wind turbine, but outside switch box was corroded and had to be replaced. CTD was checked and batteries changed. Replaced starter batteries (2 x 110 Ahr.) and service batteries (4x 110 Ahr.) in the hovercraft. The seismic data logging PC crashed again. We are not drifting anywhere for the moment so no opportunities are lost.

The twenty-third and twenty-fourth week of ice drift (02 - 15 Feb. 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved 62 nautical miles (114 km) during these two weeks. We drifted from the Makarov Basin over the top of Lomonosov Ridge and reached the edge on the Amundsen Basin side (Fig. 1). Strong low pressure activity during the first half of February generated fast ice drift. A low pressure ridge moved up through the Fram Strait and shifted eastward to extend between Svalbard and the North Pole and later between Novaya Zemlya and the North Pole. We had a period of fast ice drift (0.5 knot) to the southeast on February 5th and during most of the second week of February. Winds were 10 to 23 knots with blowing snow.

Fig. 1. The drift track (red) of FRAM-2014/15 during weeks 23 and 24 (02 - 15 Feb. 2015).

Sea ice dynamics

For a short while on Thursday 12 February, we heard loud sounds of ice pressuring a few hundred meters to the north of us, but have not noticed any consequences in our immediate surroundings. If anything, it is hidden by the darkness.

Camp life

Temperatures during the first week of February oscillated between -23°C and below -40°C during the first half (2-5 Feb.) and stayed below -40°C from Thursday the 5th through Sunday the 8th of February. In spite of this, the last part of the week was the most productive we have had in quite a while. The second week had smaller temperature variations (-24°C to -32°C). We have slowly gotten our work space into better order, but the darkness and the cold have undoubtedly had an effect on us. You develop a mental aversion towards certain tasks when the temperature falls to -40°C and below because of all the cold-related complications. You try to be aware of your own behavior at all times by asking: Why am I responding in this way to this particular challenge? It takes a determined effort to move out of this aversive state. Once you have started the process, the profound pleasure of seeing good results coming out of your data acquisition effort creates surplus mental energy.

In spite of the darkness and the cold, our general feeling is that time flies - we often talk about that. Unfortunately, there is hardly time for yourself. Since we are only two persons, you are always haunted by a backlog of duties, mostly related to preventive measures. The seismic operation is an extra challenge because it is an around-the-clock duty where you do not get more than 1.5 hours sleep before having again to get dressed and attend to the compressor in the outside work space.

The loss of the generators temporarily diverted our attention from science and created a wake of temporary solutions for conserving electric power. The problem is recently compounded by the breakdown of both the primary and spare inverters (24 volt input, 230 volt AC output) received with the air drop. An inverter is used to power the smaller battery chargers (head lamp, seismic data logger etc.). As usual there are ways to get around the problems.

Seismic data logging was moved to an identical backup system, as the primary PC failed to reboot properly at the beginning of the week. The process was guided by expert advice from PhD. Student Gaute Hope (NERSC) and senior engineer Ole Meyer (Univ. of Bergen), who both designed and implemented the overall data acquisition and communication system for the hovercraft.

Engine maintenance in the cold is an important challenge. To grease a bearing is impossible as the cold grease will not move the few centimeters between your grease gun and the bearing. A heat gun would help, but we have no generator to power a heat gun.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- four active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.
- 110 km of continuous seismic reflection measurements.

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 1050 (660) m depths, respectively.

- 300 m long string with temperature data loggers suspended from the ice.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work

- Ten CTD casts.
- Three short sediment cores.
- One successful deployment of the camera sled in 1.260 m water depth. Two other attempts with only partially useful footage due to light failure.
- Raised one current meter from 1050 to 660 m depth to avoid touching the bottom.

The drift this week enabled us to start a continuous seismic profile from the Makarov Basin across the Lomonosov Ridge into the Amundsen Basin. The slope facing the Makarov Basin was covered the first week and the flat top of Lomonosov Ridge during the second week. In total 110 km of seismic data acquired. The acoustic image of the basin to slope transition is similar to that shown in Fig. 3 of the report for week 22. On the upper flank, the whole 1.5 sec thick flat-lying section on top of the ridge appears to be truncated at the sea bed on the slope (Fig. 2). The truncated strata may be covered with a thin sub-bottom drape. The sediments on top of the ridge are flat-lying and undisturbed (Fig. 3) with a minimum thickness of 1.6 sec (~2.5? km). The flat top of Lomonosov Ridge is bounded to the east by a basement ridge. Unfortunately, because of the combination of fast ice drift and our crossing in the early hours on Saturday morning, we were unable to deploy the rock dredge in time for this target.

Fig. 2. Screen shot from the seismic monitor record drifting over the edge of Lomonosov Ridge.

Fig. 3. Screen shot of the seismic monitor where the ice station is over the top of Lomonosov Ridge.

Fig. 4. Screen shot of the seismic monitor when the ice drift is over the eastern edge of the flat area on top of Lomonosov Ridge.

Fig. 5. Screen shot of the seismic monitor showing a peculiar acoustic image within the upper 0.3 sec. (300 meter) of the sea bed. Asterisks indicate an offset artifact from changes in the pulse form as a result of increase (10-20 bars) in operating air pressure to the nominal 140 bars every time the compressor is run to replenish the air reservoir.

Fig. 6. Our preliminary interpretation of the acoustic image as sediment deformation due to impact of an object on the sea bed. The diffraction points may be possible fragments of the object.

We came across a very mysterious perturbation of the flat-lying undisturbed seismic sequence on the top of Lomonosov Ridge (Fig. 5). The water depth is 1.260 m. A small depression is flanked by symmetric elevated rims and extends over a depth range of about 150 m. Point diffractors are present at several levels at the center of the structure. A similar feature is observed about 5 km

farther east. The limited depth extent and the symmetry suggest the disturbance may be due to forces exerted from above into an undisturbed sea bed. The disturbed section appears to be covered by a ~0.02 sec. (20 m) thick sediment drape.

We welcome alternative interpretations of the observations in Figs. 5 and 6. Our working hypothesis is that the sea bed has been disturbed by an object which fell into the Arctic Ocean and created a 300-400 m wide "crater" in the sea bed and the underlying stratigraphy to 150 m sub-bottom (Fig. 6). The overlying ~20 m thick sediment drape suggests this event occurred on the order of 2 million years ago. The observation of two small possible impact structures on Lomonosov Ridge is a remarkable parallel to our observation of a 200 km x 600 km area of disturbed sea bed sediments on the Alpha Ridge about 450 km to the west (see attached publication). On the Alpha Ridge, massive submarine slides have been triggered, in places more than 100 m of sediments have been "blown away" and near bottom sediments have been deformed. All this is now covered by a 20-25 meter thick sediment drape. Our interpretation of the observations from Alpha Ridge was that fragments of an asteroid hit the Arctic Ocean about 2 million years ago and created a pressure wave which heavily disturbed the sea bed in the area of impact. So far there is no evidence of one or more craters. We suggest that the events on Alpha Ridge and Lomonosov Ridge could be related. To the best of our knowledge, there is so far no known direct evidence of impact craters in the deep global ocean. The Eltanin impact in the SE Pacific in about 4.000 m water depth is manifested by disturbed sediments.

We started our vertical profiling of conductivity (salinity), temperature and depth (CTD) from surface to the bottom in the Makarov Basin as the drift direction again turned towards Lomonosov Ridge. The instrument is a self-contained Sea Bird SBE 19plus V2 (Fig. 7). Casts were done each day and the separation varied between 13.5 and 5 km. This data will add to the inventory of oceanographic measurements used to characterize water masses and temporal changes in temperature, and to carry out calculations of the geostrophic currents needed to maintain the dynamic balance.

Fig. 7. Preparing the CTD to be lowered through the hydro-hole.

Three short sediment cores were obtained from the top of Lomonosov Ridge for the Ice2Ice project of several Nordic centers of excellence. The Ice2Ice project seeks to document the extent of sea ice in the Arctic Ocean during warm climate periods and to investigate its relation to the state of the Greenland Ice Sheet.

We deployed the camera sled in 1.260 m water depth and obtained about 30 minutes of HD video recording of life forms at the sea bed. This includes another glimpse of a half meter long bluish fish. Some of the footage is attached to this report. Unfortunately, the underwater lights are giving us problems and the intensity of one of the lights is reduced. We had two more deployments that were only partly successful due to light failure as well as the camera sled getting dragged sideways.

Fig. 8. From our effort to raise the current meter. Watching the underwater camera (left) and the picture on the screen showing the Kevlar rope having an angle at about 45° instead of being vertical.

The ice drift was heading for an area of the Lomonosov Ridge which would be shallower than 800 m. On Wednesday 11 February we managed to raise one of the current meters to 660 m depth. This instrument was initially suspended at 2.000 m and later raised to 1.050 m. The next day, we started work on the mooring for the instrument that has been at 800 meter depth since September 2014. It is now only 5 m away from a substantial pressure ridge which clearly spells trouble. We were unable to hook on to the Kevlar line under the ice. With the help of an underwater camera, we discovered the line had an angle away from the pressure ridge (Fig. 8). This indicates that the neighboring ice floe has been pushed under the site of the current meter and has diverted the line. There are now two layers of ice separated by a water layer. It may still be possible to rescue the instrument, but it will take a lot of work. The task has been postponed until late spring/early summer

We have started to see indications of light on the horizon to the south at noon.

Wild life

There has been no sign of animal life in our neighborhood during the week.

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 02 February

Position: 87° 06.0' N, 67° 48' W, temperature -28° C, air pressure 1027 hPa, wind 10 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.0 knot. Seismic acquisition PC is down - we are working on the problem. Audun moved fuel towards the camp from a temporary fuel bladder location. Sent an invitation to Dr. Artur Chilingarov for a Russian polar scientist/technician to replace Audun at crew change.

Tuesday 03 February

Position: 87° 05.9' N, 67° 47' W, temperature below -40° C, air pressure 1017 hPa, wind 5 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.0 knot. PC completed 15 hour disk scan/repair cycle. PC reboots in Windows as usual, but flips back to fault conditions. Checked the radiation flux instruments and cleaned sensors. Made the first CTD cast down to 2.450 m in 2560 m water depth.

Wednesday 04 February

Position: 87° 04.0' N, 67° 47' W, temperature -23° C, air pressure 981 hPa, wind 10 knot from the N. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards E. Moved seismic acquisition to back-up PC which has an identical set-up. Restarted seismic shooting at 1245 hours. Checked radiation flux instrument and cleaned sensors. Made another CTD cast down to 2.400 m depth - water depth is 2.550 m. Audun moved 1.000 liters of diesel up to the hovercraft.

Thursday 05 February

Position: 87° 03.8' N, 65° 28' W, temperature -36° C, air pressure 990 hPa, wind 15 knots from the S. Ice drift 0.4 knot to the E. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Made a CTD cast. On the way up, the CTD remained at 600 m depth for one hour because a hydraulic hose burst and had to be replaced. Reamed the sides of the hydro-hole.

Friday 06 February

Position: 87° 05.6' N, 63° 23' W, temperature below -40° C, air pressure 997 hPa, wind 17 knots from the S. Ice drift 0.2 towards ENE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. The camera sled was deployed in 1.260 m water depth. About 30 minutes of video recorded with the sled in motion and several life forms imaged which we have not seen in our earlier deployments. A CTD cast made to 1180 m depth.

Saturday 07 February

Position: 87° 06.5' N, 62° 32' W, temperature below -40° C, air pressure 1005 hPa, wind 4 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Deployed the short sediment corer and recovered a 20 cm core for the Ice2Ice-project.

Sunday 08 February

Position: 87° 05.8' N, 62° 10' W, temperature below -40° C, air pressure 999 hPa, wind 6 knots. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards east. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Made a CTD cast to 1.130 m - water depth is 1.250 m. Added more lead weights to the short corer, and we moved the Kevlar drum from the cold work space into the heated tent.

Monday 09 February

Position: 87° 04.0' N, 61° 33' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 994 hPa, wind 8 knots. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Checked the radiation flux sensors; the fan works fine. Recovered one sediment core (60 cm) in 1.260 m water depth and made one CTD cast down to 1.100 m depth.

Tuesday 10 February

Position: 86° 59.8' N, 60° 33' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 990 hPa, wind 16 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.3 knot towards SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Deployed the camera sled in 1.150 m water depth. The camera lights went to blinking mode at the bottom and made the run less useful. Made CTD cast down to 1.080 m depth.

Wednesday 11 February

Position: 86° 57.2' N, 58° 57' W, temperature -29° C, air pressure 990 hPa, wind 14 knot from WSW. Ice drift 0.4 knots towards SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Raised one current meter from 1.050 m depth to 660 m by drilling a hole and snagging the Kevlar line with a hook. Pulled the Kevlar through a pipe filled with ethanol to facilitate an new easier adjustment of its depth once we are off the ridge.

Thursday 12 February 2015

Position: 86° 53.5' N, 57° 08' W, temperature -24° C, air pressure 1003 hPa, wind 11 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.3 knot to the SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Started work to raise the second current meter from 800 m depth. The location is now 5 m from a pressure ridge. Using the underwater camera, we saw the Kevlar line diverted away from the pressure ridge. To recover the instrument required drilling holes to follow the line until we reached the end of the under-thrusted ice floe. This work has to be deferred until late spring/early summer.

Friday 13 February

Position: 86° 46.7' N, 54° 51' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 1001 hPa, wind 23 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.4 towards SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. A snow storm outside made problems getting inside the outer work space. Made one CTD cast in the early hours to 750 m depth and another cast late at night to 850 m depth. We also made two attempts to obtain a short sediment core, but the corer had no penetration and came up empty

Saturday 14 February

Position: 86° 43.3' N, 52° 43' W, temperature -30° C, air pressure 1005 hPa, wind 9 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.3 knot to the E. Shooting seismic reflection all day. We missed out on deploying the rock dredge over a basement exposure on the sea bed. Worked all day to improve the hydro hole which was about to be closed by new ice. Made a CTD cast in the evening and deployed the camera sled. Upon recovery, the video footage showed the camera lights had gone into blinking mode and also that the sled had been dragged sideways.

Sunday 15 February

Position: 86° 43.2' N, 52° 00' W, temperature -36° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 6 knots from the E. Ice drift 0.0 knot. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Checked out the radiation flux instrument and cleared the IR sensors for snow. Deployed the sediment corer in the early hours and obtained a 38 cm core for the Ice2Ice project. Audun went for a ski trip in the neighborhood. If the drift speed

holds up, we are about to enter the 200 nautical mile zone north of Greenland in a day or so.

Photo: Audun Tholfsen

The twenty-fifth week of ice drift (16 - 22 Feb. 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved 40 nautical miles (74 km) during the week. The drift was over the slope of Lomonosov Ridge into the Amundsen Basin (Fig. 1). The surface air pressure has had a steady pattern with a regional low pressure in the sector between Greenland and Severnaya Zemlya and a high pressure region between the Beaufort Sea and the East Siberian Sea. The result has been prevailing northerly winds at our location and steady ice drift towards southeast. The drift speed has been 0.2-0.3 knot with a maximum of 0.4 knot early Saturday 21 February.

Fig. 1. The drift track (thick red) of FRAM-2014/15 during week 25 (16 - 22 Feb. 2015).

Sea ice dynamics

On Wednesday evening, we discovered a thin crack running parallel to the hovercraft about 3 m away. The trace went under a fuel bladder and the diesel was immediately pumped over to the hovercraft fuel tank. No further motion has taken place.

Camp life

On Monday 16 February the temperature was -40°C , and varied between -26°C and -33°C later in the week. The week has been fairly productive scientifically, but our electric power challenge took another turn on Thursday when the wind turbine stopped after two weeks of operation. In winds above 16 knots, it delivered enough power to break even with our consumption. Upon inspection of the brand new turbine, we found the shaft bearing was intermittently locking the motion. With no spare ball bearing of the correct size available, the wind turbine is no longer functional. The fate of our initially diverse options for electric power during planning of this expedition defies our imagination. We considered two 4.5 kW diesel generators, two small gasoline generators (0.8 and 1.2 kW) and two wind turbines (1 kW) to give a sufficient safety margin. Both diesel generators have suffered the same fatal mechanical failure after over 3,000 hours and 2 hours, respectively. One gasoline generator and one wind turbine were lost in the ice when the camp broke up in October, and the last wind turbine is now out. The only item left is the 800 W generator which does not hold a load. Although this may sound dramatic, the problem is solved by temporarily including our auxiliary batteries which need to be charged along with the battery bank of the hovercraft engine. The result is no more time wasted on temporary solutions.

We are drifting over the lower slope of Lomonosov Ridge into the Amundsen Basin. As the ridge is now behind us, we feel the pressure is off for a couple of weeks until we get over the next submarine feature, the Morris Jessup Rise north of Greenland, presumably in late March (Fig. 1). Staying alert and ready to exploit any scientific opportunity on the sea bed presented by the seismic data on the screen, puts pressure on you day and night throughout the week. There is always a trade-off between science and logistic priorities. Camp maintenance had to become second priority for a while in spite of our awareness of the accumulated effect of recurrent periods of blowing snow week after week. We have been parked in one place since early December, and blessed with no interference from ice activity, but at a price. An over 2 m thick snow drift has accumulated on the upwind side of our work space on the port side of the hovercraft and is as high as the roof (Fig. 2). Elsewhere the additional snow depth around the hovercraft is about 0.5 m. The priority now is to make the preparations needed for relocation if desired or needed. Another task on the waiting list is relocating the 8 drums of Jet-A-1 fuel (kerosene-type fuel with -47°C freezing point) from the old camp area. They were stored near the old ice hangar and in the zone which suffered from invasion of over water on the ice. As a result, the lower 20 cm of each drum is frozen into the ice.

Fig. 2. The hovercraft and work space on 5 January (left) and 22 February (right).

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- 74 km of continuous seismic reflection measurements.
- four active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and temporarily at 660 m depths, respectively.

- 300 m long string with temperature data loggers suspended from the ice.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work: - Four CTD casts.

- Two camera sled deployments (2.280 and 2080 m water depths).
- One unsuccessful sediment coring attempt.

Another 74 km of seismic reflection data has been added to a continuous seismic profile from the Makarov Basin across the Lomonosov Ridge into the Amundsen Basin (Fig. 1). The total length of this transect is now 184 km. It is our intent to continue the seismic data acquisition over this unsurveyed southern part of Amundsen Basin until we pass the Morris Jesup Rise.

Fig. 3. Generalized sub-bottom geology along the drift track. .

The upper slope of Lomonosov Ridge is underlain by thick sediments which is onlapping a basement domain of possible volcanic origin from the mid-slope and deeper (Fig. 3). This was all surprising, since the oldest magnetic isochrones in the Amundsen Basin indicate there is space in this area which may be occupied with continental crust of a collapsed margin.

The prevailing wind pattern has shifted from northeast to west and we have been concerned about the ambient noise level when the hovercraft engine was running. We moved the hydrophone site to the upwind side and got much better results.

Our intent was to take CTD casts at regular intervals for the remainder of the drift. We have completed a transect of 14 CTD casts across Lomonosov Ridge, but are getting increasingly concerned about our fuel situation. Each cast takes about 3 hours of engine time which also contributes to charging batteries. However, we need to have three stoves going; two in the hovercraft and one for the compressor, plus a fourth stove in the work space as needed. In addition, we need to run the engine for about 20 minutes every 1.5 hours to replenish charge level on the hovercraft service batteries which power the data logging systems. All in all it amounts to over 50% higher-than-expected consumption. For this reason, we postpone further CTD work until we have established how much of the Jet-A1 fuel we have to contribute to a crew change.

Gaidropsarus argentatus (?)

Lycodes frigidus (?)

Fig. 4. Pictures of fish species imaged by the bottom camera sled on Lomonosov Ridge. The occurrences are shown in Fig. 5.

We observed fish in both camera sled deployments this week. The video clips, submitted as attachments to earlier reports, have been looked at by a number of experts. Randi Ingvaldsen of the Institute of Marine Research, Bergen, has kindly collected information from Russian and Norwegian colleagues. The consensus is that the grey fish species is most likely a *Gaidropsarus argentatus* (Norw.; Sølvtangbrosme). This species have been recovered by trawl north of Svalbard. The darker fish is probably a *Lycodes frigidus* (Norw.; arktisk ålebrosme). The Arctic Biodiversity Assessment report (<http://www.arcticbiodiversity.is/the-report/chapters/fishes>) lists thirteen species of fish found in the Arctic Central Basin, but the *Gaidropsarus argentatus* is not included. Our observations may be the first documentation of its presence in the deep basin.

Fig. 5. Locations of sightings of fish in the field of view of the bottom camera sled.

The sun is now about 9 degrees below the horizon at noon and one may walk outside without the need of a head lamp.

Wild life

There has been no sign of animal life in our neighborhood during the week.

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 16 February

Position: 86° 42.3' N, 51° 47' W, temperature -40° C, air pressure 1018 hPa, wind 4 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the south. Shooting seismic reflection all day. We are at the edge of the flat-topped ridge, water depth 1500 m. Made a CTD cast down to 1450 m at 1445 hours and another cast at 2300 hours to 2000 m in 2080 m water depth.

Tuesday 17 February

Position: 86° 40.7' N, 51° 20' W, temperature -33° C, air pressure 1012 hPa, wind 8 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Deployed the camera sled in 2.280 m water depth. Unfortunately, the Kevlar laid out on the bottom had hooked on to the sled and pulled it sideways. Made a CTD cast down to 2.100 m water depth. Also deployed the short sediment corer - had 0.6 m penetration, but the core barrel came up empty.

Wednesday 18 February

Position: 86° 37.2' N, 50° 28' W, temperature -26° C, air pressure 1005 hPa, wind 11 knot from the NW. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. CTD cast down to 2.400 m in 2.500 m water depth. Each run takes about 3 hours with the hovercraft engine running. We have to conserve fuel and will stop making CTD casts from now on. We have so far obtained a transect with 13 casts over the Lomonosov Ridge. Blowing snow in the evening. Audun discovered a small crack running parallel to the hovercraft about 3 m away. The crack went under one of the fuel bladders and the fuel was immediately pumped over to the hovercraft.

Thursday 19 February

Position: 86° 32.2' N, 50° 11' W, temperature -33° C, air pressure 1013 hPa, wind 10 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.2 knot to the SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Our internal WiFi-network which distributes the GPS-signal to the different logging systems was down for about one hour. Audun continued exploring our small 800 W generator which will take a heavy load such as the grinder (600 W), but not a small load such as battery chargers. The key is adjustment of the rpm. Also the wind turbine stopped; the problem being the seizing of its shaft ball bearing.

Friday 20 February

Position: 86° 29.8' N, 49° 39' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 12 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.3 towards SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Deployed the camera sled in 2.080 m water depth. Another observation of a fish on video.

Saturday 21 February

Position: 86° 23.5' N, 47° 54' W, temperature -27° C, air pressure 1009 hPa, wind 16 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.4 knot to the SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Continued testing the small 800 W generator. Started preparations for jacking up the hovercraft to get out of the snow drift. The hovercraft has been sitting on two 2" x 2" planks since the beginning of December and held up very well. This is in strong contrast to what we experienced in September and October when the keel was constantly sinking into the relatively warm ice. However, on the outside about 0.5 meter of snow has by now accumulated on the starboard side and 1.5 meter on the port side.

Sunday 22 February

Position: 86° 18.2' N, 46° 33' W, temperature -29° C, air pressure 1003 hPa, wind 9 knots from NW. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Started jacking up the hovercraft to free it from the snow. To get it free will be a major job which from now on will have first priority.

The twenty-sixth week of ice drift (23 Feb. - 01 March 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved 13 nautical miles (24 km) during the week over the transition between the Lomonosov Ridge and the Amundsen Basin (Fig. 1). Our good progress towards the Fram Strait over the past two weeks came to a standstill from Wednesday on. Also, the subsequent slow motion was in small nested loops. A high pressure ridge extended from the Beaufort Sea to the East Siberian Islands at the beginning of the week and later moved north to a position over the Canadian Arctic Islands. The effect at our location was northerly winds. Winds were variable during the last part of the week, due to low pressure activity.

Fig. 1. The drift track (thick red) of FRAM-2014/15 during week 26 (23 Feb. - 01 March 2015).

Sea ice dynamics

No ice activity in the neighborhood during the week.

Camp life

Temperatures during the first part of the week were around -30°C , and Friday and later around -40°C . The week started off with blowing snow all day on Monday. The snow drift attached to the work space, deposited mainly by winds from the north, is now as high as the roof of the tent and ice-house part of the workspace. Work this week has revolved around fighting the impact of snow on the hovercraft (Fig. 2). The hovercraft is able to lift because of the cushion of air trapped by the skirt and the ground. However, the 10-15 centimeter of snow on the ice is porous and the air escapes so it is difficult to get lift. We have put a tarp under the length of the craft to seal off air leakage. We also have various preventive maintenance tasks to do on the engine, but it is too cold right now to get it done.

Fig. 2. Clearing the hovercraft skirt for snow at local noon 25 February.

Tuesday 24 February was a clear day and we could work outside without the need of a head lamp for the first time since the beginning of October. It was a good feeling. Audun took a two hour ski trip in -40°C on Sunday to look for the two nearest autonomous bathymetry buoys, but did not find any. More light will help and the sun will reach our horizon about 10 March. From about 1 April, we will have the midnight sun for the remainder of our drift.

We have now spent exactly half a year on the ice - a milestone we celebrated by the dinner on Saturday 28 February. The menu was spare ribs and a Radeberger beer courtesy of Capt. Swartze, *Polarstern*, with apple cake for dessert. Unfortunately, the seismic data acquisition stopped in the middle of the meal - the air-gun would not fire. Since we were drifting over a large submarine channel on the seabed not portrayed on any official bathymetric maps, we had to attend to the air-gun problem immediately. It took several attempts and work through the whole night until 1000 hours the next day, before we were again back in operation.

As mentioned in an earlier report, Audun is doing most of the cooking. The capacity of our freezer is overwhelming. Everything freezes up whether you like it or not; potatoes and onions appear like steel balls. We take the potatoes inside for an hour or two, cut and wrap them in aluminum foil and place them on the stove for about one hour (Fig. 3). The result is tasty cooked potatoes, as if they never had experienced any frost. The onions are cut frozen and fried - again with a good result.

Fig. 3. The frozen potatoes (left) being cut and placed in an aluminum foil on top of the stove.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- 24 km of continuous seismic reflection measurements.
- four active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 2.000 m depths, respectively.

- 300 m long string with temperature data loggers suspended from the ice.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work

None.

The water depth is about 3.000 m and beyond the length of our available Kevlar line (2.800 m). The CTD work has been suspended in order to ease our fuel situation.

The drift track went in tight loops and the seismic reflection data obtained this week represent only a limited contribution to a regional transect (Fig. 1).

The seismic record from the lower slope of Lomonosov Ridge on both sides show abundant wavy accumulations of sediments within the upper 200 m sub-bottom (Fig. 4 and earlier reports). We interpret these features as sediment drifts which demonstrate that bottom currents and sediment supply has been favorable for accumulation of drifts. We measure the strength of present contour-following currents via the current meter suspended at 2.000 m depth, which will enable us to make a qualitative statement about the paleo-current field relative to the present.

Fig. 4. Screen shot of seismic section from the lower slope towards Amundsen Basin.

The deepest current meter had been raised to 660 m depth to clear the topography of Lomonosov Ridge. We have now entered the Amundsen Basin and hope we will not return to the ridge. The current meter was therefore lowered to its original depth at 2.000 m below the ice. We had to cut the Kevlar frozen into the ice and the new connection runs through a 9 cm diameter plastic pipe filled with ethanol that will not freeze.

Wild life

There has been no sign of animal life in our neighborhood during the week.

Despite the cold, life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 23 February

Position: 86° 13.7' N, 46° 03' W, temperature -31° C, air pressure 1002 hPa, wind 13 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.3 knot to the SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Blowing snow. The snow drift is level with the top of our work space and we have problems getting in.

Tuesday 24 February

Position: 86° 09.9' N, 45° 47' W, temperature -27° C, air pressure 996 hPa, wind 10 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards SW. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Serviced the air-gun and reamed the hydro-hole. Lowered the current meter suspended at 660 m depth back to its original 2.000 m depth. Today is a clear day with sufficient light so we can work outside without the need for a head lamp.

Wednesday 25 February

Position: 86° 08.7' N, 45° 48' W, temperature -38° C, air pressure 1022 hPa, wind 6 knots from the NE. Ice drift 0.0 knots. Operating the seismic reflection gear, but no ice drift. Removed the snow and freed the skirt on the port side of the hovercraft. Audun dismounted the wind turbine support.

Thursday 26 February

Position: 86° 08.1' N, 45° 47' W, temperature -29° C, air pressure 1013 hPa, wind 15 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.0 knot. No ice drift and the seismic gear on standby. Prepared for jacking up the hovercraft, disconnected from the work space and raised the starboard side of the hull 10 cm.

Friday 27 February

Position: 86° 08.8' N, 45° 38' W, temperature -38° C, air pressure 1014 hPa, wind 6 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards E. No ice drift and the seismic gear on standby. Removed the snow and freed the skirt on the starboard side and jacked the hull up 12 cm. Put a tarp under the front 1/3 of the length of the craft. Checked the radiation flux instruments. The fan is not running at the moment because of insufficient battery capacity.

Saturday 28 February

Position: 86° 08.8' N, 45° 34' W, temperature -39° C, air pressure 1012 hPa, wind 5 knots from the NE. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the N. We put a tarp under the middle section of the hovercraft. Today, we have been 6 months on the ice. Had a near formal dinner of spare ribs and apple cake and enjoyed a Radeberger beer from the case provided by the Captain on *Polarstern* at their departure. The air-gun

stopped during the meal. To get it working again took three trials in the water and work from 2000 hours until 1000 hours the next day. The solenoid was working, but the gun would not fire. Checked the radiation flux instrument at 1930 hours and cleaned the IR sensors. The fan is still not in operation.

Sunday 01 March

Position: 86° 08.1' N, 45° 03' W, temperature below -40° C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 8 knots from S. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards E. Worked on the air-gun until 1000 hours and went to bed. Audun went for a two hour ski trip to search for the two nearest bathymetry buoys, but did not locate any. Our internal Wi-Fi network for data distribution went down in the late evening and had to be rebooted.

FRAM-2014/15 at 1800 hours local time on 28 February. Photo: Audun Tholfsen

The twenty-seventh week of ice drift (02 - 08 March 2015)

Ice drift

The difference between the locations of the ice camp at the beginning and end of the week was 1.5 nautical mile (2.7 km). However the zig-zags in between amount to 14 km. All in all, the most extreme drift we have experienced so far. Winds have been less than 7 knots all week and mostly from the northwest. The drift direction has shifted back and forth between SE and W - in the latter case against the wind direction. Surface air pressure has maintained a high pressure ridge between the Canadian Arctic islands and the New Siberian Islands through Wednesday. On Thursday, our area was under the influence of a low pressure system north of Canada, and from Friday a low pressure cell heading north through the Fram Strait. On Sunday afternoon, southerly winds generated by the low pressure finally set the ice in motion and the drift was 0.3 knots. As we hardly moved during the whole week, we include results obtained Monday 9th and Tuesday the 10th of March in this report.

Fig. 1. The position of FRAM-2014/15 as of 10 March 2015. The drift from 2 - 9 March 2015 is too small to be visible at this scale.

Sea ice dynamics

A friendly thin crack was discovered on Sunday about 55 m from the craft, which separates the thermistor string from the rest of the camp. It runs 8 m from the thermistor string and 20 m from the radiation-flux instruments.

Camp life

Except for a mild Friday March 6th (-22° C), temperatures this week ranged between -27° C and -40° C. Our main activity this week has been camp logistics and hovercraft maintenance. We have now broken loose all ten drums of Jet A-1 fuel that had been frozen into the ice (20 cm) by water that flooded the ice at the time our ice hangar had to be abandoned last October (Fig. 2). This fuel will now be used for heating during the remainder of the drift. We also finished off our hovercraft site project by putting a tarp under the rear part of the hovercraft to seal off air leakage in case we have to lift off and move. However, any attempt to move will be a major challenge because of the snow accumulation around us - we will deal with that when the time comes (Fig. 3). The opportunity presented by the warm weather on Friday was used for engine maintenance. A tarp over the engine bay and a propane heater inside made reasonable working conditions for readjusting the lift fan drive belt which is an awkward job due to difficult access. We could grease all points and also change the fuel filters. Fulfilling our expectations, the 440 hp Deutz diesel engine has performed extremely well and started on the first turn at all times in temperatures below -40° C. We passed 2.000 engine hours on Monday and about 500 hours were used on this trip.

Fig. 2. Breaking loose the frozen-in fuel drums at the old camp site.

Fig. 3. The FRAM-2014/15 camp site. Note the amount of snow on the left side of the hovercraft.

So far, we have made three attempts on skis and by foot to search for the nearest autonomous bathymetry buoy which should be about 500 m from the old camp, but with no success. On Sunday, Audun made a 2.5 hour ski trip to look for the second nearest buoy and found it 1.7 km north of our present camp (Fig. 4). We are communicating with Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, USA on how to troubleshoot it and get it back in operation.

Fig. 4. Instrument case of one of the autonomous bathymetry buoys.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- 14 km of continuous seismic reflection measurements.
- four active autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 2.000 m depths, respectively.

- 300 m long string with temperature data loggers suspended from the ice.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work:

None.

The water depth is about 3.300 m and beyond the length of our available Kevlar line (2.800 m). The CTD work has been suspended in order to ease our fuel situation.

The drift track during the week was a tight zig-zag at the foot of the slope, but the distance covered nevertheless represented 14 km of seismic reflection data. The big change came Sunday afternoon and through Monday the 9th and Tuesday 10 March as we started drifting south at 0.3 knots. We had anxiously been waiting for this moment for almost two weeks. We expected to pass over a feature on the seabed of major geological significance (Fig. 5), but as yet unexplored, and not present on any editions of the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean (IBCAO Fig. 6). Our camp drifted over a submarine channel, almost 300 m deep with an apparent width of 5 km (Fig. 5). For insiders, this dimension is comparable to the width of Manhattan Island, New York (3.7 km) or the inner Oslo Fjord at the latitude of Nesodden (4.6 km). This is the largest deep sea channel in the Arctic Ocean known at present. In 2004 we published on the feature in *Marine Geology* and also submitted a formal application to GEBCO for naming it the *NP-28 Channel* in recognition of the contributions to Arctic marine geo-exploration made by the Soviet ice drift station NP-28. The NP-28 seismic data presented the first evidence for the existence and dimensions of the channel. The absence of this large submarine feature in any bathymetric maps is most likely explained by the simple fact that mapmakers can only portray on a map what is justified by the bathymetric database. We will contribute the latest available data to rectify this deficit.

Fig. 5. Screen shot of the seismic section across the channel. Apparent width is 5 km, but true width is more like 3.5 km.

Fig. 6. Compilation of available seismic data documenting the presence of the NP-28 Channel.

We interpret the NP-28 Channel to have been the major pathway for sediment transport to the southwestern part of the deep Amundsen Basin. The sediments have most likely been supplied by glacial advances over the Lincoln Sea continental shelf and mass wasting on the continental slope

funneled into a channel at the foot of the rising topography of the Lomonosov Ridge. With time a submarine fan evolved to comprise a major part of the deep Amundsen Basin north of Greenland (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 Outline of the trajectory of the NP-28 Channel, its suggested sediment source area on the Lincoln Sea continental slope and relation to the deposition of a large submarine fan in the Amundsen Basin. From Kristoffersen et al., Marine Geology, 2004.

In the last report we mentioned that one of the current meters had been lowered back to its full depth (2.000 m). A picture from this operation was inadvertently left out and is shown here in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Lowering the current meter back from 660 m depth to 2.000 m.

Wild life

There has been no sign of animal life in our neighborhood during the week.

Despite the cold, life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

At noon March 5th 2015. A walk in the polar desert looking for an autonomous bathymetry buoy.

Daily reports

Monday 02 March.

Position: 86° 07.6' N, 45° 05' W, temperature - 33° C, air pressure 1018 hPa, wind 9 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the W. Shooting seismic reflection until 1200 hours. Hauled a drum of Jet A1 fuel from the old camp to the hovercraft to use for the stoves.

Tuesday 03 March.

Position: 86° 07.6' N, 45° 20' W, temperature -30° C, air pressure 1018 hPa, wind 3 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards W. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Checked the radiation flux instruments and cleaned sensors. Have included the battery for the fan into the battery bank for the main engine to secure charging.

Wednesday 04 March

Position: 86° 07.5' N, 45° 29' W, temperature - 31° C, air pressure 1013 hPa, wind 7 knot from the NW. Ice drift 0.1 knots towards W. Operating the seismic reflection gear, but little or no ice drift. Freed two more drums of Jet-A1 from the ice in the old camp. Have received 5 cm of snow today.

Thursday 05 March

Position: 86° 07.6' N, 45° 16' W, temperature - 40° C, air pressure 1000 hPa, wind 1 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the W. Shooting seismic reflection, but little or no ice drift. Went to the old camp and broke loose the last 5 drums of Jet-A1 fuel from the ice. Took a 1.5 hour search for the bathymetry buoy nearest camp (500 m) , but did not find anything.

Friday 06 March

Position: 86° 07.3' N, 45° 16' W, temperature - 22° C, air pressure 994 hPa, wind 3 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.1 towards SE. A most welcomed "hot" day and opportunity for engine maintenance. Put a tarp over the engine bay and used the propane burner for heating. Adjusted the lift fan belt tension, greased all points and changed diesel fuel filters. We have lately been unable to get the engine to run over 1000 rpm, which turned out to be clogged fuel filters for the second time on the ice.

Saturday 07 March

Position: 86° 06.9' N, 45° 08' W, temperature - 29° C, air pressure 994 hPa, wind 2 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the W. Shooting seismic reflection all day, but almost no ice drift. Checked radiation flux instruments and weather station and removed frost. Audun went for a 2.5 hour ski trip and located

bathymetry buoy # 2 at 1.7 km away in the direction of 044 degrees.
Reported to Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution.

Sunday 08 March.

Position: 86° 06.5' N, 44° 58' W, temperature - 29° C, air pressure 993 hPa, wind 6 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards E. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Checked radiation flux instruments and the weather station for snow on sensors. Audun moved 1000 liter of our remaining fuel some of the way from the old camp towards the hovercraft. White out and light snow in the morning and light blowing snow towards the evening. A friendly thin crack was discovered about 55 meter from the craft and separates the thermistor string from the rest of the camp. It runs 8 meter from the thermistor string and 20 meter from the radiation-flux instruments.

The twenty-eighth week of ice drift (09 - 15 March 2015)

Ice drift

The FRAM-2014/15 ice camp drifted 32 nautical miles (60 km) during the week (Fig. 1). The ice was driven by winds (12-16 knots) from the north due to a low pressure system that moved north from the Norwegian-Greenland Sea. Its center was over Svalbard at the start of the week (9th March) and later moved east (Fig. 2). The ice drift was 0.3 knots up until Thursday, 12th March and then slowed down to less than 0.1 knots.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 28, 09 - 16 March 2015 (heavy red line). Thin red line indicates start of 570 km long seismic transect from the Makarov Basin to the Morris Jesup Rise.

Low pressure systems moving into the Arctic Ocean have profound effect on ice motion. The direction of the wind associated with a low pressure cell is anti-clockwise and roughly parallel to the contours, pointing slightly towards the center. The tighter the contours of equal pressure (isobars) around the center, the stronger the wind. A low pressure cell moved north from the Norwegian-Greenland Sea towards Svalbard on March 8th and then east towards Franz Josef Land and the New Siberian Islands (Fig. 2). The effect was persistent strong winds from the north in the area north of Greenland. The wind field effectively accelerated the sea ice transport out of the Arctic Ocean into the Fram Strait over the whole area to the south of the position of the FRAM-2014/15 ice camp (Fig. 3). The message for us is that as we drift south, we are likely to experience the effect of similar low pressure trajectories and a more dynamic ice situation than we have had so far this year.

Fig. 2. Maps of air pressure at sea level from www.dmi.dk showing the motion of a low pressure cell during the first part of week 28. This situation gave persistent winds from the north towards the Fram Strait between Svalbard and Greenland.

Fig. 3. Satellite image courtesy of www.woksat.info for the area north of Greenland. Note region of large broken up units south of the position of the FRAM-2014/15 ice camp

Sea ice dynamics

The friendly thin crack discovered a week ago about 55 m from the hovercraft and separating the thermistor string from the rest of the camp, widened to about 3 m and later narrowed to about 2 m on Sunday. It runs 8 m from the thermistor string and 20 m from the radiation-flux instruments.

Fig. 4. Friendly cracks in our neighborhood and the camp in the background.

Camp life

Air temperatures varied little during the week; -21°C to -26°C during the first four days and between -29°C and -1°C at the end of the week.

Work this week has mainly been keeping the seismic data acquisition and other instruments going. The effect of the unfortunate loss of the generators is becoming more and more apparent. Instead of a 5 hp generator, we have had to run the 440 hp main engine 5 hours per day for 2.5 months now to charge batteries. The consequence for our fuel supply is becoming a serious concern. If we do not get access to a generator in the near future, we will have to cut data acquisition for all systems that require power from the hovercraft.

Fig. 5. Fuel is contained in 1.000 liter fuel bladders and moved by pumping.

Removing snow is a never ending project. Passing centers of low air pressure are associated with winds and good ice drift towards the Fram Strait, but also with falling snow which collects into drifts.

The return of daylight was a big change and brings back a feeling of more energy. Our first priority was to assess the surrounding ice landscape. Our floe or flat area is about 200 x 400 m and appears like a reasonable place to be. The prevailing scenery in our neighborhood is one with ice blocks scattered around everywhere and in general not particularly friendly for hovercraft driving.

Fig. 6. The first glimpse of the sun.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- 60 km of continuous seismic reflection measurements.
- four autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 2.000 m depths, respectively.

- 300 m long string with temperature data loggers suspended from the ice.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work:

None.

The water depth is about 3.300 m and beyond the length of our available Kevlar line (2.800 m).

The seismic data acquisition is going very well. We have now completed the first half of an over 500 km long seismic profile which hopefully will extend from the Makarov Basin in the NW to across Morris Jesup Rise in the SE (Fig. 1).

About 20 km into Amundsen Basin from the foot of the slope of the Lomonosov Ridge, we observe a series of strong reflection segments at about 1.0 - 1.5 sec. (~1 km) two-way travel time below the sea bed (Fig. 7). The termination of each segment is associated with an edge diffraction. We may interpret these acoustic segments as sills (horizontal intrusions of volcanic melt) or lava flows. If so, the age of the volcanic rocks (Late Cretaceous/early Cenozoic?) can constrain the age of the host sediments.

As we move into the Amundsen Basin, we observe a thick section of undisturbed flat-lying sediments. Our penetration is limited to about 2 sec. (~2 km) below the sea bed.

The weather station and the radiation flux measurements are running well. Icing on the sun time detector has become less of a problem and power for the fan for the radiation detectors is provided by 12 volts directly from the hovercraft.

Fig. 7. Screen shot of seismic section off the foot of the slope showing possible evidence of sills or lava flows in the sedimentary section.

Fig. 8. Attending to the weather station (left) and the instruments for measuring the radiation flux (right). The camp in the background (left).

Wild life

There has been no sign of animal life in our neighborhood during the week.

Despite the cold, life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 09 March

Position: 86° 05.3' N, 44° 26' W, temperature -25° C, air pressure 990 hPa, wind 14 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.2 knot to the E. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Checked radiation flux instruments - all sensors OK, even sun time detector. Also weather station OK. Audun determined by GPS the true heading of the hovercraft to be N81°E. The thin crack near the thermistor string has widened to 20 cm. Put a tarp under the rear end of the hovercraft to seal off air leakage.

Tuesday 10 March

Position: 85° 59.6' N, 43° 41' W, temperature -21° C, air pressure 997 hPa, wind 14 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.3 knot towards SE. White-out all day. About 10 cm of snow the last 24 hours. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Checked the radiation flux instruments and the sensors were fine.

Wednesday 11 March

Position: 85° 52.2' N, 43° 01' W, temperature -24° C, air pressure 1006 hPa, wind 16 knot from the NW. Ice drift 0.3 knots towards SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Checked radiation flux instruments and weather station - all OK. Moved fuel from storage towards camp by pumping and moving bladders in relay. Cleared snow from the hovercraft skirt.

Thursday 12 March

Position: 85° 50.3' N, 42° 35' W, temperature -26° C, air pressure 1008 hPa, wind 12 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.2 knot to the E. The sky was clear and we saw the sun for the first time this year. The whole disc was already a couple of degrees above the horizon. Its presence sure makes a difference. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun made a ski trip to the nearest bathymetry buoy 1.7 km out for a check on its functionality.

Friday 13 March

Position: 85° 48.9' N, 42° 12' W, temperature -29° C, air pressure 1012 hPa, wind 1 knot from the NW. Ice drift 0.0 knot. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Checked radiation flux instruments and cleaned IR (up) and sun time sensors. More work on moving fuel. The fuel consumption needed to keep the data acquisition going is a growing concern.

Saturday 14 March

Position: 85° 48.3' N, 42° 03' W, temperature -31° C, air pressure 1011 hPa, wind 2 knots from the S. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Checked

radiation flux instruments and weather station and removed snow and frost. Audun went and brought back bathymetry buoy # 3 for checking. The crack near the thermistor string has widened to 3 m.

Sunday 15 March

Position: 85° 47.4' N, 42° 05' W, temperature -31° C, air pressure 991 hPa, wind 10 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards S. Shooting seismic reflection all day. White out and blowing snow. The friendly crack about 55 m from the craft separating the thermistor string from the rest of the camp widened yesterday to 3 m and has now narrowed to about 2 m. It runs 8 m from the thermistor string and 20 m from the radiation-flux instruments. The first drum of Jet A-1 fuel for 3 stoves lasted for 11 days.

The twenty-ninth and thirtieth weeks of ice drift (16 - 29 March 2015)

Ice drift

The FRAM-2014/15 ice camp drifted 32 nautical miles (60 km) during the two weeks (Fig. 1). The ice motion was to the southeast and to the right of winds from the west-northwest during Monday the 16th through Thursday the 19th of March. The driving force was a region of high surface air pressure over the Canadian Arctic Islands. Then followed a period of southerly winds around the weekend and later winds from the north, but the ice drift was small. Wind speeds have been less than 10 knots during the whole period.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during weeks 29 and 30; 16 - 29 March 2015 (heavy red line). Thin red line indicates start of 570 km long seismic transect from the Makarov Basin to the Morris Jesup Spur.

Sea ice dynamics

Week 29 (16-22 March) was calm, but severe ice activity started Monday the 23rd of March and continued throughout the week. The campsite occupied since mid-December included an area of about 100 m by 100 m with distributed food, fuel, equipment and instruments. Half of this surface area was completely annihilated by a combination of one ice floe being thrust under another and a pressure ridge forming. This includes the site where the hovercraft was parked and where most of the cargo was located.

Camp life

Air temperatures during the two weeks have been nearly constant (-30°C to -35°C) except Monday and Tuesday the 16th and 17th of March (-28°C). The first week was quiet and involved the daily routines keeping the seismic reflection measurements going and checking instruments. Preparations were made for an inevitable exit from this site at some unknown date. We cleared the snow around the hovercraft skirt as we have many times before, and laid out anchor points for pulleys to be used to pull us out of the snow pit.

The wake-up call came at noon on Monday 23rd March as a crack opened 3 m to the side of the hovercraft and separated the tent from the craft (Fig. 2). The radiation flux instrument and the weather station were now on the opposite floe with the tent; the thermistor string was on a separate floe. By Wednesday this crack had become a 100 m wide lead and we saw the tent in the distance. As soon as the crack opened water flooded part of the parking area and the skirt. The large accumulation of snow around the work space had loaded down the ice. The skirt in the water would have quickly frozen in -28°C temperatures, and presented an imminent danger. We disconnected all cables and structures connected to the hovercraft and recovered the air-gun. As we tried to move out, the engine would not reach high enough rpm to give us proper lift and help the winch pull us up the incline and out of the snow pit. After some time, we gained half a boat length, enough to get the skirt out of the water. However, we were not able to resolve the rpm problem and contacted Griffon Hoverworks in Southampton, UK the next day. Here we got an immediate response from a team of engineers including expertise from Deutz, UK. We monitored the hovercraft engine performance using the diagnosis software and e-mailed screen shots to UK for scrutiny. From these, Deutz's UK engineer J. Thompson concluded that condensation in the air-cooler was the likely problem caused by hundreds of hours of idling at very low temperature. The big air-cooler was removed, taken inside and thawed (Fig. 3). Five liters of water was drained out. With this, the engine speed was back to normal. We now started to get the hovercraft up the incline and out of the snow pit, but overloaded the electric winch and later recognized that the damage to the winch was fatal.

We had another winch with only 40% of the capacity of the former. Audun arranged a series of pulleys which increased the theoretical pull by a factor of six, and we hauled the craft out of the snow pit (Fig. 4). Early Thursday morning the 100 m wide lead started closing and ice rubble from its 15 cm thick, newly-formed ice poured into the former work space and parking area (Fig. 4, lower left). We drove the hovercraft to a new site about 100 m near the middle of the floe. On Friday the two floes made contact. By Saturday, our floe had been thrust under the other, about 50 m of ice

consumed and a 3 m high pressure ridge formed. Our entire campsite had been annihilated. We lost a few small equipment items and were able to pull two boxes with some food and the multi-fuel stove out of the front of the advancing pressure ridge (Fig. 4). There was a certain degree of disorder after the ice activity appeared to be over (Fig. 5)

The thermistor string had been separated from the camp area by a north-south trending lead and as it closed it also moved over 100 m to the north. We searched for the string and recognized we should be only meters away from its likely position, but there was no sign of the mooring. This was a blow to our oceanography program. As you may recall, we also lost the acoustic Doppler current profiler during the ice activity in October.

We have just experienced a recurring event in the life cycle of sea ice formation. The impact on us is not so much being repeatedly shaken by unexpected developments, and challenges to one's ability to improvise and get out of difficult situations. The most significant impact relates to your state of mind and the struggle to maintain the motivation to face another start all over again; in this instance for the fifth time in -30° C temperatures and colder. The midnight sun is here by now, the white open landscape is beautiful and quiet - a harmonic dream scene, but you walk around with a feeling of being mentally burnt out. The job to get the camp back in order will take more than one week. We have left the Lomonosov Ridge, but still move over unexplored sea bed which represents a unique opportunity to get new data.

Safety

Contrary to the perception of many people, living on sea ice presents no greater risk to life than walking the streets of any city, unless you behave in an utterly stupid manner. It does represent a risk to immobile hardware placed on the ice. All relative ice movements are slow - less than 1 meter per minute. To the best of our knowledge, in the nearly eighty year history of ice drift stations no casualty has ever been related to ice floes breaking up or pressure ridge formation. The few lives lost have all been related to helicopter and aircraft operations, and one shooting. Formation of a crack or a pressure ridge is not an accident, but a natural process in the life cycle of sea ice formation. A crack is more or less harmless, but ice ridging is destructive and you will need to get any hardware out of the way. In the extreme case of losing the hovercraft, we have tents, stoves, provisions and fuel to live comfortably on the ice for several months. It may be fortuitous, but it appears to us that if a lead widens to more than a few meters, a pressure ridge will likely form when the floes come together again. Although our data base is meager, so far we consider the width of a lead to be an omen.

Fig. 2. Opening of the crack that separated the tent (buried on the right side) from the hovercraft.

Fig. 3. Audun having dinner under the thawing intercooler suspended from the hand rail above.

Fig. 4. Different phases of the destruction of the campsite.

- Upper left: Ready to winch the hovercraft out of the snow pit.
- Upper right: The abandoned parking place partly filled with water.
- Lower left: The pressure ridge moving in.
- Lower right: Audun is pulling out the multi-fuel stove from the front of the pressure ridge which by now had advanced 40 m to the left of the parking area.

Fig. 5. Equipment and provisions having been moved away from the advancing pressure ridge.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- 41 km of continuous seismic reflection measurements (week 29 only).
- one autonomous echo sounder buoys reporting to shore via Iridium.

Oceanography:

- two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 2.000 m depths, respectively.
- thermistor string lost.

Atmosphere:

- measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.
- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work:

None.

The water depth is about 3.300 m and beyond the length of our available Kevlar line (2.800 m).

The seismic data acquisition was going very well up until Monday 23rd March when ice activity started. We passed the foot of Morris Jesup Rise, but the sediments were thick and we did not directly see basement reflections. During several time intervals the records show unknown signals with amplitudes up to ten times that of the bottom reflection.

Fig. 6. Screen shot of the seismic monitor on approach to Morris Jesup Rise. Display with fixed gain.

The weather station and the radiation flux measurements were unaffected by the ice activity and were moved over to the new camp area. However, there is no power to the fan on the radiation instrument for the time being.

Sea ice is rigid, brittle and moves on a fluid, the ocean. These properties are often used as an analog to the behavior of the outer part of the Earth. The outermost part of the Earth (the lithosphere is 10-150 km thick in the oceans) is cold, rigid, shows brittle behavior, and rests on the deeper part which is hot and able to flow on time scales of thousands of years - a phenomena much like glaciers flowing down the valleys on continents. The surface of the Earth is divided into plates which move relative to one another; new surface area is created by volcanism at mid-ocean ridges and destroyed by subduction in trenches. Similarly new ice is created by leads opening and freezing and destroyed by under-thrusting and deformation that forms pressure ridges. What happened to us during week 30 was a text book example of just this process. We stood behind the pressure ridge to the left in Fig. 7 and heard the ice floe to the right being thrust underneath the ice floe behind the ridge. The difference between the Earth and the ice analog is that the under-thrusted ice is buoyant and follows the underside of the other floe, whereas in the Earth the plate goes down because it is cold and heavy and sinks under its own weight to deeper levels (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. The analogy between destruction of plates on the surface of the Earth and partial destruction of the sea ice cover.

Other

We are proud to acknowledge the decision of the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate to support the FRAM-2014/15 expedition with NOK. 1.5 million in 2015. This brings the total funds to cover the operational costs for a ten month ice drift to NOK. 4.6 million. Additional contributions in kind are from Blodgett-Hall Polar Presence LLC (hovercraft), Alfred Wegener Institute of Polar and Marine Research (deployment), and the 333rd Squadron of the Norwegian Air Force (re-supply). We hope to be out of the ice in June.

There has been no sign of animal life in our neighborhood during the two weeks.

Despite the cold and the odd cases of ice activity, life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 16 March

Position: 85° 42.6' N, 40° 40' W, temperature -28° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 7 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.2 knot to the E. Shooting seismic reflection all day. We are getting sporadic strong chirp signals disturbing our seismic records. Checked radiation flux instruments - cleaned IR sensor. The crack has closed with minor shear movement. Audun positioned an idling wheel in front of the hovercraft to prepare for pulling it out of the snow pit. Spent the day cleaning snow from around the hovercraft.

Tuesday 17 March

Position: 85° 41.3' N, 40° 21' W, temperature -28° C, air pressure 1022 hPa, wind 3 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Large lead opened about 500 m to the north of us.

Wednesday 18 March

Position: 85° 37.7' N, 39° 45' W, temperature -36° C, air pressure 1039 hPa, wind 7 knot from the WSW. Ice drift 0.2 knots towards SE. Shooting seismic reflection all day.. Checked radiation flux instruments and weather station - cleaned IR sensor. Audun placed bathymetry buoy # 3 outside for testing with 12 volt supply.

Thursday 19 March

Position: 85° 34.4' N, 38° 51' W, temperature -31° C, air pressure 1041 hPa, wind 10 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.2 knot to the SE. Beautiful day with clear sky and the sun. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun made a ski trip to search for bathymetry buoys # 4 and # 5 - located one, but was stopped by a wide lead about 4 km out from our camp. Received an E-mail from the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate announcing their support for FRAM-2014/15 with NOK. 1.5 million.

Friday 20 March

Position: 85° 32.6' N, 38° 16' W, temperature -30° C, air pressure 1028 hPa, wind 6 knot from the NW. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the SE. The solar eclipse was hidden by clouds in the beginning and partly covered during the last phase. Shooting seismic reflection all day, but had to stop at 2300 hours due to leaking air-gun. Audun changed memory card on the radiation flux instruments. Hauled buoy #2 and two 70 Ahr car batteries out to the buoy site 1.7 km out, but unable to connect them up in the bitter cold.

Saturday 21 March

Position: 85° 30.7' N, 38° 22' W, temperature -35° C, air pressure 1027 hPa, wind 5 knots from the S. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the SE. Had 12 volt supply off from midnight to mid-day as part of checking why our power consumption is so high. The seismic data logging PC with its old battery was the problem - removed the battery and connected the power supply to a 12 volt battery on the engine side. Serviced the air-gun and started shooting at 1400 hours. Changed battery on the radiation flux instrument data logger.

Sunday 22 March

Position: 85° 28.4' N, 38° 15' W, temperature -31° C, air pressure 1030 hPa, wind 2 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.15 knot towards S. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Checked the radiation flux instruments, cleaned IR sensor and removed snow from the weather station.

Monday 23 March

Position: 85° 26.1' N, 38° 04' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1034 hPa, wind 7 knots from the S. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards S. Shooting seismic reflection. The NE-SW running crack ~50 m behind the hovercraft, that separated the thermistor string from the rest of the camp, widened to ~20 m. A parallel crack 50 m in front of the craft opened and became ~2 m wide. But at 1200 hours a new crack between the two opened 3 m from the side of the hovercraft and separated the tent from the craft. About 20 cm of overwater flooded the ice. This represented an imminent danger as the skirt would freeze in and lock the hovercraft to the ice. We disconnected cables, recovered the air-gun and took down the plywood structures that connected the tent to the hovercraft. We further laid out the 9 x 14 m tarp in front of the hovercraft to prevent air leakage through the porous snow. We started the engine, but were unable to get the necessary rpm for the craft to lift. Briefly we reached 1500 rpm which gave sufficient lift to enable the winch to pull the craft half a

boat length forward and out of the water. Tried a number of likely options (fuel filters, air filter, turbo, pipe connection to intercooler, rack on fuel pump) to solve the engine speed problem, in consultation with Bergen's chief engineer H. Berge (retired) in Spain, but got no significant improvement.

Tuesday 24 March

Position: 85° 25.4' N, 37° 49' W, temperature -31° C, air pressure 1028 hPa, wind 2 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards S. A beautiful day, no wind. We contacted Griffon Hoverworks in Southampton and got an immediate response from a team of engineers including expertise from Deutz, UK. We were able to monitor the hovercraft engine performance using the diagnosis software and e-mail screen shots to UK for scrutiny. From that, Deutz's UK engineer J. Thompson concluded that condensation in the air-cooler was the likely problem, caused by hundreds of hours of idling at very low temperature. The air-cooler was removed, taken inside and thawed out. Five liters of water was drained out. With this, the engine speed was back to normal. We now started to get the hovercraft up the incline and out of the snow pit, but overloaded the electric winch and later recognized that the damage was fatal. A propeller aircraft at low altitude was seen at 1300 GMT.

Wednesday 25 March

Position: 85° 25.3' N, 37° 26' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1009 hPa, wind 1 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards S. Beautiful day, clear sky and calm. By now the lead next to the hovercraft had widened to about 100 m. The ice activity was very low. Audun took the winch apart to attempt repair, but the windings were cut and burnt - a fatal fault. We have another small winch with only 40% of the capacity of the former. Audun devised a series of pulleys, one being the drum of the damaged winch. This scenario would in theory increase the maximum pull by a factor of six.

Thursday 26 March

Position: 85° 24.4' N, 37° 24' W, temperature -34° C, air pressure 1011 hPa, wind 7 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards S. At 0230 hours, we suddenly woke up to the sound of ice ridging - the 100 m wide lead next to the hovercraft was slowly closing. The 15 cm thick new ice on the lead was now piling up as rubble where the hydro hole was. We started winching while running the engine at maximum power and 50% forward thrust. The hovercraft came slowly up the incline out of the snow pit. The ice activity stopped in the early morning when the lead had narrowed down to 10 m. We were very tired and went to bed at 0900 hours, still only 10 m away from the lead. Got up after lunch and powered up the hovercraft at 1600 hours and drove off to a new campsite in the middle of the floe about 100 m away. The tent which was at the edge of the lead on the other side was the next priority. It was buried in snow up to the roof and the floor was covered with 10 cm thick ice from frozen overwater. The drum with 2.800 m Kevlar line and everything else were recovered.

Friday 27 March

Position: 85° 23.7' N, 37° 24' W, temperature -31° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 5 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards S. Worked all day clearing equipment and food away from the pressure ridge. The fuel was the first thing to be pumped over to an empty bladder 50 m away. The radiation flux instrument and the weather station was dismantled at 2000 hours and carried over the pressure ridge to our floe. Intermittent ice ridging had by now consumed the site where the hovercraft had been parked for the last three months. The pressure ridge was 2 m high and 10 m wide. We have up until now not lost any food or equipment.

Saturday 28 March

Position: 85° 22.4' N, 37° 30' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 9 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards S. Woke up at 0530 hours to the sound of fierce ice ridging 100 m away at the old parking site. To our surprise, the pressure ridge had increased to 3-4 m high and advanced about 40 m into our floe from the original crack where the hovercraft used to be parked. We were able to dig out two boxes of food and some equipment items. We then went to search for the thermistor string which had been isolated on another floe to the northwest. This separate lead had now closed with over 100 m of transverse motion. We could find the approximate location of the mooring site within meters, but the site was buried under a pile of ice rubble and no traces of the mooring could be seen. We went to bed at 1000 hours and got up at 1500 hours. Audun checked out the mooring sites for the two current meters and they had not experienced any ice activity. We then started preparing a new parking area for the hovercraft by pouring water over the surface, instead of having to put a tarp underneath to seal off the porous snow.

Sunday 29 March

Position: 85° 20.5' N, 37° 26' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 1021 hPa, wind 6 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards SE. Finished preparing the parking area and pulled the craft into place resting on two 4" x 4" pieces of lumber. Moved some equipment items away from the pressure ridge towards the new campsite. Audun refueled the hovercraft.

The thirty-first and thirty-second weeks of ice drift (30 March - 12 April 2015)

Ice drift

The FRAM-2014/15 ice camp has experienced two weeks of very slow and irregular drift, at times opposite to the wind direction. A net drift of only 6.35 nautical miles (12 km) was towards the Fram Strait. Surface air pressure gradients in our area have been weak throughout the period. High surface air pressure over the Beaufort Sea persisted up until Monday 6 April and later moved slowly towards Siberia. Weak incursions of a low pressure trough between Svalbard and Franz Josef Land towards the Canadian Arctic Islands occurred on Friday 3 April and 6th through 9th April. The wind speed at our location during these incursions increased from about 5 knots to 10-18 knots and directions were variable. The slow ice drift during the past month (72 km) probably reflects the stable weather conditions dominated by large high surface air pressure cells and few incursions of low pressure centers from the North Atlantic.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during weeks 31 and 32; 30 March - 12 April 2015 (heavy red line). Thin red line indicates start of 570 km long seismic transect from the Makarov Basin to the Morris Jesup Rise.

Sea ice dynamics

Having escaped the ice pressure event that erased our camp area, and having been parked for four days at the new location, we saw a new crack had opened about 35 m in front of the hovercraft and widened to about 20 m (Fig. 2). No ice activity has occurred since then. Today, 14 days later, the ice thickness on the refrozen lead is 44 cm.

Fig. 2. A new lead opened 35 m in front of the hovercraft on 31 March and froze over. The pressure ridge which consumed the earlier camp site is seen in the background.

Camp life

Air temperatures during the past two weeks has been nearly constant (-30°C to -35°C) except Saturday 4 April (-28°C), Tuesday 7 April (-25°C) and Sunday 12 April (-19°C). The weather has been gorgeous with the sun shining around the clock except for two days of white-out. However, the ice drift, our science activity, and life in general have been on hold.

In the early hours of Monday 30 April, the hovercraft engine stopped while charging the batteries. It was clearly a fuel issue and we located the problem to be air coming into the fuel line through a leaky primer pump. The pump was beyond repair, but the problem was circumvented by a ball valve from our "nice-to-have" box. To get the final air out of the system, and the engine to fire on all cylinders required considerable effort by the electric starter. On the final stretch, this exceeded our battery capacity. As a result, the hovercraft became immobile. The batteries were flat and no option was available to get them charged - we needed a generator. What was left of battery capacity had to be reserved for communication and all systems requiring power were turned off, even the navigation PC. From now on, navigation was by hand-held GPS.

Two weeks earlier, we had inquired about the possibility of a Norwegian air drop of generators to the ice camp, and now Easter time was here. We had also contacted the Danish Arctic Command in Greenland and received a very positive response, but the earliest flight opportunity available was 23 April. The Russian activity to establish the annual Barneo ice camp near the North Pole was ramping

up and we approached the Expeditionary Centre of the Russian Geographical Society, to explore the possibility of assistance to obtain generators and cost share delivery by an air drop. Generators were acquired in Murmansk, but a series of unfortunate delays implied a tough challenge of transport by helicopter from Barneo to FRAM-2014/15. The distance is 300 nautical miles or halfway from Svalbard to the North Pole. The air drop by the 333rd Squadron of the Norwegian Air Force finally came through on Friday 10 April under optimum weather conditions. The P-3C Orion with chief pilot Johan Hætta and his crew delivered four boxes with parachutes and jettisoned six cartons and a surprise package in the same drop zone used on 23 December 2014 in total darkness. The result is shown in Fig. 3. Use of parachutes from a P-3C Orion is not a regular activity and was of special interest to the parties involved. The operation went like clockwork and all items were received in good order. This included two generators, a new winch, diesel primer pumps, antifreeze, 10 kg of oatmeal, onions, oranges, the favorite cake and newspapers etc. (Fig. 4). The P-3C Orion made a few passes for photo documentation of the camp environment and returned to base. Two hours later, the generator was running and our activities could return to normal. Most importantly, we have regained our mobility and preparedness to safely face any unexpected new ice activity.

Fig. 3. Drop zone (upper panel) and the received cargo assembled in the camp (lower panel).

Safety

Science in a safe way is our priority. Many components contribute to a safe operation in the sea ice environment. To us the ability to communicate with the outside world is by far the most important. For this reason, we have three separate sets of Iridium telephones and HF radio capability via amateur radio. If the need arises, the means and level of support have to be defined from the ice and not from the shore, otherwise any response will not be rooted in reality.

To us, the situation during the last two weeks is considered an unfortunate circumstance which highlighted the recognized need for resupply. Lack of mobility is a serious concern as new ice activity could in no time have taken the situation to a new level. The risk would be to the immobile hovercraft and supplies, but any direct risk to human life quite remote. In the worst case, as pointed out in the previous report, we have the resources, supplies and communication to live comfortably on the ice during the months needed for the ride down to the Fram Strait.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- one autonomous echo sounder buoy reporting to shore via Iridium.

Oceanography: - two Aanderaa current meters at 800 and 2.000 (recovered) m depths.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.

- sun time.

- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work: None.

Three weeks have passed with no seismic reflection measurements, but during that time the camp has only moved less than 30 km in the direction of the Fram Strait. The work space and the hydro-hole are finished at the new site and we are ready to continue the geophysical and geological data collection effort. We would, however, like to see a more continuous and direct drift track before we start firing the air-gun again. Slow ice drift is associated with a complicated trajectory, tracing out nested swirls of a few hundred meter radius, with essentially nil net southeast motion.

Sea ice activity presents a certain amount of risk to all long term instrument deployments. We have earlier (late November) lost the acoustic Doppler current meter (ADCP), and two weeks ago the thermistor string to ice activity. To be safe, we decided to recover the current meter suspended for 7 months below the ice, mostly at 2.000 m depth. This job was done in three steps, where we first man hauled 1 km per day for two days. The last task was making a hole in the 1.5 m thick ice and successfully recovering the instrument (Fig. 4). The second current meter is only a few meters from a pressure ridge and the Kevlar line has been deflected by underthrust ice. The recovery job will be a major effort and put off until it gets warmer.

The disruption incurred by the ice activity and subsequent two week power problem caused a four day loss of data for the radiation flux instruments and the weather station.

Fig. 4. Recovering the current meter by hauling up the 2 km of Kevlar line (upper left), making a hole in the ice (lower left) and the final recovery (right) in pleasant -30° C.

Wild life

There has been no sign of animal life in our neighborhood during the two weeks.

Acknowledgement

We thank the 333rd Squadron of the Norwegian Air Force, the crew of the P-3C Orion and other support personnel for once again providing much needed supplies to our remote location. The positive attitude and the effort of our Russian colleagues at Barneo and Pole Position Logistics to provide assistance, are much appreciated.

Despite the cold and flat batteries, life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 30 March

Position: 85° 19.2' N, 37° 15' W, temperature -32° C, air pressure 1025 hPa, wind 4 knots from the ENE. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the SE. The engine stopped just after midnight while charging batteries. Got it going by bleeding fuel filters. This happened several times in a row. Started searching for the fault. Unrestricted flow in the fuel line, but diesel is dripping from the primer pump. When the engine is running, air is sucked into system via this route. Found a ball valve in my junk box with the right threads and put the valve between the block and the primer pump. Purged air out of the system using a separate 12 volt pump and closed the valve. Had the engine running on a couple of cylinders, but on the home stretch the battery capacity was exhausted. From now on we had no ability to charge our batteries. Closed down all systems, including the navigation PC - will obtain position information from a handheld GPS for the time being. Power to internet switched on as needed. The 24 volt hot water circulation pump was put on a separate 12 volt battery. Informed NERSC and John K. Hall and requested a reminder to FOH to consider an air drop of generators. Also sent an e-mail to the Danish Arctic Command inquiring about flight opportunities.

Tuesday 31 March

Position: 85° 18.8' N, 37° 13' W.

All instruments turned off to save power. Moved the weather station and the radiation flux instruments at the new camp site. The fan on the radiation flux sensor will not have power until our generator problem is sorted out. Audun marked the N-direction on the ice floe and determined the azimuth of the weather station to be N354°E. Audun also prepared recovery of the current meter at 2.000 m depth and pulled up the first 100 m. Made another search for the thermistor string with negative result. Moved 100 liter Jet-A-1 from the old camp site to the hovercraft to be used for heating. We received a very positive response for the Danish Arctic Command, but unfortunately no flight opportunities before 23 April. As we still have no response from the Norwegian Air Force, we sent a letter to the Expedition Office of the Russian Geographical Society, Moscow, asking them to consider the possibility of assisting us with an air drop in connection with a planned IL76 flight out of Murmansk to the Barneo ice station at the North Pole.

Wednesday 01 April

Position: 85° 18.5' N, 37° 11' W, temperature -35° C, beautiful day, calm. All instruments turned off to save power. Pulled the current meter from 1.900 m depth to 800 m below the ice. Checked radiation flux instruments and removed ice from the sensor cupola. Check the internet now and then for messages.

Thursday 02 April

Position: 85° 18.4' N, 37° 11' W, temperature -30° C, wind 15 knots from the NW. White-out all day. Low pressure system over Svalbard is moving slowly eastward. Ilyushin IL-76

flight is postponed until Saturday/Sunday. All hovercraft power systems turned off except the hot water circulation pump.

Friday 03 April

Position: 85° 18.3' N, 37° 04' W, temperature -27° C, wind 10 knots from the S. All power systems in the hovercraft turned off except the hot water circulation pump. Pulled up the current meter from 800 m depth to 30 m below the ice. Made waffles for the first time on this trip.

Saturday 04 April

Position: 85° 18.0' N, 37° 00' W, temperature -28° C, wind 5 knots from the NE. All instruments turned off to save power. Started on the new hydro-hole - ice thickness is 1.7 m. Drilled 9 holes down to 1.5 m depth and removed ice blocks down to 1 m depth. Ice thickness at the current meter site is 1.5 m. Drilled 14 holes ($\phi=10$ cm) down to 1.3 m - need about 10 more holes. Checked radiation flux instruments and cleaned cupolas with pure alcohol to remove thin ice layer. IL-76 flight delayed

Sunday 05 April

Position: 85° 17.7' N, 36° 57' W, temperature -32° C, wind 5 knots from the NW. All instruments turned off to save power. Checked battery status. The battery for the engine is 17 volts instead of 28. Service battery for all instruments is 23 volts instead of 28. Have four separate 12 volt batteries measuring 11.5 - 12.3 volts. Completed drilling of the periphery of the hole to recover the current meter and removed the upper 0.8 m of the ice thickness. IL76 flight and air drop delayed.

Monday 06 April

Position: 85° 17.5' N, 36° 57' W, temperature -30° C, wind 10 knots from the NE. All instruments turned off to save power. Continued removing ice at the current meter site and broke through, but slush prevented us from seeing the ice bridges remaining at the bottom the hole - had to give up for the time being. Started putting up the new work space - finished the walls on three sides.

Tuesday 07 April

Position: 85° 17.5' N, 37° 02' W, temperature -25° C, wind 15 knots from the SW. We received 5 cm of snow and white-out all day. All instruments turned off to save power. Got e-mail from the Norwegian Defense Operations Headquarter offering a resupply mission on 10 April, or alternatively four days later by P-3C Orion. Two generators and replacement winch ordered. Checked the radiation flux instrument and removed snow from the IR sensor (up).

Wednesday 08 April

Position: 85° 17.4' N, 36° 56' W, temperature -30° C, wind 18 knots from the W. All instruments turned off to save power. Put up the work tent - it is supported by a wooden frame as we have no compressed air at the moment. Successfully recovered the current meter. The generators and winch, along with other minor items

were packed, ready for air drop, by the Defense Supply Squadron at Gardermoen.

Thursday 09 April

Position: 85° 17.9' N, 36° 19' W, temperature -32° C, wind 5 knots from the NW. All instruments turned off to save power. Moved the Kevlar drum into the work tent. Rolled up 1000 m of Kevlar line and brought it back to the new camp. Received information that everything was ready for the planned air drop.

Friday 10 April

Position: 85° 17.4' N, 36° 02' W, temperature -32° C, wind 3 knots from the SW. All instruments turned off to save power. Marked a 300 m long drop zone on the remaining part of the floe which we occupied up until end of November 2014. The P-3C Orion overhead at 1620 hours. Dropped four parachutes with generators and winch and then 6 cartons by free fall. The drop was rounded off by a photo pass and ended by 1800 hours. Everything was received in good order. Collected all air dropped items, unpacked and started one generator for charging the hovercraft batteries.

Saturday 11 April

Position: 85° 16.9' N, 36° 07' W, temperature -32° C, wind 7 knots from the NW. Restarted navigation data logging. The Honda 20i generator is run every three hours for 30 minutes and starts willingly in the low temperature. Recovered all markings from the drop zone. Replaced the faulty primer pump in the diesel line of the hovercraft engine. Continued work on getting the work space ready.

Sunday 12 April

Position: 85° 16.4' N, 36° 11' W, temperature -19° C, wind 4 knots from the NW. One centimeter of new snow during the night. Ice drift zero. Started the engine - waited until today since it has not been run for nearly two weeks and temperatures have been below -30° C. We are mobile again. Continued work getting the work space ready

The thirty-third week of ice drift (13 - 19 April 2015)

Ice drift

Week 33 of ice drift was a period of no motion followed by a period of unusually fast drift. The ice in the region of the camp moved only a few tens of meters between Sunday 12 April and the morning of Wednesday 15 April (Fig. 1), while the drift during the rest of the week was 37 nautical miles (68 km). The maximum speed was 0.8 knot. The driving force was a low pressure system that moved across Greenland from south to north in twelve hours on Wednesday 15 April and became stationary near the North Pole for the rest of the week (Fig. 2). Winds were over 20 knots from Saturday morning and 30-40 knots on Sunday with gusts to over 50 knots.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 33, 13 - 20 April 2015 (heavy red line). Thin red line indicates start of 570 km long seismic transect from the Makarov Basin to the Morris Jesup Spur

Fig. 2. Low pressure activity during week 33 ending with a stationary center at the North Pole for many days. Winds associated with a low pressure system are parallel to the contours of equal pressure, anticlockwise with respect to the center and pointing slightly inwards.

Sea ice dynamics

No ice activity has been observed during the week in spite of wind speeds of 30-40 knots with gusts to over 50 knots during the weekend.

Camp life

The week has been mild with air temperatures in the range -23°C to -12°C . The arrival of the low pressure cell on Wednesday brought a warm spell where the temperatures for six hours were as high as -4°C . We devoted our time during the first part of the week to maintenance as the sea ice was not moving at all until Wednesday afternoon (Fig. 1b). The weather forecast told us about the arriving low pressure cell and immediate prospects of ice drift. It was time for the final breakthrough in the hydro-hole, to resume the seismic reflection measurements. The access hole in the ice is done by drilling many holes with a 10 cm diameter auger and then cutting out ice blocks with a chain saw. As one gets deeper, the task gets more tedious (Fig. 4). It is desirable to make the remaining bottom layer only 10-15 cm thick and in the end cut through along the periphery as much as possible while the water level is rising in the hole.

Fig. 4. Making the hydro-hole. Ice thickness 1.8 m.

The high winds associated with the low pressure cell started in the early hours of Saturday and remained steady over 30 knots with blowing snow (Fig. 5). We cleared snow from inside the work space once on Saturday, but gave up any further upkeep until the weather improved.

Fig. 5. A day with blowing snow

The visit in excellent weather by the P-3C Orion of the 333rd Squadron provided an opportunity to get a photographic overview of the ice situation around the camp (Fig. 6). We are surrounded by pressure ridges on three sides and in front of us is a newly refrozen lead. The sharp ridge behind the hovercraft is the collision zone and the leading edge of the smaller ice floe to the right. Our ice floe was over-ridden by the ice floe to the right and about 50 m, including our former camp area, was forced under the floe. As a result, our camp area completely disappeared from the surface and the floe to the right has double the thickness. You could feel what was going on by walking over the floe to the right when the ice activity occurred.

Fig. 6. Overview of the camp area. Photo courtesy of 333rd Squadron, Norwegian Air Force, Chief pilot Johan Erling Hætta.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- one autonomous echo sounder buoy reporting to shore via Iridium.
- seismic data acquisition resumed on Sunday.

Oceanography: - one Aanderaa current meter at 800 m depth.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work None.

The air-gun was lowered into the new hydro-hole on Sunday evening and seismic reflection measurements resumed after a four week break. To build a new camp took over a week and we had no ice drift during the last three weeks to make the seismic operation worthwhile. This is a restriction imposed by our limited fuel reserves.

Fig. 7. Screen shot of seismic monitor with data from the northwest corner of Morris Jesup Spur.

The seismic section shows basement (volcanic+) topography buried and smoothed by sediments. Morris Jesup Rise, along with the northeastern part of the Yermak Plateau north of Svalbard, are

considered to be a result of local excessive volcanism in the time frame 50 to 40 million years ago. They later separated and continued to move apart by continental drift.

Wild life

There has been no sign of animal life in our neighborhood during the week.

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well, and the arrival of new generators is part of that.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 13 April

Position: 85° 16.4' N, 36° 11' W, temperature -21° C, 1007 hPa, wind 4 knots from the NW. No ice drift. Audun went to look for bathymetry buoy # 1 and found it 4.7 km out from camp. Worked on the weekly report.

Tuesday 14 April

Position: 85° 16.4' N, 36° 12' W, temperature -20° C, 1002 hPa, wind 7 knots from the NE. No ice drift. Checked the radiation flux instrument and removed snow from the IR sensor (up). Adapted the foot plate from the old winch to fit the new winch. Audun brought half a drum of Jet-A-1 to camp. We also uncovered the sediment corers stored at the old camp. Our reserve of diesel is about 2.000 liters plus about 950 liters of Jet-A-1 for heating.

Wednesday 15 April

Position: 85° 16.8' N, 36° 13' W, temperature -17° C, wind 10 knots from the NE. Ice drift 0.1 knots to the NE. We received 3 cm of snow during the night. White-out all day. We had a warm spell in the late evening and early morning of the next day when the temperature reached -4° C. Checked radiation flux instruments and removed snow from the IR (up) sensor. Discovered a leak in the radiator. After checking and consultation with Griffon Hoverworks, it was determined to be a leaking gasket between two sections of the radiator, rather than frost damage to the cooling ribs. Put in a bar to better distribute the force from the bolts which are at 5 cm spacing. Prepared the camp for the coming high winds. Had the generator running most of the day to get hot water for a shower.

Thursday 16 April

Position: 85° 20.1' N, 37° 13' W, temperature -12° C, air pressure 988 hPa, wind 5 knots from the NW. White-out all day. Ice drift 0.5 knot towards NW. We have moved 6.5 nautical miles to the NW during the night. Checked the radiation flux instruments and removed snow from the IR (up) sensor. A warm spell is here and we worked all day removing ~2 cm thick layer of ice from the outer walls of the flotation tanks inside the cabin. Refilled some antifreeze and the radiator leak seem to be contained. We are running the Honda generator during the day and the main engine during the night for charging batteries.

Friday 17 April

Position: 85° 19.7' N, 35° 54' W, temperature -23° C, pressure 994 hPa, wind 13 knots from the SW. Ice drift 0.5 knot towards E. Worked on the hydro-hole to get the final break through at the bottom. The ice thickness is 1.8 m. Also repaired the hydrophone cable - the first 6 m of wire was broken in several places and is not fit for the low temperature. The 333rd Squadron has kindly made video footage of the FRAM-2014/15 camp area available to John K. Hall.

Saturday 18 April

Position: 85° 20.9' N, 33° 35' W, temperature -20° C, air pressure 995 hPa, wind 22 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.4 knot towards E. The low pressure has arrived and we have a snow storm - winds were gusting to 35-40 knots during the day. Cleared the work space for snow and tried to get seismic shooting going. The room was soon covered with a layer of snow inside, and in the end we gave up, and will continue the work when the wind is down. Heating inside the hovercraft cabin suddenly stopped and the temperature inside went below +10° C. Supply from the day tank must be clogged. Rigged a 20 liter diesel container inside until the weather is improved for outside work on the day tank.

Sunday 19 April

Position: 85° 21.2' N, 30° 14' W, temperature -15° C, air pressure 993 hPa, wind 30-45 knots from the NW. Gusts to over 50 knots during the night. Ice drift 0.8 knot due E. The wind came down to 20-25 knots at noon. Started seismic shooting at 2200 hours.

The thirty-fourth week of ice drift (20 - 26 April 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved 53 nautical miles (98.5 km) during week 34 (Fig. 1). Steady 20-30 knot winds from the west were generated by a region of low surface air pressure centered at the North Pole up until Wednesday 22 April. Continued westerly winds were subsequently produced by a strong high pressure cell over the Canadian Arctic Islands for the remainder of the week (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1a. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 34, 20 - 27 April 2015 (heavy red line). Thin red line indicates start of 570 km long seismic transect from the Makarov Basin to the Morris Jesup Rise.

21 April 0000 GMT 2015

25 April 0000 GMT 2015

Fig. 2. Main surface air pressure states during week 34 giving steady winds from the west at our location north of Greenland.

Sea ice dynamics

No ice activity has been observed during the week in spite of the high winds.

Camp life

Air temperatures were around -20°C during the first part of the week, while under the influence of the low pressure centered at the North Pole. The high surface air pressure over the Canadian Arctic during the rest of the week brought in air about 5 degrees warmer. This was a major change from the cold at the beginning of the month and outdoor work got easier in many ways. Our hydro-hole no longer freezes up. Low clouds and white-out conditions have persisted throughout the week along with the high winds, but the effect of the sun is getting stronger as soon as it clears a bit.

This week has been busy and scientifically rewarding. Undersea features with major changes in water depth always present new opportunities. We use the camera sled to follow what the bottom looks like and what life forms exist. With the seismic data we image the sub-bottom layering down to at least 1.5 km below the seabed. The video of life at the bottom provides interesting entertainment. In the sequences from the last run, one starfish after another (6) came out of nowhere and went for a certain point on the Kevlar line, tried to embrace it and then left. In a previous run a big fish (*Lycodes Frigidus?*) was trying to bite off the line.

Blowing snow is a consequence of high winds and a matter of constant concern. Snow drifts up to two meters deep, ten meters wide and several tens of meters in length accumulated over the weeks have given us problems several times in the past. Now, with the increasing effect of the sun, there is

less dry snow to move and drifts are small. We keep a free passage around the skirt of the hovercraft in case the need arises to leave the site on a short notice.

We store our food in aluminum boxes (Zarges) and wooden crates on the ice in the camp area. They are exposed to the sun which is getting higher and is with us day and night. For this reason, we are starting to make a snow and ice shelter for our frozen food.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- one autonomous echo sounder buoy reporting to shore via Iridium.
- single channel seismic reflection measurements, 98 km.

Oceanography: - one Aanderaa current meter at 800 m depth.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.
- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work:

- short sediment cores, 35-55 cm long, from water depths of 1160 to 1750 m.
- 5 camera sled deployments in water depths of 1080 to 1650 m.

Morris Jesup Spur - more a pile of sediments than a volcanic construction?

The ridge extending north from the northern coast of Greenland (Fig. 1) was given the name Morris Jesup Rise by American map makers Bruce Heezen and Marie Tharp in 1971. Their map of the Arctic Ocean floor appeared in an issue of the National Geographic Magazine and portrayed the bathymetry in terms of the new paradigm of sea floor spreading. The ridge extends from Kap Morris Jesup, the northernmost point on mainland Greenland, named by Robert Peary after his sponsor, a New York banker. The official name is now Morris Jesup Spur approved in April 2003 by the GEBCO Sub-committee on Undersea Feature Names at the International Hydrographic Bureau in Monaco.

To the best of our knowledge, the Morris Jesup Spur has only been crossed by the U.S. ice station *ARLIS II* in 1965, doing seismic reflection measurements with a sparker source, and visited at its northeastern end by *Polarstern* in 1991. Present bathymetric definition of the feature is mostly in the state of an outline, with the exception of the NE-corner, visited by swath-mapping icebreaker surveys. The water depths along our track are 100 to over 400 m different from what can be inferred from the latest version of the bathymetric map. The top of the spur is portrayed on the map as

relatively flat, and about 10 km wide. Our present position on the map should be about the middle of the flat area, but depths from the seismic section indicate we are still on the NW-flank (Fig. 3).

Most surprising is the presence of more than 1.5 sec. (~1.5 km) of sediments. We have only observed possible knolls of volcanic basement buried by sediments in the far NW. For the rest of the track, basement is not detected and is covered by more than 1.5 km of sediments. We do, however expect to see a narrow basement ridge before a precipitous increase in water depth to more than 3.000 m about 25 km to the east of our present position. The observed sediment thickness has several implications: 1) the amount of volcanic material associated with Morris Jesup Spur may be far less than hitherto considered; 2) where did all the sediments come from? and; 3) what hydrodynamic conditions induced sediment deposition in the form of a spur? The upper 0.8 sec of the section appears as a drape, evidence of current-controlled deposition is absent and only a few very minor sub-marine channel features can be seen. Vertical stacks of diffractions in a few places suggest the entire sediment section has been cut by relatively recent faults.

Fig. 3. Screen shot of seismic monitor with data from the northwest flank of the main Morris Jesup Spur showing layered sediments below the seabed down to at least the level of the multiple reflection.

Life on the seabed

We have deployed the camera sled at five locations in water depths from 1080 to 1650 m. In two of the deployments on the muddy slope, fish come into the field of view (Fig. 4). In one case, the fish appears to be a *Lycodes frigidus* species as also encountered at several sites on Lomonosov Ridge. In the other case two fishes swimming together have tentatively been identified as *Gaidropsarus argentatus* (courtesy of J. Schou Christensen, Univ. of Tromsø). A video clip of the latter is attached to this report.

Fig. 4. Fish imaged by the bottom camera sled on Morris Jesup Spur

Wild life

There has been no sign of animal life in our neighborhood during the week.

The spring is here and life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 20 April

Position: 85° 14.5' N, 27° 25' W, temperature -22° C, 1009 hPa, wind 26 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.4 knot towards E. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun changed memory card and battery on the radiation flux instrument. Battery was 12.2 volts, but only data for 21-24 March was on the card. The stoves in the cabin went out before noon, and the temperature fell to below +10°. The problem was a valve in the primer pump. Had to improvise a temporary solution with a 20 liter diesel tank inside.

Tuesday 21 April

Position: 85° 12.5' N, 26° 10' W, temperature -19° C, 1010 hPa, wind 25-30 knot knots from the SW. Ice drift 0.5 knot towards E. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Recovered one short sediment core in 1.340 m water depth and made one camera sled deployment in 1.430 m water depth. Observed two large fishes in the video from the seabed.

Wednesday 22 April

Position: 85° 07.8' N, 24° 22' W, temperature -22° C, 1016 hPa, wind 18 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.4 knots to the ESE. White-out all day. Shooting seismic reflection measurements. Camera sled at the bottom 1845-2130 hours. Side drag in the Kevlar line during the fast drift caused the sled to lift off bottom.

Thursday 23 April

Position: 85° 00.5' N, 23° 32' W, temperature -20° C, air pressure 1029 hPa, wind 24 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.4 knot towards the SE. Shooting seismic reflection measurements all day. Recovered two short sediment cores in 1.160 and 1.700 m water depth, respectively. The camera sled on the bottom 1415-1700 hours.

Friday 24 April

Position: 84° 52.3' N, 22° 26' W, temperature -14° C, pressure 1039 hPa, wind 23 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.4 knot towards ESE. Shooting seismic reflection all day.

Recovered one short sediment core from 1.750 m water depth. Moved the radiation flux-instrument mast 20 m towards the weather station because the large snow drift behind our work space was approaching the site. The weather has improved slightly so Audun removed the outside day tank for heating fuel for inspection. The fuel outlet had iced up. Cleaned the tank and we were back to normal.

Saturday 25 April

Position: 84° 48.8' N, 21° 42' W, temperature -15° C, air pressure 1040 hPa, wind 28 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.4 knot towards SE. shooting seismic reflection all day. One short sediment core recovered from 1.630 m water depth. The camera sled on the bottom from 1730 to 2030 hours. Put an eight kilogram weight on the Kevlar to weigh it down and prevent the sled from lifting off the bottom. One bluish fish observed.

Sunday 26 April

Position: 84° 42.7' N, 20° 43' W, , temperature -13° C, air pressure 1035 hPa, wind 22 knots from the W. White-out all day. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun remeasured North reference directions. The hovercraft is pointing in the direction of N241°E. Azimuth of North-direction for the weather station and the radiation flux instrument is now 013°. The camera sled deployed in 1000 m water depth. Audun visited bathymetry buoy #1 about 1.7 km out. Only minor evidence of recent ice activity near the site. Air-gun was leaking and serviced.

The thirty-fifth week of ice drift (27 April - 03 May 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved 17 nautical miles (32 km) during week 35 (Fig. 1). A large cell of high surface air pressure positioned over North Greenland and the Canadian Arctic Islands dominated until Friday May 1st and winds at our location were 8-14 knot from the NW. The high pressure later moved into the Beaufort Sea and winds were down to 4-6 knots. The ice drift was 0.1 knot for the most part. We have had complete cloud cover all week and white-out conditions.

Fig. 1a. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 35, 27 April - 03 May 2015 (heavy red line). Thin red line indicates start of 570 km long seismic transect from the Makarov Basin to the Morris Jesup Spur.

Sea ice dynamics

No ice activity has been observed during the week.

Camp life

Drifting over Morris Jesup Spur during the last two weeks has been a bonanza in terms of science opportunities. With the new generator received by the air drop on April 10th, we were back to normal data acquisition capacity and ready for the task. Our camp life during these weeks has been dictated by what action needs to be taken from what we infer from the images emerging from the seismic data acquisition. The reward has been a complete change of our perception of what the spur represents in terms of geology. Rather than being a pile of volcanic rocks related to a "Yermak hot spot" as usually portrayed in the scientific literature, its upper crust is probably for the most part sediments which may even have a resource potential. The joy of experiencing unexpected scientific surprises in nature is something one must be part of to understand the full depth of the experience.

With the focus on the sea bed, little note has been taken of the fact that white-out conditions have prevailed throughout the whole week. Complete lack of contrast from an all-white surface made it virtually impossible to walk outside the simplest path without stumbling and falling. We have, however enjoyed warmer air with temperatures in the range -17°C to -9°C . We have also been blessed with weak winds and no blowing snow. Unfortunately, the white-out conditions have prevented us from pursuing the search for the last two autonomous bathymetry buoys.

The target areas of this expedition were the submarine ridges. We have now passed over the last ridge, the Morris Jesup Spur, and will for the remainder of the drift move over deep water ($>3000\text{ m}$ depth) as well as ocean floor considered to be younger than 30 million years. At this time, we have acquired over 1.000 km of single channel seismic data during our drift on the sea ice. Our activities will change constrained by the fact that the length of our remaining Kevlar line is 2.800 m and we also have to restrict our fuel consumption. This means no more seabed work and no more seismic data acquisition. The focus will be more on the water column. Among other issues to be dealt with are rescue of the second current meter at 800 m depth where the site has been deformed by a pressure ridge. We also need to have a second look for the acoustic Doppler current meter we lost during the first major camp break-up last year, as well as the thermistor string lost a month ago.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- one autonomous echo sounder buoy reporting to shore via Iridium.
- single channel seismic reflection measurements, 32 km.

Oceanography: - one Aanderaa current meter at 800 m depth.

- Atmosphere:
- measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.
 - surface infrared skin temperature.
 - sun time.
 - Aanderaa weather station.

Station work:

- 2 short sediment cores, 35 cm long, water depth 810 m.
- 3 camera sled deployments, water depth 810 m.
- 2 dredge deployments.

At the end of this week, we passed 1.000 km of single channel seismic data acquired during the FRAM-2014/15 ice drift. We also completed the 570 km long profile from the Makarov Basin to the Fram Strait. We have operated successfully under challenging conditions with periods of air temperatures down to -43° Celsius. Once we got stable heat on the compressor and learned why the air-gun sometimes goes into auto-fire, the equipment and procedures have performed really well.

Part II: Morris Jesup Spur - more a pile of sediments than a volcanic construction

1. Observations of the spur architecture

We have crossed the Morris Jesup Spur about 100 km north of the shelf-break as portrayed on the latest version of the IBCAO map and about halfway out along the length of the spur (Fig. 1). The spur has a 25 km wide flat top in 810-830 m water depths at the site of our crossing (Figs. 2 and 3). The slope to the northwest is about 7°, but is a precipitous 60° to the southeast (Fig.3).

The seismic data show at least the upper 1 km below the seabed (down to the multiple reflection) to be represented by sediments with a 7° northwest component of dip, which appears uniform across the spur (Figs. 2 and 3). The sediment layers are truncated at the top across the spur and covered by a ~100 m thick sediment drape (Fig. 2). The thickness of the drape does not appear to change from the northwestern slope to the top of the spur. The entire spur is known to be associated with a strong magnetic intensity anomaly, considered to be evidence for the entire spur being a volcanic construction.

2. Observations relevant to the glacial history

The northwest dipping strata that mantle the spur are cut by a razor sharp unconformity across the top of the 25 km wide structure (Fig.2). At the southeastern edge is a 3.5 km wide accumulation which rests on the unconformity, and is overlain by the same drape as the rest of the top of the spur (Fig. 3, lower panel). In other words; the process(es) that formed the unconformity, and the accumulation at the margin, are of the same age. In cross-section the accumulation looks very similar to an end-moraine of a glacier.

3. Observations from the seabed

The video recordings from travel over the seabed show surprises. At the top of the spur, the seabed in the northwestern part is mud with abundant animal tracks, but littered with rock pebbles. In the central part, patches of gravel are abundant, but also patches of a broken up centimeter-thick crust of light colored sediments. Towards the southeast, the bottom is muddy with extensive networks of strings of sediments from burrowing animals. A video clip is attached to this report to provide a visual impression. There also appear to be areas with an abundance of small holes, some isolated cone-shaped sediment mounds and also small cave-like structures (Figs. 4 and 5). The holes are not associated with any indication of where the excavated mass has been disposed.

Concluding remarks

1.

The seismic data acquired during the FRAM-2014/15 ice drift across the central part of the Morris Jesup Spur, and by the German icebreaker Polarstern in 1991 over the northeastern tip, suggest that the structure may consist of two parts; a volcanic northernmost part and a continental southern part (Fig. 1). This also presents an analogy to the structure of the Yermak Plateau north of Svalbard, which was juxtaposed to the spur before about 36 million years ago. The strong magnetic intensity anomaly associated with the southern part of the Morris Jesup Spur may be due to deep-seated intrusions rather than extrusive magmatism. The dip of the sediments at the location of the trajectory of the ice drift station (Figs 1-3) may either be due to uplift in the southeast or be mostly the original dip of the continental margin sequences.

2.

We interpret the accumulation on top of the regional unconformity at the southeastern rim of the spur as an end-moraine deposited by a grounded glacier (Fig. 3, lower panel). This accumulation suggests the unconformity was generated by a grounded ice shelf, rather than the spur being eroded at or near sea level in the past. The grounded ice shelf would probably have been continuous with mainland Greenland since the bathymetry north of the shelf edge shows no known deep incisions. We submit that the case presented here has the potential of being the best documentation of thick glacial ice extending north of the main Greenland ice sheet. The nearly one hundred meter thick drape deposited since the event indicates an age of several million years.

The idea of thick ice shelves extending into the deep Arctic Ocean is a matter of debate. Bottom features on the main ridges and plateaus are due to the activity of deep-draft ice bergs and any continuation with a source in the form of a major glacial ice sheet is unclear.

3.

We have benefitted from discussions with Martin Hovland (retired, Statoil) on the observations of the small scale features on the seabed. Hovland is the author of numerous publications and several books on aspects of seabed micro-morphology and associated life forms. The small sand volcanoes are most likely formed by fluids transporting sand sized material to the surface (Fig.5. lower panel). The small holes and caves (pockmarks) are also formed by escaping fluids where the material is brought into suspension and transported away by the bottom currents. The nature of the fluids may be pore water or gas. However, given the limits of the quality of our seismic data, we observe no

apparent amplitude anomalies in the seismic signal which could indicate the presence of fluids or gas.

Fig. 2. Upper panel: Screen shot of the seismic monitor of data acquired over the northwestern edge of the Morris Jesup Spur.
Lower panel: Screen shot of the multiple reflection showing the detail of the unconformity and the overlying sediment drape.

Fig. 3. Upper panel: Screen shot of the seismic monitor showing data over the southeastern edge of Morris Jesup Spur
Lower panel: Screen shot of multiple reflection showing detail of the sediment accumulation above the unconformity at the southeastern edge of the spur.

Fig. 4. Bottom photos showing examples of holes in the seabed. Note the lack of expression of where the removed sediments have been deposited.

Fig. 5. Upper panel: Bottom photo showing a sand volcano and adjacent caves in the seabed sediments.
 Lower panel: Conceptual view of the process forming a sand volcano. Illustration courtesy of Martin Hovland.

Wild life

Still no sign of animal life in our neighborhood so far this spring.

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 27 April

Position: 84° 39.1' N, 20° 30' W, temperature -11° C, 1039 hPa, wind 12 knots from the N. White-out. Ice drift 0.0. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Audun built an enclosure of ice blocks to protect the frozen food from the sun. Moved in most of the frozen stuff. Checked the radiation flux instrument - everything OK.

Tuesday 28 April

Position: 84° 38.5' N, 20° 27' W, temperature -14° C, 1035 hPa, wind 8 knots from the NNW. White-out. Ice drift 0.0 knots. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Had the generator running all day to get hot water for a shower and washing clothes. Put down the 50 kHz and 200 kHz transducer to look for scattering layers in the upper 2-300 m of the water column. Saw a pronounced layer at about 50 m depth.

Wednesday 29 April

Position: 84° 36.7' N, 20° 14' W, temperature -14° C, 1030 hPa, wind 13 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.1 knots to the SE. White-out all day. Shooting seismic reflection measurements all day. Recovered a short sediment core. Camera sled at the bottom 1230-1530 hours. Observed six fishes and small holes which may have been formed by venting of fluids. Also in places broken pieces of crust of light-colored sediment. Deployed the dredge for two hours, but returned empty. Made screen shot of 50/200 kHz echo sounder every six hours.

Thursday 30 April

Position: 84° 32.2' N, 19° 54' W, temperature -17° C, air pressure 1030 hPa, wind 14 knots from the NW. White-out all day. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards the SE. Shooting seismic reflection measurements all day. Dredge on the bottom 0340-1300 hours - returned only small angular fragment of lightly metamorphosed shist. Camera sled on the bottom from 1400 to 1840 hours. Saw small sand volcano adjacent to opening of two orifices in the bottom. Pumped fuel from the only bladder in camp to the rear tank which became 3/4 full.

Friday 01 May

Position: 84° 30.3' N, 19° 53' W, temperature -11° C, pressure 1027 hPa, wind 4 knots from the NE. White-out all day. Ice drift 0.0 knot. Continue shooting seismic reflection. Recovered a short sediment core from 820 m depth at the SE edge of the top of the spur. Reorganized our stock of eggs. Those that were closest to the outer wall in the flotation tank had been frozen and were cracked and had to be disposed of. About 120 out of 400 eggs left.

Saturday 02 May

Position: 84° 29.0' N, 19° 46' W, temperature -9° C, air pressure 1026 hPa, wind 6 knots from the NE. White-out all day. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards SE. Continue shooting seismic reflection.

Sunday 03 May

Position: 84° 42.7' N, 20° 43' W, temperature -13° C, air pressure 1035 hPa, wind 22 knots from the W. White-out all day, but the sun became visible at 1700 hours. Shooting seismic reflection all day. Deployed the dredge in 1400 m water depth over the southeastern edge of the spur. When recovered six hours later, the first few hundred meters of Kevlar line near the dredge was a mess and the dredge was empty. With this our geological sampling program on FRAM-2014/15 came to an end. Audun visited bathymetry buoy #1 about 1.7 km out. Only minor evidence of recent ice activity near the site. The air-gun was leaking. It was recovered and serviced.

The thirty-sixth week of ice drift (04 - 10 May 2015)

- a snow bunting passed through camp 10 May -

Ice drift

The ice camp moved 15 nautical miles (28 km) during week 36 (Fig. 1). Gradients in surface air pressure have been weak throughout the week over large parts of the Arctic Ocean. The higher pressure has been over North Greenland and the Canadian Arctic islands. Winds have been out of the west at our location with 14-17 knots on Monday and Tuesday and less than 8 knots the rest of the week. We have had sun from a clear or partly cloudy sky all week except Friday and Sunday.

Fig. 1a. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 36, 04 - 10 May 2015 (heavy red line).

Sea ice dynamics

No ice activity has been observed in our neighborhood during the week. However, weak, but persistent westerly winds over the past two weeks have created a large scale fracture pattern north of Greenland upstream of the main outflow of ice from the Arctic Ocean (Fig. 2). A major shear zone is formed at the boundary between the moving sea ice and the land fast ice along the coast of Northeast Greenland. The continued drift of the FRAM-2014/15 ice camp will be largely parallel to this shear zone. At the latitude (81° 30' N) of Station Nord (Fig. 2), the outflow of ice accelerates, the sea ice cover gets fragmented and large leads open up between floes.

Fig. 2. Satellite image of the ice situation and fracture patterns off northeast of Greenland. Image courtesy of www.woksat.info.

Camp life

In our minds, we are on the home stretch, having passed Morris Jesup Spur and all our target areas. We feel the pressure is off in the sense that our days are no longer a chase, run by the science

opportunities you could read from the seabed at the same time as seismic data acquisition was kept up. To keep the air-gun going required attention which did not allow you to sleep more than 1.5 hours at a time, for periods of over a month. It took some resolve to keep it up at temperatures down to -40°C during the dark season. But the data is now stored on the computer disk and the pressure is off.

The air temperatures during the week have varied very little (-14°C to -18°C) and the sun has been shining all day except for white-out conditions on Friday and Sunday. The sea ice in the area is approaching the entrance to the Fram Strait (Fig. 2) and ice activity will increase down-stream. So far winds have been weak and the ice drift slow during the past two weeks. To, prepare for a new reality, we have removed the connection between the hovercraft and the work space and closed the opening. The work space over the hydro-hole is now a stand-alone building. Next on the logistics agenda is to move equipment and fuel still remaining near the old camp site over to where we are now. Otherwise, possible development of new intervening leads and shear zones may easily displace the cargo many hundreds of meters, and ice rubble make it nearly inaccessible. For now, we have to clear a saddle point in a pressure ridge for the hovercraft to pass and get to the old site.

We have used the good weather to search for the two remaining bathymetry buoys (#4 and #5) not yet accounted for (Fig. 3). On Saturday, Audun made a ski trip out to 5 km away from the camp, but could not locate any of them. Earlier in the week, new batteries were connected to buoy # 1, also 4.7 km out from camp.

The air drop by the 333rd Squadron was essential to get us back to being useful. With the new generator (number five on this expedition), end of seismic data acquisition, and the warmer weather, we feel we have regained control over our fuel situation. Our revised consumption should bring us safely through wherever the drift ends.

Fig. 3. Left: Audun searching with binoculars for the bathymetry buoys.
Right: Each buoy site is marked by a 3 m long plastic pipe, but the buoy itself has a very low profile

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- one autonomous echo sounder buoy reporting to shore via Iridium.

Oceanography: - one Aanderaa current meter at 800 m depth.

- 50 kHz and 200 kHz echo sounders to check scattering layers.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work: - one camera deployment down to 30 meter depth

An essential part of doing science is curiosity. Imaging the seabed and the sub-bottom layers using an acoustic sound source (8 - 120 Hz) has been a major task during the past eight months. When this ended, we turn our attention to acoustic images of the water column out of pure curiosity using the following tools:

- i) a sparker source to image acoustic impedance contrasts mainly caused by water temperature differences, and
- ii) high frequency echo sounders (50 and 200 kHz) to map the scattering layer in the upper few hundred meters. The scattering layer is due to biological activity.

An autonomous seismic buoy using a sparker source was developed as part of an IPY project and has been used in test runs on Yermak Plateau with good results. When mobilized here, we encountered a short circuit in the sparker energy source and have not been able to resolve it by now, but continue to pursue the issue.

Echo sounders use high frequencies which gives high vertical resolution. The energy transmitted by an echo sounder will be reflected from any obstacle in the water column before it hits the seabed where it is reflected back as a strong return and tells us what the water depth is. The energy reflected back from any target in the water column is dependent on size and acoustic impedance (velocity times density) contrast. At 200 kHz, the wave length is 7.5 millimeter and a tiny bit of energy will be reflected back from life forms down to a few millimeters in size. If there are many small individuals per unit volume, we may detect the reflected or back scattered energy as a tiny spot on the screen. If there are clouds or patches occurring, we see many spots over a depth interval that form a layer of some thickness - hence the name "scattering layer". In the open ocean, the scattering layer is found at depths between 200 and 600 m depth during the day. At night it rises to near the surface and diffuses. The scattering layer is attributed to zooplankton which descend to depths during the morning to escape their predators during the day. At night the plankton rises to the

surface to feed in the nutrient rich water. In the central Arctic Ocean, the scattering layer was probably first detected from ice station T-3 in the summer of 1963 using a 12 kHz echo sounder. It was found to occur between 50 and 200 m depth. It showed no diurnal depth variation, but rather an annual variation and was only present during the summer months and early fall; June through October.

Research in the marginal ice zone north of Svalbard has documented that the scattering layer, as detected by a 200 kHz echo sounder, is mainly due to abundance of species of the copepod *Calanus* - a zooplankton up to five millimeters in size. The signal from the 50 kHz responds to larger targets such as Arctic cod.

We use a Furuno FCV-620 dual-frequency (50 and 200 kHz) echo sounder. Our logging system is for the detected bottom echo only and not for the entire data trace from the water column. To record the echoes in the water column, we photograph the echo sounder screen at 6 hour intervals. In Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 are shown some sample records. At 200 kHz, the concentration of scatterers varies little around 50 m depth. The 50 kHz signal, on the other hand, shows large irregular variations both during the day and at night. Particularly large co-occurring concentrations were observed in the evening of May 8th (Fig. 6).

Our only means of in situ documentation is to attempt video recording at the depth of maximum concentration. We deployed the GoPro camera and a light source down to 30 m depth. Individual plankton can be seen passing in and out of the field of view, but insufficiently resolved. This video approach may only be useful for the larger targets detected by the 50 kHz signal.

Fig. 4. Records of the scattering layer as detected by the 200 kHz echo sounder.

Fig. 5. Records of the scattering layer detected by the 50 kHz echo sounder.

Fig. 6. Echo sounder record from an event of extremely strong returns from the upper 150 m of the water column.

Fig. 7. Foot prints of the polar fox which passed by our camp.

Wild life

Audun spotted tracks of a polar fox which had inspected our camp from the nearest pressure ridge. The fox used the occasion to leave droppings which have been collected and will be turned over to relevant experts who can read the information.

On Sunday May 10th we welcomed a snow bunting which touched down at 1532 hours on the hovercraft and later left for an unknown destination.

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 04 May

Position: 84° 23.3' N, 19° 15' W, temperature -18° C, 1025 hPa, wind 17 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.2 towards SE. At 1600 hours, our seismic program had come to the end. Stopped data acquisition and pulled the air-gun out of the water - last field file is # 40370. Take screen shots of the 50/200 kHz echo sounder at least at local noon and local midnight.

Tuesday 05 May

Position: 84° 18.3' N, 18° 42' W, temperature -17° C, 1021 hPa, wind 14 knots from the NW.
A clear day. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards SE. Audun restarted data logger on the radiation flux instrument. He also made a ski trip with batteries to bathymetry buoy # 1 4.7 km out from our camp, but was missing a tool to complete the job.

Wednesday 06 May

Position: 84° 13.2' N, 18° 09' W, temperature -15° C, 1024 hPa, wind 6 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.2 knot to the SE. Sunshine from a clear sky all day. Audun went back to the site of buoy #1 and connected up the batteries. The old ones measured 5.5 V and 7.2 V, respectively. Removed the heat enclosure from the compressor and tidied up. Moved the sparker buoy into the work tent. Audun rechecked the radiation flux data logger and rebooted the program. Making pictures of the scattering layer.

Thursday 07 May

Position: 84° 11.8' N, 17° 59' W, temperature -16° C, air pressure 1029 hPa, wind 2 knots from the W. White-out from 0900 hours. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the SE. Cleared the workspace from its connection to the hovercraft - only generator power line is attached now. Connected up the sparker buoy.

Friday 08 May

Position: 84° 11.3' N, 17° 59' W, temperature -14° C, pressure 1032 hPa, wind 6 knots from the SSE. Sun from a clear sky all day. Ice drift 0.0 knot. Deployed the hydrophone for the sparker buoy. Got the control electronics checked out OK, but the sparker energy source kept blowing a fuse and the problem was not found. A more permanent location inside the work space was made for the generator.

Saturday 09 May

Position: 84° 10.9' N, 18° 00' W, temperature -14° C, air pressure 1030 hPa, wind 5 knots from the S. Sunshine from a clear sky all day. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards ESE. Audun

went on skies to search for bathymetry buoys # 4 and # 5, but did not find any. Worked on the sparker buoy to look for shorted connections. Made a frame for mounting the camera and underwater light source in an effort to see if we may be able to get video of the life forms that make up the scattering layer in the upper 150 m below the ice. Made a camera deployment to a weak concentration of scatterers at 30 m depth. A few individuals can be seen passing through the field of view, but the resolution is insufficient. We have to go for the bigger targets sometimes displayed in the results from the 50 kHz echogram.

Sunday 10 May

Position: 84° 10.3' N, 18° 01' W, temperature -15° C, air pressure 1027 hPa, wind 8 knots from the NW. White-out all day. Ice drift 0.0 knot. Audun moved a Jet A-1 drum to camp to be used for heating. The ice house for storage of food was expanded. A snow bunting suddenly touched down on the roof of the hovercraft at 1532 hours. Rather than restitute and stock up on food in our camp, the bird left after just a few minutes.

The FRAM-2014/15 camp as of May 10 2015.

The thirty-seventh week of ice drift (11 - 17 May 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved 8 nautical miles (15 km) during week 37 (Fig. 1). Early in the week, the general state of high air pressure over the Arctic Ocean was intruded by a low pressure cell moving north from the East Siberian Sea (160° E). Winds in our area were weak (3-7 knots) and from the east and southeast. The ice drift was slow and to the northeast - we moved back to where we came from. By mid-week, we came under the influence of a low pressure system moving north from the Laptev Sea which became stationary in the North Pole area. Winds were now from the north at speeds of 13-16 knots which changed the ice drift to the southeast and increased the drift speed to 0.3 knot. Most of the time we have had a full cloud cover and poor visibility with brief intervals of the sun breaking through.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 37, 11 - 17 May 2015 (heavy red line).

Sea ice dynamics

No ice activity has been observed in our neighborhood during the week. A thick cloud cover has prevailed throughout the week and features of the regional ice surface are obscured in satellite images.

Camp life

This week has been devoted to various logistic chores and observations of the scattering layer. Although the air temperatures have been pleasant (-12 °C to -16 °C), the persistent weather conditions, characterized by low clouds with near white-out conditions, is not particularly inspiring. The diffuse light gives low terrain contrast which makes it impossible to drive the hovercraft safely. Moving the remaining equipment and fuel over from the old camp has been postponed. We also want to transfer the remaining diesel fuel from the bladder to empty Jet A-1 drums in order to make all our fuel polar bear safe. We are likely to get visits by polar bears in the near future.

Our drift at the moment is about 66 nautical miles off the coast of Northeast-Greenland and we are not likely to get any closer to shore downstream through the Fram Strait

The FRAM-2014/15 camp on 17 May 2015.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- one autonomous echo sounder buoy reporting to shore via Iridium.

Oceanography: - one Aanderaa current meter at 800 m depth.

- 50 kHz and 200 kHz echo sounders to look for scattering layers in the upper 200 m.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work: - 3 camera deployments to 36, 55 and 36 m depths, respectively.

- One 12 hour time-lapse of 50 kHz and 200 kHz echo sounder display.

We have experimented a bit with how to get information on the scattering layer with what we have. Our challenge is the underwater light sources which are insufficient and often fail. The scattering layer seen on the 200 kHz echogram is present all the time. These echoes are probably caused by the abundance of zooplankton. However the larger life forms, as detected by the 50 kHz signals, are more sporadic. We may be able to capture the larger objects in underwater images.

We have made a 12 hour time-lapse of the scattering layer as displayed on the screen of the echo sounder. The time-lapse runs from 2100 hours to 0900 hours local time (sun time). The file was planned to be attached to this report, but we are unfortunately unable to reduce the file (30 Mb) to a size useful for transmission via Iridium.

To image the life forms in the scattering layer, we lowered the underwater camera down to the level of maximum echo returns and left it for up to 3 hours. The marine life appeared in no way to be attracted by the underwater lights. What was caught in the field of view appeared to be more or less by accident. This is very different from our camera runs on the seabed in the deep ocean where the lights attracted numerous individuals soon after arrival. Some results from the lowering to 55 m depth are shown in Figs. 2 and 3. The relatively poor definition in these images is related to their origin as a video recording and also to the fixed focus of the GoPro camera. The quality can be partly improved by a time-lapse approach. Our scientific background in marine biology is completely missing and we kindly encourage interested individuals to help identify the species in the figures to the extent that the photo quality allows.

Fig. 2. Single pictures from the video showing different life forms at 55 m depth within the scattering layer at local noon 15 May.

Image of the same individual in different positions

Image of the same individual in different positions

Fig. 3. Single pictures from the video showing different life forms at 55 m depth within the scattering layer at local noon 15 May.

We stopped the CTD program over the deep water transect after Lomonosov Ridge due to fuel considerations. The new generator brought relief and the lowered general consumption give reasons to reconsider. To define research objectives, we have benefitted from discussions with S. Rysgaard, Univ. of Aarhus, B. Rudels, Finnish Inst. of Marine Research, and P. Haugan, Univ. of Bergen. A transect off Northeast Greenland with temperature and conductivity (salinity) measurements would:

- i) augment ongoing oceanographic research in the Independence Fjord area by the group from Aarhus University at the new Villum Research Station, and
- ii) contribute to the data base for determining where and how much of the Atlantic Water from the Amundsen and Nansen Basins joins the flow of water which has made the complete polar basin loop.

We will start making CTD casts down to 1000 m depth at least every 10 nautical miles.

The return from the ice

We have learned that it will not be possible to obtain support from the Norwegian Coast Guard vessel *KV Svalbard* for recovery of FRAM-2014/15 at the end of the drift in the Fram Strait. The reason given is time spent in support of other government institutions.

We actively search for other opportunities to recover all equipment and ensure a safe return to shore.

Wild life

We have not made any observations of animal or bird life on the ice during the week.

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 11 May

Position: 84° 10.1' N, 18° 00' W, temperature -12° C, 1024 hPa, wind 3 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.0. Cleared a passage through a pressure ridge for driving to the old camp. Audun revisited the 2014 camp for photo documentation of changes.

Tuesday 12 May

Position: 84° 10.5' N, 18° 02' W, temperature -16° C, 1016 hPa, wind 4 knots from the SE. A clear day before lunch, white-out afterwards. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards NE. New attempt to figure out the problem with the sparker energy source, no success. Lowered the camera to 36 m depth in the scattering layers. No good close-up images of zooplankton. Taking pictures of the echo sounder screen every 6 hours to capture the activity in the scattering layer.

Wednesday 13 May

Position: 84° 10.8' N, 18° 07.4' W, temperature -16° C, 1017 hPa, wind 6 knots from the E. Ice drift 0.1 knots to the NE. Poor visibility all day, but not full white-out conditions. Prepared the hovercraft for a drive by i) clearing snow and ice accumulated between the inner and outer skirt, ii) clearing the decks and iii) remove the snow from behind to form a passage for re-entering our present parking position. Checked the radiation flux instruments and data logger. Received an e-mail from the Danish group operating the new Villum Research Station at Station Nord proposing up-stream CTD casts to supplement their oceanographic work in Independence Fjord.

Thursday 14 May

Position: 84° 11.2' N, 18° 13.5' W, temperature -15° C, air pressure 1018 hPa, wind 7 knots from the NE. White-out. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the NE. Checked the radiation flux instrument. Continued transfer of the seismic log to an Excel-sheet.

Friday 15 May

Position: 84° 11.3' N, 18° 15' W, temperature -15° C, pressure 1014 hPa, wind 11 knots from the N. Poor visibility, but not quite white-out. Ice drift 0.0. Camera down for 2.5 hours at 55 m depth. A number of useful passages of copepods, polar cod and others. Audun attempted a ski trip to look for the missing bathymetry buoys, but aborted due to poor visibility. Continued transfer of the seismic log to an Excel-sheet.

Saturday 16 May

Position: 84° 08.8' N, 18° 07' W, temperature -14° C, air pressure 1015 hPa, wind 17 knots from the N. Poor visibility all day. Ice drift 0.3 knot towards SE. Mounted new lights

on the camera rig. Made tests of time-lapse photography of the echo sounder screen. Continued transfer of the seismic log to an Excel-sheet.

Sunday 17 May

Position: 84° 04.1' N, 17° 20' W, temperature -12° C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 16 knots from the WSW. Ice drift 0.3 knot to the SE. Poor visibility before lunch, improved later. Deployed the camera at 36 meter depth for 2.5 hours, but no good images obtained. Completed transfer of the seismic log to an Excel sheet.

A squid?

The thirty-eighth week of ice drift (18 - 24 May 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp moved 15 nautical miles (28 km) during week 38 (Fig. 1). Winds have been from the northwest for most part of the week except Wednesday (southwest) and Saturday (northeast). The exceptions were due to incursions of low surface air pressure from the Svalbard area. The change in wind direction on Saturday forced the ice to drift to the west for about half a day. Faster ice drift (0.3 knot) at the end of the week was driven by a low pressure system which extended from Svalbard to the North Pole.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 38, 18 - 254 May 2015 (heavy red line).

Sea ice dynamics

No ice activity has been observed in our neighborhood during the week. The satellite image from 23 May in Fig. 2 shows the large scale fracture pattern northeast of Greenland. The main shear zone off the coast is very prominent and extends far to the northwest. The ice flow accelerates dramatically south of the latitude of Station Nord, but the total volume of ice flowing out has a minimum during the early summer (May and June).

Fig. 2 Satellite image from 23 May courtesy of www.woksat.info showing ice distribution and fracture patterns north of Greenland and Svalbard.

Camp life

The loss of several oceanographic instruments, and their stored time series of currents and temperature during the winter, has bothered us a lot. But the cold and the darkness and lack of subsequent ice activity made us wait until the spring to make an all-out search effort. This week has been devoted to a final search for the missing current meter (800 m depth), the acoustic Doppler current profiler (ADCP), and the 300 m long thermistor string. As explained in the Science section below, there is some bad news and some good news.

Temperatures have been between -7 °C and -14 °C this week and for most of the time, we have had beautiful weather. Surface air pressure gradients have been small and winds weak. Working outside is a real pleasure - the kind of weather you would hope for your dream Easter vacation in the mountains. The snow surface is for the most part hard and uneven, with small and large drift deposits. The effect of the sun and incipient melting helps to seal off pores and make hovercraft driving easier. Small snow banks, on either side of the entrance to the hovercraft parking, guide the craft to its exact parking location. The ideal case for an expedition like this would be to enter your target area and be able to carry out your work during the finest moments the beautiful polar desert can offer. The rest of the year, you may go into hibernation surrounded by a maze of data loggers.

We have received a generous offer from the Danish Arctic Command in Greenland for an air drop on May 27, if needed. This could be carried out in connection with their scheduled surveillance flight of their Exclusive Economic Zone. Spare radiator parts on hold in Bergen, can now be available as well as more antifreeze fluid. On April 15, four days after the air drop from the 333rd Squadron, we got a leak between the two radiator sections and our anti freeze supply became rapidly depleted. Temporary repairs stopped the leak and our hope was that this would hold up until the end of the expedition.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- one autonomous echo sounder buoy reporting to shore via Iridium.

Oceanography: - 50 kHz and 200 kHz echo sounders to look for scattering layers.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work: - 3 CTD casts to 1000 m depth.

- One 12 hour time-lapse of 50 kHz and 200 kHz echo sounder displays.

We have resumed making CTD casts as stated in the previous report.

Our approach to the search for the lost equipment has been to drill 15 cm diameter access holes and lower an underwater camera (Fig. 3 and 4). The under-ice light conditions permitted target definition out to 10-15 meter. The ice activity which disrupted the camp and the mooring sites took place in late November. We monitored the subsequent surface expression of ice activity continuously, and made the first under-ice search in the dark 11-12 February. The ADCP site had been hit by under-thrusted ice and the wire most likely sheared off. At the current meter site, we could see the Kevlar line coming out of the underside of the ice at an angle, but deferred recovery because of the cold and the dark. This turned out to be a fatal mistake. Working conditions were better now in late May, but there were no sign of the Kevlar line - it must have been torn off and the line with the current meter at the end was lost.

We then turned to the thermistor string. The mooring site was separated from the camp by a shear zone during the last week of March and displaced ~150 m. A nearby stake to mark the path between the old and the new camp gave us a clue about its location. We had searched for the surface expression of the mooring several times, but with no success. From the first access hole, we could see a faint linear object, and after four holes were made, we had cross-bearings to the nearest half meter (Fig. 4). The thermistor string has 4 months of temperature data recorded for every 10 m depth down to 300 m. Final recovery will be next week. To us, locating the string was a major victory.

Fig. 3. Drilling access holes in search for the thermistor string.

Fig. 4. View from an access hole of the first thermistor in its position just below the underside of the ice.

Wild life

The High Arctic is coming alive. We had visits by the first snow bunting on 10 May, and the second one came on 20 May (Fig. 5). An Ivory gull came over the camp on 18 May and Audun saw another two on a ski trip on 20th May.

Fig. 5 Audun has captured the two snow buntings having a meal together

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 18 May

Position: 84° 01.5' N, 16° 40' W, temperature -8° C, 1014 hPa, wind 3 knots from the SW. Ice drift 0.2 towards SE. Put up a 12 hour time-lapse of the echo sounder screen. Checked the radiation flux instrument. Removed the cover and insulation mats from the hovercraft superstructure, and mobilized the craft for departure. Just after getting off the parking ramp a loud rattling noise was heard. The starboard brace which holds the propeller duct had come loose and the threads of the adjusting eye-bolt had been pulled out. Propeller blades were hitting the duct at the top inside. We had no spares, but could do satisfactory repairs using parts from our unofficial "nice-to-have" collection. We made two trips over to the old camp and moved all equipment and all remaining fuel over to the present camp. The visibility went down so we stayed overnight at the old camp site. We saw an Ivory gull over the camp for the first time this year.

Tuesday 19 May

Position: 83° 58.2' N, 16° 37' W, temperature -14° C, 1016 hPa, wind 15 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.3 knot towards the S. The camera was lowered to 22 m. The field of view was straight down, but did not capture any life in the two hours of recording. Made a CTD cast down to 1000 m depth.

Wednesday 20 May

Position: 83° 52.7' N, 16° 25' W, temperature -11° C, 1021 hPa, wind 11 knots from the SW. Ice drift 0.2 knots to the SE. Beautiful weather all day, but reduced visibility in the late evening. Made a CTD cast down to 1000 m. Audun made a ski trip and recovered bathymetry buoy #1 from 4.3 km out. He also spotted two Ivory gulls on the way. Washed part of the superstructure that had deposits from the stove pipe accumulated through the winter. Also cleaned the deck around the compressor. Snow bunting number two for the season landed near the hovercraft and later inspected the place where our garbage is burnt.

Thursday 21 May

Position: 83° 51.7' N, 16° 14.4' W, temperature -11° C, air pressure 1019 hPa, wind 4 knots from the NW. Clear sky - a beautiful day. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the SE. We loaded the hovercraft and drove over to the current meter mooring. Drilled five holes all together and inspected the underside of the ice with the underwater camera. Much to our surprise, there was no trace of the Kevlar line coming out of the ice. Returned to camp.

Friday 22 May

Position: 83° 50.9' N, 16° 06' W, temperature -7° C, pressure 1019 hPa, wind 5 knots from the NW. Drove over to the current meter site and continued the search. The current meter suspended at 800 m depth is lost. Moved over to the ADCP mooring. Drilled a hole 7 m from the mooring, but did not reach through. Made it through 2 m thick ice 10 m away. Lowered the camera, but no sign of an instrument. This is in a pressure ridge and even if we could spot the

ADCP, we probably would not have been able to recover it. Moved the last fuel back to our camp. We received an e-mail from Danish Arctic Command with a generous offer of an air drop if needed on Wednesday May 27. We gratefully accepted and spare parts were shipped from Bergen to Søndre Strømfjord on the shortest notice. This enables us to get spares for the radiator and extra antifreeze and the temporary repair will no longer be a gamble. An extra four kilos of oatmeal and two kilos of onions were deleted from the list due to import restrictions in Greenland.

Saturday 23 May

Position: 83° 50.0' N, 16° 12' W, temperature -13° C, air pressure 1005 hPa, wind 12 knots from the ESE. A beautiful day. Replaced the full data storage on the weather station. The display on the replacement cartridge is blurred and unreadable. Battery voltage was 7.35 volt. Added two D-cells to get 10.3 volt out. Drove the hovercraft to the location of the displaced thermistor string. The mooring was separated from camp by a shear zone only a meter or two away and displaced over 150 m to the east. From the first hole drilled, we could barely see something with the underwater camera that might be the string. After four holes, we had cross bearings and good photo documentation of an intact string. Recovery will be next week. Our remaining fuel is 1700 liters diesel, 2 drums of Jet A-1, and 1 drum of gasoline.

Sunday 24 May

Position: 83° 47.7' N, 16° 08' W, temperature -12° C, air pressure 1013 hPa, wind 13 knots from the WSW. Ice drift 0.3 knot to the SE. Poor visibility in the morning, but clear sky most of the day. Made a CTD cast down to 1000 m.

The thirty-ninth week of ice drift (25 May - 31 May 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp has only made a southward progress of about 1 nautical mile (2 km) during week 39 (Fig. 1). The true drift was about 6 nautical miles to the southeast and then about 5 nautical miles back to the northwest again. The wind was from the north (10 knots) on Monday 25 May due to a weakening low pressure system in the North Pole area. But for the rest of the week, winds (5-12 knots) were from the east and southeast. Our location was within outliers of the high pressure cell which moved between the Canadian Arctic and the coast of Siberia. The ice drift was to the southeast until Thursday morning when it turned towards the northwest.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 39, 25 - 31 May 2015 (short heavy red line).

Sea ice dynamics

No ice activity has been observed in our neighborhood during the week. The satellite image from 01 June in Fig. 2 shows the large scale fracture pattern northeast of Greenland. The northward ice drift has left a wide lead of open water running along the coast of Northeast Greenland.

Fig. 2 Satellite image from 01 June courtesy of www.woksat.info showing ice distribution and fracture patterns north of Greenland and Svalbard.

Camp life

The net ice drift during week 39 was the lowest of all weeks during our nine months on the ice. We moved 6 nautical miles to the southeast and then 5 miles back in the direction we came from. Since we are on the home stretch, and southward progress captures a lot of our attention, it has not been a good week. The first three days of the week had nice weather and we were occupied by our final recovery of the last thermistor in the string. Overcast and temperatures between -9°C and -3°C dominated the rest of the week. A high point was the air drop offered by the Danish Arctic Command on Friday 29th (Fig. 3). The Challenger jet piloted by Kristian Kjær and his crew dropped a single parachute from 200 feet altitude (65 m). Most importantly, the drop brought us resupply of antifreeze and spare radiator parts. We greatly appreciate the flexible attitude demonstrated by changing the flight schedule to compensate for the late arrival of cargo from Bergen to Kangerlussuaq. In our mind, the air drop is an excellent example of synergies in international cooperation. FRAM-2014/14 is drifting within a completely unexplored part of the Exclusive Economic Zone of Greenland/Denmark collecting geo-scientific data which in general terms are relevant to the resource potential of the region (see our report for week 35). "Rigsfelleskabet" retains at no cost, a copy of all the relevant information acquired during this part of the ice drift. A separate logistic operation to obtain the same information would require a double digit figure in millions of kroner.

The snow cover on the ice is visibly shrinking from the heat of the sun, and the surface is gradually getting glazed. Bluish areas are emerging where the snow cover is thin.

Fig. 3. Air drop from the Danish Air Force Challenger jet.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling: - none.

Oceanography: - 50 kHz and 200 kHz echo sounders to check for scattering layers.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.

- sun time.

- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work: - One CTD cast to 1000 m depth.

- One camera deployment to 22 m and 55 m depths.

A CTD cast is done every 5 nautical miles, so only one was done during the week due to the slow drift.

The last of the autonomous buoys is not reporting useful bathymetry. It will be recovered when the weather conditions (light contrast) permit. Since our Knudsen echo sounder is dead, we are temporarily not collecting bathymetry.

Recovery of instruments suspended from wire connections frozen into the ice is a challenge which may be overcome by many different approaches. It is mostly an exercise in improvisation. The attached video clip shows an example of a classic device made to hook the Kevlar line and pull the thermistor string out through the access hole. To recover the first thermistor just below the underside of the ice is a separate problem. In this case, the thermistor string was suspended from an 8 mm steel wire through the ice. The steel wire was at the center of three bundled plastic pipes (OD=90 mm) filled with ethanol. Based on previous experience, we considered it possible to lift the bundle out of the ice when the time of recovery came. However, the ice pressure had bent the pipe stack within the ice so lifting proved impossible. From a close access hole we managed to pull the steel wire downwards from the underside of the ice to give enough slack to allow the thermistor to become vertical within the access hole. The rest of the job was done by the hovercraft winch. All the gear was recovered without any damage.

Wild life

One and sometimes two snow buntings have been seen in camp every day during the week.

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 25 May

Position: 83° 42.7' N, 15° 48' W, temperature -10° C, 1016 hPa, wind 10 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards SE. Drove the hovercraft out to the site of the thermistor string mooring. Found the top of the mooring under an ice block at the edge of the pressure ridge. Drilled an access hole 40 cm away and hooked on to the string and pulled it up. Got everything up on the ice except thermistor # 1. Drove back to camp for the night.

Tuesday 26 May

Position: 83° 41.1' N, 15° 38' W, temperature -10° C, 1025 hPa, wind 5 knots from the E. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the SE. Went back towards the mooring site, but the hovercraft got stuck on an ice ridge underway. Had to jack the craft up to remove the ice ridge. Came loose, but got stuck two more times in ice rubble and had to use the winch to get out. Drove back to camp in the evening

Wednesday 27 May

Position: 83° 39.7' N, 15° 32' W, temperature -7° C, 1030 hPa, wind 4 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the SE. Made a CTD cast down to 1000 m. Returned to the thermistor site. Got the thermistor positioned vertically in the access hole so we could use the hovercraft winch to pull the Kevlar up and the mooring wire out of the ice. Everything came out with no damage. Drove back to camp. Had a shower in the sauna. The generator had to run all day to get enough water from melting snow.

Thursday 28 May

Position: 83° 39.7' N, 15° 32.5' W, temperature -9° C, air pressure 1025 hPa, wind 6 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.0. Checked the radiation flux instrument. Data logger had stopped and battery voltage 3.7 volt. Changed battery and restarted logger. Deployed the underwater camera into the scattering layer - first at 22 m depth and then at 55 m depth. **Abundant activity, but no good images captured beyond what we already have.**

Friday 29 May

Position: 83° 39.4' N, 15° 31' W, temperature -9° C, pressure 1028 hPa, wind 5 knots from the SE. **Overcast and low light contrast of the ice surface. The Danish 5954 Challenger coastal surveillance plane came overhead at 1545**
Air Force
GMT and
antifreeze
and a
rendered.
dropped a parachute from 60 m height. We received resupply of
and spares for hovercraft radiator, spare swords for the chain saw
battery for one of the laptops. A thank you note was dispatched to the
Danish Arctic Command expressing our appreciation for the service

Saturday 30 May

Position: 83° 41.6' N, 15° 48' W, temperature -5° C, air pressure 1019 hPa, wind 12 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards the NW. Checked the radiation flux instrument. Data logger voltage 12.6 volt. Checked weather station - battery is 10.3 volt.

Sunday 31 May

Position: 83° 43.2' N, 16° 08' W, temperature -5° C, air pressure 1023 hPa, wind 6 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the W. The northwestward drift is very disappointing and the weather forecast suggests this will go on until Tuesday next week.

The FRAM-2014/15 camp on May 29, 2015.

Camp site 8 June 2015

Week forty of ice drift (01 - 07 June 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp drifted 35 nautical miles (65 km) along the lower continental slope of Northeast Greenland during the week. The northward motion we experienced at the end of week 39 turned west and south in the morning of Tuesday 2 June. We were now under influence of an extensive low pressure which had moved along the coast of northern Norway during the weekend and proceeded towards the North Pole area via Franz Josef Land. Winds were now from the north at speeds of 22-35 knots. The ice drift was a pleasant 0.3 knot all Wednesday 3 June through Saturday 6 June. With the warm wind (-3 °C to -5 °C) followed low clouds and poor visibility, but the weekend had glorious weather.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 40, 01-08 June 2015 (short heavy red line).

Sea ice dynamics

No ice activity was been observed in our neighborhood until Friday afternoon. Three parallel cracks, about 10 cm wide, opened through our ice floe; one right behind the hovercraft skirt, and another one between the craft and the radiation flux instrument and weather mast. The satellite image in Fig. 2 shows that the regional scale leads have closed in the situation where the forcing wind field is from the north and Northeast Greenland represents a buttress.

Fig. 2. Satellite image from 06 June courtesy of www.woksat.info showing ice distribution and fracture patterns north of Greenland and Svalbard. The mountains sighted in Northeast Greenland on the north side of Independence Fjord indicated by red "X" are Wyckoff Bjerge (northwest) and Kim Fjelde in the southeast.

Camp life

Temperatures have been between $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and even above zero during the weekend. The warm weather is something to get adjusted to. The melting effect is visible everywhere, the snow gets "rotten" - you sink in. Cracks that develop in our neighborhood will not heal by freezing so we get an idea what to prepare for. We have just moved all loose items to a seemingly intact area behind the hovercraft. However, the hovercraft, the hydro hole, the and work space is isolated on a separate 20 meter wide elongated strip of ice - a long stride takes you across the crack in between. The radiation flux instrument and the weather station are once again on a separate floe. We consider the safety risk minimal and will stay like this for the time being, because of the work that needs to be

invested in order to relocate and make a new hole in the 2 meter thick ice. If necessary, it is a matter of disconnecting the two hydraulic hoses to the winch, start the hovercraft and move off. Our limited experience suggests that if cracks start to penetrate the camp area, locate the nearest 100-200 meter wide property free of incipient cracks and claim it. There is little point in expending energy going off in a distance. As the ice activity gets more dynamic farther south, we foresee a challenge in keeping the cargo on the ice together. In the case of the thermistor string, the mooring moved over night 350 meter away from us in a shear zone, not only 150 meter as we originally estimated. Ironically, we will depend on the ice breaking up, because our neighborhood is far too chaotic for hovercraft driving - we need leads and slack ice to move in between.

Saturday was a very clear day and brought a lot of excitement. We walked and skied out to the site of the bathymetry buoy #2, about 1.7 km from the camp. The task was to recover the hydrophone below the 2.5 thick ice. A four meter high ice block in a nearby pressure ridge presented a look-out point. Audun shouted "I see land", but was met with skepticism. The two darker areas on the horizon could be drifting ice islands, however the satellite pictures show none. With time we could clearly see the nearest mountains of Northeast Greenland; Wyckoff Bjerge (bearing 247°) and Kim Fjelde (bearing 238°) at a distance of about 100 kilometer (marked with red "X" in Fig. 2). This was a great feeling; first sight of land since the beginning of August last year.

Fig. 3. Land in sight! Wyckoff Bjerge, in Northeast Greenland about 100 km away in the background.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry and sub-bottom profiling:

- echo sounder (autonomous bathymetry buoy made by CMR).

Oceanography: - current meter suspended at 150 m below the ice.

- 50 kHz and 200 kHz echo sounders to check for scattering layers in the upper 200 m.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface.

- surface infrared skin temperature.
- sun time.
- Aanderaa weather station.

Station work: - Five CTD casts to 1000 m depth.

The fast drift and southward progress during the week was a relief. Although some data are collected no matter what the drift is, moving south has a positive psychological effect. Also, every new CTD cast means we have moved another 5 nautical miles.

To get bathymetry in camp, we have activated an autonomous buoy which uses a SyQwest EchoBox echo sounder. For the time being, it transmits via Iridium to Christian Michelsen Research in Bergen to allow tuning of the parameters for optimum results. We have also suspended a current meter at 150 m depth through the hydro-hole.

The five autonomous bathymetry buoys deployed in September last year have all stopped working for various reasons. We know one has been taken by ice, and the instrument cases for the two closest sites (1.7 and 4.7 km from camp) have been recovered. On Saturday, we recovered the hydrophone below the 2.5 m thick ice at the closest site, 1.7 km away (Fig. 4). The idea is to try and activate one in camp in order to explore what the problems are. We have also recovered the instrument case of a mass balance buoy for the Finnish Meteorological Institute and checked the ice thickness (187 cm) at the site near our old camp.

Fig. 4. Drilling for recovery of the hydrophone of the autonomous buoy.

Wild life

Ivory gulls are visiting every day, but have not yet encountered signs of polar bears since we spotted tracks of a polar bear and possibly two cubs in our camp on October 10, 2014 at 89° N, 177° E.

Life in the High Arctic is treating us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 01 June

Position: 83° 44.8' N, 16° 18' W, temperature -6 °C, 1028 hPa, wind 9 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards W. Checked the radiation flux instrument and the weather station. Deployed our Aanderaa SeaGuard current meter to 150 m depth in the hydro-hole to record for the rest of the drift. Audun recovered the Finnish mass balance buoy which had stopped working. The buoy was located in the old camp area. Burned all remaining garbage in the old camp area. Two Ivory gulls came by our site today.

Tuesday 02 June

Position: 83° 44.15' N, 16° 24.7' W, temperature -3 °C, 1030 hPa, wind 6 knots from the ENE. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the S. Downloaded data for the last month from the radiation flux instrument. Hovercraft maintenance all day. A snow bunting was found dead - we had noticed the bird seemed to be physically reduced during the last few days.

Wednesday 03 June

Position: 83° 39.7' N, 16° 24' W, temperature -3 °C, 1022 hPa, wind 22 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.3 knot to the SSE. Worked on the weekly report.

Thursday 04 June

Position: 83° 31.95' N, 16° 06.9' W, temperature -5 °C, air pressure 1018 hPa, wind 32 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.3 knot towards SSE. Deployed the SyQwest EchoBox echo sounder of the autonomous buoy made by Christian Michelsen Research to obtain bathymetry from the camp site. Iridium transmission was deactivated and recording is on internal memory with a 10 minute repetition rate. Made two CTD casts down to 1000 m.

Friday 05 June

Position: 83° 23.4' N, 15° 36.7' W, temperature -5 °C, pressure 1015 hPa, wind 23 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.3 knot towards the S. Made a CTD cast down to 1000 m depth. Finished transfer of all logs to Excel format. Discovered a band of 3 parallel cracks trending NW-SE across our floe. Hovercraft azimuth is N240°E. One of the cracks is right behind the stern skirt, and one crack separates the craft from the radiation flux instrument and the weather station. Cracks are 10 cm wide.

Saturday 06 June

Position: 83° 19.5' N, 15° 15.7' W. Ice drift 0.3 knot towards the SE. A glorious day. The AirMar weather station on the hovercraft went down. Made a CTD cast to 1000 m depth. Went out on skis and on foot to bathymetry buoy #2, 1.7 km out. The buoy was located in a 50 m wide flat area surrounded by a maze of pressure ridges. We drilled a 15 cm diameter inspection hole through 2.5 m thick ice and checked with the underwater camera. The hydrophone cable was hooked and the hydrophone recovered by cutting the cable. From a look-out point on a high pressure ridge, we could clearly see two mountains in Trolle Land, Northeast Greenland, about 110 km away. This was Wyckoff Bjerge at a bearing of N247°E and Kim Bjerge at a bearing of N238°E (Fig. 4). This was exciting! All equipment was returned to camp from the buoy site.

Sunday 07 June

Position: 83° 15.8' N, 14° 45' W, wind 7 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the ESE. Made CTD cast only down to 800 m as winch did not function properly. Checked radiation flux instrument - battery showed 12.07 volt. Checked floatation tanks in the cabin for water from condensation - emptied 6 liters out of the tank below the work bench. Audun went out for a ski trip. Two Ivory gulls over the camp in the evening. The crack behind the hovercraft has widened to 0.5 meter.

Week forty one of ice drift (08- 15 June 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp drifted 35 nautical miles (66 km) along the lower continental slope of Northeast Greenland during the week (Fig. 1). We have moved one degree of latitude south over the last two weeks. The motion at the beginning and end of the past week was parallel to the major shear zone off the coast east of Station Nord (Fig. 2). Thursday and Friday, we moved closer to shear zone and all patches of open water between us and the coast disappeared. Through Wednesday, the westerly winds were due to a low pressure near the North Pole. Later a low pressure over the Barents and Kara seas gave us winds from the north and an ice drift towards the coast of Greenland. The drift speeds have been over 0.2 knot for most of the week.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 41, 08- 15 June 2015 (short thick red line).

Sea ice dynamics

The half meter wide crack right behind the hovercraft and two other parallel cracks have closed. A 10 meter wide lead which opened on 31 March about 35 meter in front of the hovercraft has also closed and formed a 2 meter high pressure ridge. These features run roughly parallel to the coast. Our motion has been to the south-southeast parallel to the shelf break, but also had a component towards the shear zone during the middle of the week. As we see on the satellite image in Fig. 2, there is no open water between our camp and the coast. We are prepared and alert for any ice activity that may necessitate a move.

Fig. 2 Satellite image (Synthetic Aperture Radar) from 12 June courtesy of Danish Meteorological Institute (<http://ocen.dmi.dk/arctic/images/MODIS/Nord/20150612s01a.ASAR.jpg>) showing ice distribution and fracture patterns northeast of Greenland. Note the shear zone for ice motion off the coast.

Camp life

The summer weather is mostly a situation with low clouds, and low terrain contrast from the diffuse light. The visibility is low. We had light rain two days this week. In between were a couple of gorgeous days. The temperature on Monday was +7 °C and between 0 °C and -3 °C the rest of the week.

Part of the daily routine is making adjustments as best we can to protect the frozen food from thawing. We cover the boxes with snow and insulation mats. The hovercraft cabin and the engine bay have had their spring cleaning. The other part of the routine is keeping the instruments going. Over and over again, we are faced with situations which demonstrate the advantage of having "boots

on the ice" to maintain all the marvelous data collecting technologies. This week Audun recovered an AWI mass balance buoy which had stopped working three weeks after it was deployed from *Polarstern* near our camp on the 30 August last year. A similar buoy belonging to the Finnish Meteorological Institute was recovered last week. The instrument had stopped reporting good data last fall. Our own five autonomous bathymetry buoys have stopped working. Two have been recovered, one we know has been taken by ice during the dark season, and three searches for the remaining two have been unsuccessful. An additional autonomous echo sounder buoy was activated in camp, but encountered problems with detecting and locking on the bottom echo. This tuning problem was solved in consultation with Chr. Michelsen Research in Bergen who again consulted the US manufacturer.

A third part of the routine is keeping your personal things in a kind of order. After over 9 months on the ice your inventory of socks are depleted and holes need to be mended (Fig. 3). If pushed hard enough, we are actually capable of knitting new socks.

Fig. 3 A concentrated left-hander mending his socks

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry: - Syquest echo box and autonomous data acquisition reporting via Iridium

Oceanography: - current meter suspended at 150 meter below the ice.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface

- surface infrared skin temperature

- sun time

- Aanderaa weather station

Station work: - 6 CTD casts to 1000 meter depth; one every 5 nautical mile

Oceanography - how can FRAM-2014/15 contribute?

Water masses are characterized by their temperature, salinity, content of dissolved gases and elements which can be utilized as tracers. These parameters are used to identify the water mass source region, the degree of mixing between water from different sources, the residence time in a region and to compute the large scale circulation assuming a geostrophic balance of forces. The basic parameters; salinity and temperature are recorded by a Conductivity, Temperature and Depth profiler (CTD) lowered through the water column. Our hovercraft *Sabvabaa* is equipped with a light version of this instrument (Fig. 4). Sensors to record dissolved gases can be added to the instrument, but studies of tracers require in situ water sampling.

Oceanography and CTD profiling are part of almost every scientific expedition into the deep Arctic Ocean. As reported by Bourgain and Gascard (2011), over 18.000 vertical CTD profiles were made between 1997 and 2008 (Fig. 5). Two thirds of these were obtained during the fourth International Polar Year (2007-2008). Most of the casts have been made during summer expeditions. If we overlay the drift track (thin red line) of FRAM-2014/15 during 2015 on this map, it is apparent that our drift traverses an area not covered by this effort as well as later surveys. The ice is simply too difficult for non-nuclear icebreakers and too deformed to land a light air plane during the March-April weather window for flying. We made a total of 13 CTD casts to full water depth across the Lomonosov Ridge from the Makarov Basin to the Amundsen Basin (thick red line in Fig. 5) during the height of the winter. Our fuel consumption and projected reserves at the time did not allow this program to continue. Fortunately, we have been able to resume CTD casts down to 1000 meter depth for the remainder of the drift following a resupply from an air drop by the 333 Sq. of the Norwegian Air Force in early April over Morris Jesup Spur. A CTD cast is made every 5 nautical mile.

Fig. 4 The CTD profiler before launch

As stated in our report for week 37, our oceanographic objectives for this part of the drift are:

- i) augment ongoing oceanographic research in the Independence Fjord area by the group from Aarhus University at the new Villum Research Station, and
- ii) contribute to the data base for determining where and how much of Atlantic Water from the Amundsen and Nansen basins joins the flow of water which has made the complete polar basin loop.

Fig. 5 Map of the distribution of CTD stations in the Arctic Ocean from Bourgain and Gascard (2011). The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during 2015 is indicated by the thin red line and sections of the drift track with CTD casts by the thick red line.

In Fig. 6 is shown the temperature and salinity profiles from two of our stations (station 153 and 163) 45 nautical miles (83 km) apart south of Morris Jesup Spur. The temperature profile show the warm (>0 °C) Atlantic Water between 200 and 600 meter depth. The Atlantic Water enters the Arctic Ocean through the West Spitsbergen Current and also through the Barents Sea. It flows as a boundary current around the entire polar basin and deflects into the sub-basins along its path to fill the entire Arctic Ocean at this depth interval. The warm water is up to $+6$ °C west of Svalbard, but has

cooled down to +1 °C off the coast of Northeast Greenland (Fig. 6). This enormous heat reservoir would easily melt all the sea ice if it had not been for the insulation represented by the overlying less saline and lighter waters. Salinity has the greatest effect on density at low temperatures. The uppermost mixed layer (20-50 meter thick) has the lowest salinity and is formed by ice melting and river input. Below is a zone of increasing salinity down to over 200 meter depth (Fig. 6). This is called the halocline and the salinity gradient is the crucial factor for maintaining a perennial ice cover. Density increases with increasing salinity at depth and creates a stable stratification which prevents heat from the warm Atlantic Water to reach the surface by convective transport. Convection is the most effective form of heat transport. The vertical green bar to the right in Fig. 6 shows the reach of the thermistor string (300 meter depth). The string has accumulated 6 months of data from the fall and winter situation to monitor the vertical heat transport from the Atlantic Water to the underside of the ice (Principal investigator Ilker Fer, Univ. of Bergen)

Fig. 6 Temperature and salinity profiles from stations 153 and 163 off the coast of Northeast Greenland. Locations are shown in inserted map. The scale for the salinity is at the bottom of the figure.

The water at station 153 and 163 is assumed to have contributions from Atlantic Water modified along three different paths; one having made the full circuit along the margin of the entire polar basin, one from recirculation in the Amundsen Basin and one from the Nansen Basin. In Fig.7 we compare the results from station 153 and 163 with typical water mass characteristics of the Amundsen and Nansen basins as presented by Rudels (2009). Station 153 and 163 appear to be closest to the characteristics of water having made the loop within the Amundsen Basin

Fig. 7 Temperature and salinity profiles of station 153 and 163 compared to properties of upper water masses in the Amundsen (AB) and Nansen (NB) basins from Rudels (2009).

Another significant oceanographic data set obtained during FRAM-2014/15 is the current meter which was successfully recovered after being suspended for 8 months below the ice at 2000 meter depth. The record starts in the Makarov Basin and ends in the Amundsen Basin. The instrument was raised to 1050, 800 and 660 meter to cross Lomonosov Ridge five times.

Fig. The radiation flux instrument (right) and the weather station (left)

Our surface instruments for measuring the radiation flux (Meterological Institute, Oslo) and the weather station (Univ. of Bergen) works well.

Wild life

Ivory gulls are visiting every day.

Life in the High Arctic treats us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 08 June

Position: 83° 11.2' N, 14° 17' W, temperature + 7 °C, wind 1 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.2 towards SE. The 0.5 m wide crack beyond the hovercraft has closed to 0.2 m. Made CTD cast down to 1000 meter depth. Audun collected the thermistors from the string and stored them inside the hovercraft. Started cleaning the sump in the engine bay and checked bilge pumps.

Tuesday 09 June

Position: 83° 07.07' N, 13° 45.9' W, temperature 0 °C, 1009 hPa, wind 12 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.3 knot towards the SE. Light rain today. The crack behind the hovercraft has closed completely. Made CTD cast to 1000 m depth. Audun recovered the AWI mass balance buoy which had ceased to function three weeks after deployment 30 August last year. The snow shelter protecting our Zarges boxes with food collapsed in the mild weather and had to be restored. The CMR bathymetry buoy in camp operate on a 10 minutes repetition rate which turns out to be hard on the batteries - changed to two 115 Ahr batteries. We saw three Ivory gulls in camp today.

Wednesday 10 June

Position: 83° 00.9' N, 13° 11' W, temperature - 1 °C, 1014 hPa, wind 18 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.35 knot to the SSE. White-out conditions. Checked the radiation flux instruments and the weather station. Made a CTD cast to 1000 m depth. Started to run a check of our ARGOS 96010 tracker buoys and coordinated with Chr. Michelsen Research, Bergen for reports. Audun transferred two drums of fuel to the hovercraft main tanks. Shipment of our storage container still at AWI, Bremerhaven is finally underway to Longyearbyen. Six Ivory gulls visited the camp at the same time. Audun made a repeat GPS measurement to determine the azimuth of the hovercraft which is now 260 degrees as compared to 241 degrees on 26 April.

Thursday 11 June

Position: 82° 54.52' N, 12° 56.3' W, temperature - 3 °C, air pressure 1025 hPa, wind 12 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.15 knot towards S. A glorious day. Felt a shock at 0137 GMT and thought it may have been an earthquake from the Lena Trough below. However, both NORSAR, Univ. of Bergen and GEUS did not see any events recorded on the Svalbard stations or at St. Nord. The shock could have been related to the start of a pressure ridge about 35 meter in front of the hovercraft. Made CTD cast to 1000 m depth. Both ARGOS tracker buoys report good positions - batteries checked 12.4 and 11.9 volt. Audun downloaded all data recorded by the CTD to date. Have made an assessment

of all the cargo beyond the maximum payload of the hovercraft and estimate the weight to be over two tons.

Friday 12 June

Position: 82° 50.1' N, 12° 55.9' W, temperature 0 °C, pressure 1023 hPa, wind 14 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards the S. A beautiful day. The former lead with present ice thickness of 0.6 m about 35 meter from the front of the hovercraft closed and quietly formed a 2 meter high pressure ridge. The Syquest echo box in camp does not find the bottom reflection. Water depth is around 3000 meter. CMR consulted the Syquest company and adjustments were made to resolve the issue. Made a CTD cast down to 1000 meter depth. Audun made a 5 hour ski trip to search for the two autonomous bathymetry buoys (# 4 and #5) not accounted for, but had no luck. This was our third unsuccessful attempt. Completed a major spring clean-up of the hovercraft cabin. Corresponded with Bert Rudels on oceanographic issues.

Saturday 13 June

Position: 82° 48.5' N, 12° 59.1' W. Temperature -1 °C, air pressure 1021 hPa, wind 12 knot from the N. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards the S. White-out conditions. We are drifting on a course that brings us closer to the major shear zone along the coast, but still about 40 km away. Made a CTD cast to 1000 meter depth. Had the generator going all day to melt snow for drinking water - we need to replenish every two weeks.

Sunday 14 June

Position: 82° 42.8' N, 12° 56' W, temperature -2 °C, air pressure 1012 hPa, wind 18 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.3 knot to the S. White-out conditions and light snow fall, 5 cm in total. Checked the radiation flux instrument - data logger battery is 11.65 Volt. Worked on the weekly report.

Week forty-two of ice drift (15- 21 June 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp drifted 16 nautical miles (30 km) along the lower continental slope of Northeast Greenland during the week (Fig. 1). The ice drift remained to the south at 0.1 knot even though winds were from variable directions during the first three days of the week. A weak high pressure over the Norwegian-Greenland Sea and Svalbard gave winds from the southeast during Thursday through Sunday, and ice drift towards the east.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 42, 15- 21 June 2015 (short thick red line).

Sea ice dynamics

Starting on Saturday 20 June, the crack right behind the hovercraft first widened to 25 meter and 24 hours later to more than 200 meter Fig. 2. Some of the activity is illustrated by the attached time lapse which covers 14 hours. From the satellite picture (Fig. 3) it is clear we are getting closer to the area of pack ice divergence. On Sunday 21 June, we dismantled the work space and

Fig. 2 The lead behind the hovercraft in the process of widening on Sunday 21 June.

Fig. 3 Satellite image from 21 June courtesy of Danish Meteorological Institute (<http://ocean.dmi.dk/arctic/images/MODIS/Nord/20150621TERR.jpg>) showing ice distribution and fracture patterns northeast of Greenland.

moved the hovercraft 30 meter away from the lead for the night. The next morning the remaining items were moved across the lead.

Camp life

The past week had two beautiful Arctic days and five days with low visibility or white-out. Temperatures have been above zero degrees (0 , +3) except for Friday (-1 °C). The surface of the snow in the low areas is getting bluish from melt water saturation and will eventually turn into melt ponds. Our daily chores are related to minimizing the impact of the summer melt and positioning cargo in preparation for more ice activity. The wild life has become more diverse. First were the snow buntings, then Ivory gulls, Pomarine skuas, a Fulmar and finally the first polar bear and a seal.

On Sunday, we had to relocate our camp for the fourth time during this nearly ten month ice drift. Relocation in 24 hour light is vastly different from past relocations to the light of our head lamps. We are approaching the area where the ice pack disintegrates and will change the way we operate. We will no longer put up any shelter for work, it is warm enough to do without. No hydro holes will be made. We will collect our cargo on the "best" piece of ice in the neighborhood and use the mobile hovercraft to exploit nearby sites of opportunity for doing the regular CTD casts and deploy the autonomous echo box to obtain bathymetry. In this way, any rapid change in the ice situation will cause minimum disruption. If needed, we have available and checked out two ARGOS trackers which can be used to tag ice floes and follow their position until recovery.

This week, we had to throw away the remaining stock of eggs (c. 40). Finding a good egg was down to one or two out of ten eggs. Our supply of the long term milk has passed its time limit and is also getting hurt by the warm environment. The potatoes have thawed and may still be of use for another week. However, the alternative dry foods are in place so there is little to worry about.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry: - Syquest echo box and autonomous data acquisition reporting via Iridium

Oceanography: - current meter suspended at 150 meter below the ice.

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface

- surface infrared skin temperature

- sun time

- Aanderaa weather station

Station work: - 2 CTD casts to 1000 meter depth; one every 5 nautical mile

The water depth (c. 3000 m) is out of reach of our remaining Kevlar line (c. 2700 m) so no bottom sampling is possible.

With the need to move our camp, we had to recover our Aanderaa SeaGuard Doppler current meter suspended at 150 meter below the ice from 1 June. To our great surprise there was moisture inside the housing and signs of corrosion. We will need help to attempt recovery of any data.

The autonomous echo sounder box is performing very well and obtains a stable depth value after 2-4 pings. One depth measurement is made every twenty minutes, i.e. every 50-100 meter along the drift track.

Wild life

We saw the first Ivory gull on the 18 May. At that time, the camp was 155 km off the coast of Northeast Greenland. This was the only visiting species until the Pomarine skua arrived on 15 June. A Fulmar was sighted on 18 June. We have for several weeks been about 100 km away from the nearest shore. Sea birds have been present over the camp every day since 7 June and up to 14 individuals. Audun was able to photograph a Pomarine skua wearing a yellow tag with the letter code JN (Fig. 4).

After forty-two weeks on the ice, we sighted our first polar bear - a somewhat scruffy looking individual who went for the food storage. The bear took off when the hovercraft engine was started and did not return.

A seal was sighted in the 200 meter wide lead behind the hovercraft on Sunday.

Fig. 4 Summary of the wildlife observed in camp. Date of first sighting and distance offshore is given.

Life in the High Arctic treats us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 15 June

Position: 82° 41.2' N, 12° 48' W, temperature 0 °C, wind 7 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.05 towards SE. White-out. Woke up to a sound outside. A somewhat scruffy bear was outside the hovercraft. We have been 42 weeks on the ice and this is the sight of a polar bear. The animal walked over to the food storage and started digging for one of the Zarges boxes. We started the hovercraft engine and the bear took off, and we have not seen it since. The AirMar weather station on the hovercraft went down. We consulted Bergen, but did not solve the problem. The melt process is accelerating and ponds are forming around the hovercraft. A pomarine skua was visiting the camp several times.

Tuesday 16 June

Position: 82° 40.64' N, 12° 51.2' W, temperature 0 °C, 1009 hPa, white-out, light rain turning into snow near midnight. No wind and no ice drift. Made a CTD cast down to 1000 meter. Continued work on the weather station issue - the problem was lack of disk space. Files were backed up and moved and the data could then be logged and displayed properly. Continued work cleaning up the sump below the engine in the engine bay. Audun reorganized some of the food.

Wednesday 17 June

Position: 82° 38.23' N, 12° 53.3' W, temperature +3 °C, 1008 hPa, wind 5 knots from the NE. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the S. A glorious day. Audun continued sorting the food. Finished work in the engine bay and cleaned and checked the bilge pumps. Removed about 100 liter of water from the rear flotation tanks. The water is melt water leaking in from above. Pairs of Ivory gulls and Pomarine skuas are visiting the camp. Audun managed to photograph a tagged Pomarine skua. The tag was yellow with capital letters JN.

Thursday 18 June

Position: 82° 36.76' N, 12° 50.8' W, temperature +2 °C, air pressure 1010 hPa, wind 2 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.0 knot. White-out.

Friday 19 June

Position: 82° 36.16' N, 12° 43.5' W, temperature -1 °C, pressure 1010 hPa, wind 8 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the E. White-out until 0200 hours, then clearing and later a beautiful day. Moved cargo to higher ridges to avoid melt pond formation. Made a new small hydro hole for the CTD, because the main hole is getting contaminated. Audun is organizing some of the equipment in boxes. Had to throw out the remaining eggs - about 40. We have visits by Ivory gulls all day.

Saturday 20 June

Position: 82° 37.1' N, 12° 31.6' W. Temperature 0 °C, air pressure 1014 hPa, wind 7 knot from the SE. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the E. White-out conditions. Checked the radiation flux instrument - battery is 12.57 volt. Checked echo box battery 12.35 volt. Moved six more boxes over to pallets on higher ground. The lead behind the hovercraft opened to 25 meter and the old refrozed and later pressured lead 35 meter in front of the hovercraft opened 1-2 meter. Had the generator running from lunch time on to make hot water for a shower in the evening. We are starting to see the contours of melt ponds on the snow covered ice surface.

Sunday 21 June

Position: 82° 35.8' N, 12° 19.8' W, temperature 0 °C, air pressure 1018 hPa, wind 4 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.15 knot to the SE. A beautiful day with no clouds. The lead behind the hovercraft skirt widened to over 200 meter during the night. Made a CTD cast to 1000 meter depth. We are at the very edge of the floe and will be in danger if the ice comes together and ice pressure occurs. Started pulling down the tent and the work space and loaded onto the hovercraft. We moved the hovercraft 30 meter away from the edge. Audun redetermined the hovercraft azimuth to 255 degrees - a change from 260 degrees measured 10 June.

Week forty-three of ice drift (22- 28 June 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp drifted 22 nautical miles (41 km) during week forty-three, but effectively only 12 nautical miles in the "right" direction along the coast (Fig. 1). Water depths are 2600-3100 meters. The surface air pressure was a high extending from Greenland to Novaja Zemlja at the beginning of the week and gradually turning east to the Laptev Sea area towards the weekend. Local winds were variable through Tuesday and from the southeast on Wednesday and Thursday which drove the ice away from the coast (Fig. 1). From Friday on, we had winds from the north and the ice drifted south.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 43, 22- 28 June 2015 (thick red line). The satellite image (<http://ocean.dmi.dk/arctic/images/MODIS/Nord/20150629AQUA.jpg>) courtesy of Danish Meteorological Institute shows the ice distribution and is draped over the bathymetry from the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean (IBCAO).

Sea ice dynamics

The crack behind the hovercraft widened to about 200 meter last week and started to come together again. The first thing in the early hours on Monday was to move the hovercraft about 30 meter into the floe and park for the night. Later, we moved over to the floe where all the equipment was and parked a similar distance from the lead. At the end of the week, the lead widened to a maximum of about 500 meter. The ice is generally slack and no pressuring occurs.

The sea ice cover in our area has a free boundary to the south and also to the west since open water is present most of the time between our location and the coast of Northeast Greenland. The general sea ice movement is divergent dominated by cracking and lead formation. Pressure ridges are rarely formed as individual floes have limited momentum. From our perspective, divergent motion is the least problematic form of sea ice dynamics. Ice pressure during the winter has transformed the sea ice surface in our vicinity to a dense network of ridges and we actually welcome extensive break-up of the ice and formation of leads in order to get out. We have stated several times in the past that formation of cracks are virtually harmless unless you by chance straddle the break. The hovercraft is like a lonely car in a vast parking lot and is moved as easy as any car. A platform of two meter thick sea ice is for all practical purposes a local "terra firma" considering loads represented by a small ice camp. The thickness of our floe is more than the requirement for landing a 200 ton cargo plane on the sea ice runway in Mc Murdo, Antarctica. A floe 100-150 meter in diameter will have the buoyancy to carry our camp one hundred times over and is considered by us as the ideal platform for a continued safe ride south. Unfortunately, the image of an ice crack or an isolated drifting ice floe may seem frightening to many people. If a situation arises, any action taken should be rooted in the reality at the site and not originate from some outsider's unconstrained and uninformed imagination. In this respect, the drift in 1893- 1896 clearly had an advantage.

Camp life

As always, days of complete overcast and low light contrast dominate throughout the week. Tuesday and Sunday was glorious. Temperatures have been between -2°C and $+2^{\circ}\text{C}$. The vigorous snow melt generate fresh water which flood the low areas on the ice, saturate the snow and form melt ponds. The ponds absorb the sun light more efficiently than the snow and deepen - some may even extend through the ice at the end of the season. Pictures from past ice stations show extensive melt ponds within the camp areas and small boats were used to move around. We drill a hole in the ponds and the fresh water drains quickly into the ocean below (Fig. 2).

We have placed the cargo on pallets on higher ground to avoid melt water damage (Fig. 3)

The melt water can be used for drinking water (Fig. 4). Carefully chosen ponds have water with no perceptible taste of salt. From now on we do not need to have the generator running all day to melt snow for our water supply.

As the ice cover gradually disintegrates and wide leads form, the motion is no longer entirely coherent, but individual floes rotate during the drift. From Friday to Sunday, our floe rotated 18 degrees.

Fig. 2 Draining melt water ponds

Fig. 3 The camp area as of 28 June

Fig. 4 Audun pumping fresh melt water from a melt pond.

Science

Underway continuous measurements:

Bathymetry: - Syquest echo box and autonomous data acquisition reporting via Iridium

Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface

- surface infrared skin temperature

- sun time

- Aanderaa weather station

Station work: - 1 CTD casts to 1000 meter depth; one every 5 nautical mile

The water depth (c. 3000 m) is out of reach of our remaining Kevlar line (c. 2700 m) so no bottom sampling is possible.

Fig. 5 Making a CTD cast in the nearby lead

We now make the CTD casts in the large lead 25 meter away from where the hovercraft is temporary parked (Fig. 5). Also, the transducer of the echo box is lowered into the lead. Smaller floes move freely within the large open water area driven by the tide and the wind and pile up in alternate ends. We sometimes recover the transducer in the evening to avoid damage from colliding floes while we are asleep.

Fig. 6 Algal? growth on the underside of the ice

Interesting cases of algae? growth are observed below some ice floes (Fig. 6).

Wild life

During the week, we have had visits by the following new species:

Kitty wake, Ruddy turnstone, Sabine's gull, Brunnich guillemot, Little auk, Arctic tern and Iceland gull/Glaucous gull. A hooded seal has also been observed.

A polar bear visited us on 23 June.

Life in the High Arctic treats us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 22 June

Position: 82° 33.33' N, 11° 55.9' W, temperature +1 °C, air pressure 1021 hPa, wind 8 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.15 towards SE. The wide lead behind the hovercraft started closing in the early morning and the hovercraft was moved 30 into the floe and parked for the night. The weather station mast fell over as the pegs for the guide wires had melted out. Moved both the weather station and the radiation flux instrument mast to the floe where all our cargo is assembled, and aligned the sensors with the North-direction. Orientation of the sun-time sensor was corrected. Initiated data logging.

Tuesday 23 June

Position: 82° 32.36' N, 11° 39.5' W, temperature +1 °C, air pressure 1020 hPa, wind 4 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.15 knot towards SE. Mist in the morning, but later a glorious day. Visit by one or two polar bears during the night. The weather station mast was down, and the animal(s) had worked at the food storage, but done no significant damage. Moved more cargo to higher areas. Bathymetry buoy voltage 12.33 volt.

Wednesday 24 June

Position: 82° 29.92' N, 11° 26.4' W, temperature -2 °C, 1021 hPa, wind 11 knots from the SE. Ice drift 0.05 knot to the NE. Made one CTD cast. Had to move the radiation flux instrument about 10 meter, because the polar bear(s) had left tracks within the area imaged by the radiation sensors.

Thursday 25 June

Position: 82° 32.1' N, 11° 15.7' W, temperature -2 °C, air pressure 1016 hPa, wind 15 knots from the SSE. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards NE. Moved cargo and organized some of the food. Melt water is accumulating on the ice. We drill holes to drain the fresh water and inhibit formation of melt ponds in our immediate vicinity.

Friday 26 June

Position: 82° 31.81' N, 10° 50.9' W, temperature 0 °C, pressure 1018 hPa, wind 9 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.3 knot towards the SE. GPS measurement for determination of the North-direction and the azimuth of the hovercraft (163 degrees). The weather station and radiation flux instrument boom checked for N-S alignment.

Saturday 27 June

Position: 82° 29.49' N, 10° 47.5' W. Temperature +2 °C, air pressure 1021 hPa, wind 4 knot from the NW. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the S. Overcast, low clouds, rain before noon. Work on a wooden crate for the compressor. Engine maintenance - checking for possible oil and cooling water leaks.

Sunday 28 June

Position: 82° 26.83' N, 10° 47.8' W, temperature 0 °C, air pressure 1024 hPa, wind 4 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.15 knot to the S. Continued engine maintenance and dismantled the compressor, air hoses and air bottles. The lead that opened behind the hovercraft and was closing at the beginning of the week is no at least 500 meter wide. For the first time we replenished our drinking water supply from the melt ponds. There is no detectable taste of salt. The azimuth of the hovercraft was 163 degrees on Friday and was now measured to 141 degrees.

Weeks forty-four and forty-five of ice drift (29 June-12 July 2015)

Ice drift

The ice camp drifted 40 nautical miles (74 km) during the two first weeks (44 and 45) in July (Fig. 1). Only about half of that was towards the south. The camp is about 30 nautical miles away from the nearest land and 10 nautical miles away from the wedge of open water along the coast of Northeast Greenland. The surface air pressure has formed a relatively weak, but persistent high extending from Svalbard into the central Arctic Ocean and generated several periods of winds from the south and slowed the ice drift.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 44 and 45, 29 June - 12 July 2015 (thick red line). The satellite image (<http://ocean.dmi.dk/arctic/images/MODIS/Nord/201507111311.jpg>) courtesy of Danish Meteorological Institute shows the ice distribution and is draped over the bathymetry from the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean (IBCAO).

Sea ice dynamics

Local sea ice activity during the two weeks has been minor and probably mostly tidally driven variations in the width of leads already present. No ridging has occurred. We have moved from 15 to 6 and back to 10 nautical miles from the nearest open water. The satellite pictures show periods of considerable ice motion along the ice edge in addition to floes being discharged to free an unconstrained motion in open water.

Camp life

The past two weeks have been exceptional in that we had low clouds and reduced visibility for only 35% of the time, the rest has been a true pleasure. Camp life revolved around keeping the science going and taking measures to minimize the impact of the melting surface as well as keeping the food as cold as possible. During the southward drift, our site has also moved from 15 to 6 nautical miles away from the nearest open water. The ice cover in this area is largely a dense network of pressure ridges formed during the winter. Ice ridges represent obstacles to hovercraft driving, and to icebreakers. The surface expression of an ice ridge is called the "sail". Due to isostatic compensation, the keel depth of an ice ridge is more than four times the sail height and the width of the keel is 2-4 times the width of the sail. So, for a 2 meter high sail in an area of 2 meter thick level ice, you are considering a 10 meter thick local sea ice obstruction to an icebreaker. Most of the ridges in this area less than one hundred meters apart (Fig. 2), which for all practical purposes render the area inaccessible to diesel driven icebreakers given any reasonable effort. For this reason, patience is needed to ride out the last part in the life cycle of sea ice and we have opted for assistance in mid-August.

Fig. 2 The sea ice surface in front of the hovercraft at its present position

For several years, a plan to work on the ice covered coast and fjords of Northeast Greenland has been on our drawing board. A new research facility, the Villum Research Centre, established by University of Aarhus at Station Nord was inaugurated 9 July by Her Majesty Queen Margrethe of Denmark. Northeast Greenland inside 3 nautical miles is a national park and any research activity is subject to permission by Greenland Authorities. The Villum Research Centre has on our behalf, submitted an application to the Greenland Authorities to enter the premises and operate in the Independence Fjord area during the interim period until the planned pick-up in mid-August. The objectives are to gain insight into hovercraft driving conditions over fjord ice, demonstrate the capabilities of a hovercraft research platform and carry out water depth measurements in the ice covered passage from the shelf to Station Nord. The capabilities to do oceanographic work and geological sampling are also present.

The initial plan for cruise PS 93.1 of the German research icebreaker *Polarstern* included a geological station c. 110 nautical miles to the south of the ice camp. The cruise took opportunity of favorable ice conditions and the grid of geological stations was moved to the north. The Captain and Chief Scientist visited the ice camp by helicopter on Sunday 5 July to familiarize themselves with the situation at the camp. An attempt followed to transfer the cargo from the ice camp to *Polarstern* by helicopter, but was aborted by mutual agreement due to various time constraints. The cargo transferred was limited to disposable dangerous goods such as used motor oil, batteries and ten empty fuel drums. Audun Tholfsen was granted permission to return to Norway onboard *Polarstern*.

At this point we are c. 27 nautical miles from nearest land on Nordostrundingen and c. 65 nautical miles from Station Nord. All the cargo in the ice camp has been placed up high on a former pressure ridge and tagged with two ARGOS satellite trackers and one tracker transmitting via Iridium (Fig. 3). The hovercraft is standing by about 4 nautical miles landward of the ice camp (Fig. 4) awaiting confirmation of a permission to enter the national park as well as improved ice conditions for passage to open water and Greenland.

Fig. 3. The FRAM-2014/14 cargo (c. 2 ton) placed on top of a pressure ridge and tagged with three satellite trackers

Fig. 4. The hovercraft on 12 July 2015. The ability to find an optimum path over the sea ice surface is much improved by a use of a camera on top a telescope mast (max. height 13 meter). The image from the "virtual bridge" is displayed on a laptop near the driver.

Science

Underway continuous measurements until end of week 44 of ice drift:

- Bathymetry: - Syquest echo box and autonomous data acquisition reporting via Iridium to CMR.
- Atmosphere: - measurement of incoming and outgoing radiation from the ice surface
- surface infrared skin temperature
 - sun time
 - Aanderaa weather station

Station work until end of week 44 of ice drift:

- 4 CTD casts to 1000 meter depth

The science program on FRAM-2014/15 was terminated on Friday 3 July 2015 at the end of week 44 of ice drift. With the imminent disintegration of the sea cover ahead and limited available work force, we would like to be unconstrained by scientific duties on the drifting sea ice. During the interim period until a scheduled pick-up in mid-August, we hope to move the scientific activity to the adjacent Independence Fjord area of Northeast Greenland and work in cooperation with the new Villum Research Centre established by University of Aarhus.

In the ice camp, the radiation flux instrument and the weather station were dismantled and packed. All equipment items belonging to outside institutions go with the hovercraft, other items are stored in camp on an ice ridge marked with satellite trackers awaiting recovery in mid-August. The

transducer of the bathymetry box was operated in the nearest lead. However, large pieces of ice were moving back and forth driven by tidal forces and often hit the buoy site. For this reason, we only kept the transducer in during day time. Now the buoy serves as a tracker of the cargo at the camp site.

Wild life

An Arctic tern is the only new bird species that was observed visiting the camp during the last two weeks

We had polar bear visits in camp seven days in a row starting at the beginning of week 44. The last one, a young bear was a bit aggressive, but eventually left. Days later, a seal was spotted on the ice.

Life in the High Arctic treats us well.

Yngve Kristoffersen & Audun Tholfsen

Daily reports

Monday 29 June

Position: 82° 25.14' N, 11° 04.7' W, temperature 0 °C, air pressure 1024 hPa, wind 3 knots from the SSE. Ice drift 0.1 towards SSE. A CTD cast was made to 1000 meter water depth. The azimuth of the hovercraft is now 144 degrees and was 141 degrees yesterday. Audun spotted an Arctic tern in camp. Received an e-mail from AWI-logistics which expressed their understanding that our contact so far had been to explore possibilities not asking for assistance. The cruise plan suggests a minimum separation of at least 100 nautical miles between the ship and the ice camp.

Tuesday 30 June

Position: 82° 25.00' N, 10° 54.3' W, temperature 0 °C, air pressure 1014 hPa, wind 10 knots from the SSW. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards E. Sun shine until the afternoon and overcast in the evening. A polar bear visited the camp. The bear appeared timid and kept at a distance. The animal was mostly interested in fish we had to dispose of. Responded to the e-mail from AWI-logistics that we did not anticipate their assistance would be needed considering the separation between the

ship and the ice camp. The earlier alternative to use the sealer HAVSEL out of Longyearbyen in mid-August was reaffirmed with the owner.

Wednesday 01 July

Position: 82° 22.85' N, 10° 51.6' W, temperature 0 °C, 1017 hPa, wind 8 knots from the NW. Ice drift 0.2 knot to the S. Overcast, rain during the middle of the day. Made one CTD cast to 1000 meter water depth. The hovercraft azimuth is now 148 degrees. Had a polar bear around the camp all day. Audun sorted food and repacked. We had to take down the Norwegian flag which has been flying from the mast on top of the hovercraft since 30 August 2014, because the rope broke. A new flag was put in.

Thursday 02 July

Position: 82° 16.73' N, 10° 41.5' W, temperature -1 °C, air pressure 1021 hPa, wind 8 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards the S. Made a CTD cast down to 1000 meter depth. We moved cargo to the top of the pressure ridge that was formed by the destructive event in late March. This is considered the maximum safety to avoid being submerged as the summer melt progresses. A polar bear was walking around near the camp most of the day.

Friday 03 July

Position: 82° 14.08' N, 10° 35.3' W, temperature +4 °C, pressure 1023 hPa, wind 2 knots from the WSW. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the SSE. The azimuth of the hovercraft was determined to 147 degrees from GPS measurements. At 0950 GMT the AWI Polar-5 aircraft was overhead and a brief contact was made. At 1800 hours, the data logging of the radiation flux instrument was terminated, and also for the weather station at 1915 hours (Norw. Summer time). All the equipment were dismantled and packed. Our remaining fuel is 45 liter of gasoline and 1600 diesel including Jet A-1. A polar bear was around in camp all day, being mostly interested in the food storage - had to scare the animal away several times.

Saturday 04 July

Position: 82° 13.57' N, 10° 27.8' W. Temperature +2 °C, air pressure 1026 hPa, wind 1 knot from the ENE. Ice drift 0.15 knot towards the SE. *Polarstern* was now at 81° 36' N, 06° 36' W. The cruise had taken advantage of the ice situation and moved the grid of geological stations to the north relative to the initial plan. An e-mail from Chief Scientist R. Stein informed us that there would be another geological station farther north and the Captain and the Chief Scientist would like to visit the ice camp by helicopter tomorrow morning. Had a shower in the sauna in the evening. A polar bear visited the camp during the night, but did no damage.

Sunday 05 July

Position: 82° 11.50' N, 10° 13.4' W, temperature +1 °C, air pressure 1029 hPa, wind 3 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.2 knot to the SE. Made a CTD cast to 1000 meter depth in the morning. Captain Wunderlich and the Chief Scientist arrived by helicopter at 1045 hours from a position about 11 nautical miles to the south of the ice camp. The purpose of the visit was to gather information about the situation at the ice camp for later consultation with the AWI logistics in Bremerhaven. From our standpoint, pick-up of *Polarstern*. The return flight to the ice camp included two persons from *Polarstern* to assess the amount of cargo to be moved. The estimate was 12 helicopter trips. Later in the evening, we did away with all burnable waste in the camp and made the final preparations for cargo to be moved. A very aggressive polar bear appeared in the late evening, but was chased away.

Monday 06 July

Position: 82° 09.90' N, 09° 56.4' W, temperature +2 °C, air pressure 1027 hPa, wind 11 knots from the SSW. Ice drift 0.2 towards E. The Chief Mate and three of the *Polarstern* crew arrived by helicopter with equipment for cargo transfer. The priority was the disposable dangerous goods (used oil, batteries, empty fuel drums). *Polarstern* was now on station about 20 nautical miles to the west of the ice camp and each helicopter round trip was of the order of one hour. It became clear from consideration of the amount of cargo combined with flight crew work regulations that at least one extra day would be needed. This time would have to come out of the science time of a relatively short cruise, and it was agreed to terminate the attempted cargo transfer. Facing the prospect of another five weeks of slow drift and the summer go by, Audun asked to be transferred to *Polarstern* for return to Tromsø 18 July. Permission was granted by the parties involved, and the necessary document signed declaring that "RV *Polarstern* can proceed with her expedition according to vessels schedule and there are no further responsibilities from the side of the Master and Chief Scientist of RV *Polarstern*".

Tuesday 07 July

Position: 82° 07.80' N, 09° 44.2' W, temperature -1 °C, air pressure 1028 hPa, wind 8 knots from the E. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards S. Made a frame on port deck and put 1000 meter Kevlar line in. Reported to *Polarstern* with a summary of the past events.

Wednesday 08 July

Position: 82° 06.18' N, 09° 56.7' W, temperature -2 °C, 1028 hPa, wind 6 knots from the NE. Ice drift 0.1 knot to the SW. Activated two ARGOS trackers and the CMR buoy on the cargo stored on the pressure ridge, and started driving the hovercraft in the direction of Greenland. Had to stop after one hour because of vibrations

when the propeller pitch is increased beyond 2/3 of full. Consulted with Griffon Hoverworks, UK, tightened the drive belt and continued. Got stuck on an ice ridge and had to winch out. At about midnight, we came into a very challenging area characterized by a mess of ice ridges and had to park. About 4 nautical miles had been covered.

Thursday 09 July

Position: 82° 03.05' N, 10° 22.0' W, temperature +2 °C, air pressure 1034 hPa, wind 7 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards SW. There is no sense in trying to proceed in this terrain due to the fuel consumption. The only alternative is to wait it out. Unfortunately the forecasted winds will remain from the south until Wednesday next week. Retightened the propeller drive belt and rearranged the utility box on the starboard side forward. Saw a seal on the ice basking in the sun at a distance.

Friday 10 July

Position: 82° 01.61' N, 10° 31.9' W, temperature +1 °C, pressure 1031 hPa, wind 7 knots from the SSE. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the W. A beautiful day all the way through. Worked on reports and made a reconnaissance trip on foot in the neighborhood.

Saturday 11 July

Position: 82° 01.52' N, 10° 49.5' W. Temperature 0 °C, air pressure 1027 hPa, wind 9 knot from the SE. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the S. Worked on reporting.

Sunday 12 July

Position: 82° 26.83' N, 10° 47.8' W, temperature 0 °C, air pressure 1024 hPa, wind 4 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.15 knot to the S. Worked on reporting.

Week forty-six of ice drift (13 - 19 July 2015)

New web-site: <http://sabvabaa.nersc.no> for updates

Ice drift

The ice camp drifted 36 nautical miles (67 km) during the past week (Fig. 1). The drift was oblique to the coast and the nearest point was about 13 nautical miles away from land.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 during week 46, 12 - 19 July 2015 (thick red line).

Fig. 2 The ice situation as it developed during the week. Satellite images courtesy of Danish Meteorological Institute

Sea ice dynamics

We observed only minor local ice activity during the week, probably driven by the tide for the most part. No ridging occurred. However, the regional ice activity was something very different. As seen from Fig. 2, a large sliver of the landfast ice was severed off about 13 July, disintegrated and the pieces moved fast along the coast towards the south. At the same time, a jet of drifting sea ice created a tongue which turned west around the southeast corner of Nordostrundingen. Formation of the jet implied large lateral variation in drift speed and increased the separation between the hovercraft and the abandoned camp where all the equipment is stored (Fig. 2). At the hovercraft, we measured drift speeds up to 0.5 knot. What forced the jet, a local coastal current or sea ice convergence and extrusion, is not known.

Camp life

The daily routine is dominated by the focus on the dynamics of the ice cover near the ice edge where the sea ice approaches the end of its life cycle. Our location within the ice field has up until now been beyond the reach of any western icebreaker given a reasonable effort, due to the general ice conditions (density of ice ridges and ice thickness). Also hovercraft driving has been impossible with a reasonable consumption of fuel and the need to cut your way through in places. The cargo could have been retrieved by helicopter if available, but there would still be the need for the hovercraft to get out. Although we are soon at a point where the distance to land starts to increase, continued patience is the best option. Continued patience also goes along with an emerging mechanical problem of reduced forward thrust. The cause is a bad drive axle bearing. A spare drive axle and bearing assembly is held in Longyearbyen and steps are taken in cooperation with University of Aarhus to get the part out here. Our plan is still to make it to Independence Fjord and work there until pick-up in mid-August.

We are parked on an ice floe about 200 x 300 meter in size, close to an old pressure ridge which runs along its length about 1/3 inboard from the edge. This 1/3 of the floe is higher than the rest of the area and has a free board of 60 centimeter. The large freeboard is because the ice thickness has been doubled by underthrusting (Fig. 3). Sea ice thickens by thermodynamic processes and by mechanical underthrusting. The thickness of new sea ice increases with time by freezing, but the rate of increase slows down exponentially as the insulating effect of the ice cover increases with increasing thickness and snow cover. Most of the sea ice thicker than 2.5 meter is formed by one ice floe underthrusting another. We do not know any figures for the percentage of the sea ice area thickened by mechanical underthrusting, but my guess would be well over 50% in areas with abundant pressure ridges.

Fig. 3. Underthrusting of ice behind a pressure ridge

We are right now in the zone where the sea ice cover disintegrates completely and melting accelerate dramatically as open ocean conditions are approached (Fig. 2). Although, it may appear dramatic on the satellite image (Fig. 2, 19 July), the surface is still dominated by melt ponds and an occasional small open "hole" of sea water (Fig. 4, lower panel). Not much ice activity has happened on the local level up until now.

Fig. 4 Comparison between the driver's view (upper) and the view obtained via the camera (lower). Pictures are taken 19 July, compare Fig. 2, lower panel.

Science

With a reduced crew, we have terminated the ice drift science program as a safety measure in order to be unconstrained as the ice edge is approached.

Wild life

A polar bear at a distance and a couple of Ivory gulls are the only wild life observed during the week. I We remain surprised by the few encounters with polar bears in this region.

Life in the High Arctic treats me well.

Yngve Kristoffersen

Daily reports

Monday 13 July

Position: 82° 03.18' N, 11° 05.1' W, temperature 0 °C, air pressure 1020 hPa, wind 12 knots from the S. Ice drift 0.1 towards NNW. Worked on the weekly report

Tuesday 14 July

Position: 82° 00.07' N, 11° 03.7' W, temperature -1 °C, air pressure 1025 hPa, wind 11 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.4 knot towards S. Cut a passage through an adjacent pressure ridge to prepare hovercraft access to the nearest lead. A polar bear passed by at a distance of about 100 meter. Washed some clothes.

Wednesday 15 July

Position: 81° 56.40' N, 11° 08.2' W, temperature +1 °C, 1025 hPa, wind 7 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.2 knot to the S. Moved the hovercraft over a lead and parked on ice which appeared to be of double thickness from underthrusting. Tried first to park near the edge of the floe to get the echo sounder transducer into the water, but the free board was high (>0.5 m). There was the risk that the hovercraft would slide over the edge and tip sideways into the water, so the attempt was abandoned. The ice drill did not reach through the flow and acquiring bathymetry data had to be abandoned. We have a problem with the propulsion in that when pitch is increased above a certain level, a rattling noise is heard. Past attempts to tighten the drive belt have not alleviated the problem. After being advised to slacken the drive belt between the engine and the propeller, the drive axle was found to have a play which indicates a bad bearing. The hovercraft is drivable, but the problem needs to be rectified

without delay. Since we need the engine running for charging of batteries, the drive belt was removed for the time being. We were notified from NERSC that a new web-site for the expedition was put on line (sabvabaa.nersc.no). The site presents updated satellite images of the ice situation around the drift station.

Thursday 16 July

Position: 81° 51.51' N, 11° 10.7' W, temperature +3 °C, air pressure 1027 hPa, wind 6 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.1 knot towards the S. We need to get spare drive axle/bearing from Longyearbyen to here. The possibility of an air drop by a Danish Air Force flight to St. Nord 29 July is investigated.

Friday 17 July

Position: 81° 48.65' N, 11° 05.3' W, temperature +5 °C, pressure 1026 hPa, wind 2 knots from the W. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards the S. Moved the hovercraft a few meter and put lumber across the keels to avoid melting. We are parked parallel to a pressure ridge 4 m away on ice that is likely to have been doubled by underthrusting. Extended observation mast to 13 meter and took pictures in the four main directions. Permission to enter the national park is still pending. A possible air drop by the Danish Air Force will require dispensation as there will be passengers onboard.

Saturday 18 July

Position: 81° 45.1' N, 10° 53.5' W. Temperature +3 °C, air pressure 1026 hPa, wind 2 knot from the W. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards the S. Took pictures in the four main directions. Removed the drive belt for the propeller to minimize load on the bearing. Remaining gasoline for the generator is 15 liter to be held in reserve. The main engine is used for charging batteries from now on.

Sunday 19 July

Position: 81° 36.96' N, 10° 39.2' W, temperature -2 °C, air pressure 1025 hPa, wind 12 knots from the NNW. Ice drift 0.5 knot to the S. Radar distance to land is 13 nautical miles. Took overview pictures in the four main directions. The drive axle assembly in Longyearbyen has been inspected by Audun and found in good order.

Week forty-seven and forty-eight of ice drift (20 July - 2 Aug.2015)

New web-site: <http://sabvabaa.nersc.no> for updates

See the web-site: <http://www.aari.ru> for the Russian ice drift station North Pole - 2015

Ice drift

The hovercraft site drifted 67 nautical miles (124 km) during the two week period (Fig. 1). The separation between the hovercraft and the trailing camp increased to over 20 nautical miles. During the middle of week 48, the hovercraft left the drifting sea ice and parked on landfast ice near Krøyer's Holme. The location is marked with "x" in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 hovercraft during week 47, 20 - 26 July 2015 (thick red line). Parking location on landfast ice is marked with a black "x"..

The ice drift is a result of forces from wind drag and currents. The currents may be both a general background current and tidal currents. The tidal component becomes apparent by a drift trajectory in the form of cycloids at 12 hour intervals when the wind forcing is weak and the steady state currents are slow (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 The drift track 23-27 July 2015 describing nested cycloids.

Sea ice dynamics

The export of sea ice from the Arctic Ocean through the Fram Strait has a minimum during the summer months May through August. At present the main outflow is on the eastern side of the strait as a direct continuation of the Transpolar Drift (Fig. 3). FRAM-2014/15 was deployed on sea ice at a location which under normal circumstances would be included in the Transpolar Drift. The anticipated direct trajectory would be towards Svalbard via the North Pole. Quite unexpectedly, the sequence of cells of low sea level air pressure making their way into the central Arctic Ocean during the winter months resulted in a drift trajectory which gave five crossings of the Lomonosov Ridge and brought the ice camp towards Canada/Greenland. In this region, old ice from the Beaufort Gyre exits the polar basin. On the average, passage of low pressure cells increase sea ice export through the Fram Strait and the export is sensitive to the trajectory of the low pressure. Low pressures moving east of the Fram Strait enhances outflow of ice. This summer, low pressures moving north from Northern Norway towards Svalbard have enhanced the outflow of ice on the eastern side of the strait (Fig. 3).

As shown in Fig. 2 of the report for week 46, a tongue of drifting sea ice accelerated southward after 13 July like a jet stream out of the large ice field to the north (Fig. 3, upper panel). This tongue gradually dispersed as shown by the situation on 23 July 2015 (Fig. 3 lower panel). The distance between the abandoned camp with the stored equipment and the hovercraft increased to over 20 nautical miles (37 km). Thursday 23 July was a clear day and provided an opportunity to compare the satellite information with the ground view. The hovercraft was now drifting in an area where the satellite images indicated scattered sea ice (Fig. 3b). The ground view at the hovercraft site at the same time gave a slightly different impression. The ice surface was rather extensive to the west and north, our directions of prime interest. The picture in Fig. 5 is taken from an airplane a few hours after the pictures in Fig. 4.

At the same time, the location of the abandoned FRAM-2014/15 camp with the stored equipment appeared from the satellite image to be located in a more massive ice field (Fig. 3, upper panel). This is also reflected in the photo overview taken from the airplane (Fig. 6).

Fig. 3 Satellite image from 17 July 2015 showing the extent of sea ice drifting out through the Fram Strait. Location of the FRAM-2014/15 camp indicated by red "x" and the location of the hovercraft parked on landfast ice indicated by red "o". Note the extensive cover of landfast sea ice along the coast of Northeast Greenland. Satellite image courtesy of the web site <http://woksat.info>

Fig. 3 Upper panel: Ice situation 19 July and the location of the hovercraft and the cargo
 Lower panel: Ice situation on 23 July and locations of the cargo and the hovercraft Sabvabaa.
 Krøyer's Holme where the hovercraft parked on landfast ice 28 July is on the lower left.

Fig. 4 View of the ice surrounding the position of the hovercraft on 23 July 2015.
Photos are taken by a camera on a 13 meter high mast.

Fig. 5. Overview of the ice floe at the hovercraft site 23 July 2015.. Drop site marked by red "X". Photo courtesy of Pilot Tom-Are Stølsdokken, Lufttransport. View to the WSW.

Fig. 6 Overview of the abandoned FRAM-2014/15 camp with the equipment stored on top of a pressure ridge..Photo courtesy of pilot Tom-Are Stølsdokken, Lufttransport.

Camp life

Our time is consumed by keeping ourselves updated on the ice situation and constantly evaluating the advantage of any passing opportunity. We are provided daily with detailed satellite images from the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Centre and position information from the satellite trackers in the abandoned camp. Additional satellite images are available from web-sites such as: ocean.dmi.dk/arctic/ or www.woksat.info/wos.html. The images provide information on ice concentration in a general way, but to convert the image resolution into hovercraft driving conditions is a learning experience. Areas of apparent scattered ice often turn out to be not passable. At this time, the surviving sea ice are mostly fragments of pressure ridges and not level passable areas. Also, because of the limited resolution, the abundance of ice seems to be considerably higher than the images convey.

The hovercraft left the FRAM-2014/15 camp on the July 8th with the intent to reach Independence Fjord and the scientists at the Villum Research Station. The transit was considered to be made up of several shorter segments which reflected the developing opportunities of the ice situation. The first advance was only about 4 nautical miles before the ice conditions did not justify the fuel expenditure. Also, as pitch was applied to the propeller, a rattling sound started when the level increased beyond 2/3 of normal load. Trouble shooting followed in consultation with engineers at Griffon Hoverwork, Southampton. In the end it became clear that the drive axle coming out at the back of the engine had a play which meant the bearing was bad. A pulley at the end of the axle transfers torque to the propeller via a toothed belt. If the axle gives way, the belt slackens, skips positions on the pulley and emits a rattling sound. A spare axle/bearing assembly was held in Longyearbyen and with generous logistic assistance from University of Århus, an airplane was hired to drop the spare part on 23 July (Fig. 7). The cargo landed 30 meter from the hovercraft and ten hours later the replacement had been completed. No test was made as the weather turned bad with 20-30 knots wind and snow for nearly two days. When the propulsion system was tested on the 26 July, a vibration was still there to some extent. A loose engine mount was tightened, but the problem was not completely solved. As a practical consequence, it is not possible to attain normal speed levels over ground; we make 7 knots over water instead of 25 knots. Ice has much lower friction and the disadvantage is less.

The ice concentration to the north of our site continued to suppress any hope for more progress towards Independence Fjord. As the distance between the abandoned camp and the hovercraft site kept increasing and the ice was open to the west, we decided to leave the drifting sea ice and wait it out parked on the landfast ice about 24 miles to the west. In the evening of 28 July, we parked at the very edge of the landfast sea ice (Fig. 8). With that eleven months adrift was temporarily over. It was a moment which called for some reflections and the last glass of red wine available.

The wide strip of sea ice attached to the coast of Northeast Greenland (Fig. 3) forms in the late fall and completely disintegrates in late July-middle August which means now. At this latitude the present width of the ice belt is over 30 kilometer. The outer part is an amalgamation of shear zones which have the surface expression of parallel ridges of ice blocks. We would have to clear our way to make it farther into the landfast ice. Also, the heavy traffic of dense fields of ice blocks driven by the

tide passing along the edge would make it difficult to escape (Fig. 8). We took advantage of the ice conditions on the 31 July and moved north to within 1 kilometer of Krøyer's Holmer (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3,

Fig. 7 Cargo with the spare parts received on the ice floe axle/bearing

Replacement and used drive assembly (each 15 kilos).

Fig. 8. Upper: First landing on the landfast sea ice 3.1 nautical miles south of Krøyer's Holme. Lower: New location on landfast sea ice 0.5 nautical mile from Krøyer's Holmer.

lower panel) and parked on a thick level ice floe. This site appeared comparatively safe (Fig. 8, lower panel).

At this point we are faced with the reality that only about 700 liters of diesel fuel remains. The fuel will be needed for heating and the rendezvous with the relief vessel in about two weeks. Any hope of reaching Independence Fjord has to be abandoned.

Temperatures during the past two weeks have been in the range -1°C to $+3^{\circ}\text{C}$. Week 47 had a single day of clear sky (Thursday 23 July), the rest was low clouds and near white-out conditions. The two last days of week 48 (01 and 02 August) were glorious - a low dense cloud cover dominated the rest of the week.

Space technology and the field office on sea ice

Being able to communicate with the outside world is crucial to any activity in remote areas. Having had the good fortune of getting the experience of the life of a scientist on the ice (1979 and 1982) in the era of HF-radio communication, I fully appreciate the importance of the satellite communication facilities of today. The challenge with HF-radio communication is the highly variable ionospheric conditions. As an employee of the Norwegian Polar Institute at that time, I had access to a powerful transceiver and could communicate directly with Svalbard Radio on the same frequencies as the fishing fleet. The main camp communication was via HF to Station Nord, or phone patches to the United States using the radio amateur band.

Today, there is precious little difference between what you can effectively achieve working out of your regular office and a High Arctic field office as the FRAM-2014/15 ice drift. The satellite phone and access to internet are on your desk. Although, the Iridium satellite communication system with its limited bandwidth has constraints, it is fully functional for the majority of tasks. The daily routine apart from regular e-mail correspondence, includes downloading satellite images to follow the sea ice conditions, air pressure charts and checking the weather forecast.

Most importantly, it makes it possible for us to independently handle matters arising with the same efficiency as being at your home institution. A recent example was the need for getting a spare part over from Longyearbyen two weeks ago. Options were explored in e-mail communication with the logistic support group (Aarhus University) for the Villum Research Centre at Station Nord. We then asked our home institution (Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Centre, NERSC) to transfer the money to hire a plane, and the air drop was carried out the day after. Throughout the year, crucial support has been given on computer issues by key NERSC staff by directing us through the problem via the satellite telephone. A team of engineers at Griffon Hoverwork, Southampton responds instantly via e-mail with advice on problems arising with the hovercraft. As a result, the quality of the communication facility compensates to a considerable extent for the need to have one person for every task on the ice, an issue which relates to safety as well as costs.

Another aspect is the fact that it is also possible to continue your scientific publishing activity from a remote sea ice site in the High Arctic. In our report for week 8, we mention the submission and completed final revision of our paper to Journal of Geophysical Research where we report the

results of two seasons of vibroseis exploration of the sub-ice geology in Dronning Maud Land. This is a first on the Antarctic continent using the vibroseis technology and another joint cutting edge science venture with our German colleagues.

Validation of satellite imagery is an important topic of research. One aspect is the portrayal of the sea ice concentration in images of limited resolution. This is an issue which has great practical importance for us at the moment. As shown in Fig. 4, we collect ground photo documentation of the actual sea ice conditions in the marginal ice zone with a foot print of about 4 square kilometers.

Science

With a reduced crew and frequent relocations, we have terminated the ice drift science program as a safety measure .

Wild life

A young polar bear made a brief visit, but instead of going for the food box above his head on the deck, the bear bit a hole in the hovercraft skirt and was subsequently scared away by the sound of the engine.

The difference in abundance and diversity of the bird life between our present location and the west coast of Spitsbergen, is striking. We have daily visits by a few single individuals of Iceland gulls. On Saturday 01 August, we got a surprise visit by five large birds, tentatively identified as Common Eider in late summer plumage (Fig. 9 and 10). They rested peacefully at the ice edge near the hovercraft before continuing.

Fig. 9. Common Eider? in late summer plumage.

Fig. 10. Common Eider? In the left background.

Life in the High Arctic treats me well.

Yngve Kristoffersen

Daily reports

Monday 20 July

Position: 81° 27.75' N, 10° 10.4' W, temperature 0 °C, air pressure 1025 hPa, wind 9 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.4 towards the S. Overcast all day. A polar bear suddenly put his paws on the front window, but took off as the engine was started. The radar shows land is 14 nautical miles away. Awaiting satellite images to decide what to do next. Dense cloud cover render only synthetic aperture radar (SAR) images useful.

Tuesday 21 July

Position: 81° 19.66' N, 09° 44.4' W, temperature 1 °C, air pressure 1022 hPa, wind 6 knots from the WSW. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards ESE. Low clouds all day. We are now isolated on a floe 200 x 300 m with about 100 meter of open water on three sides. Beyond that is solid ice all around. Danish Air Force C-130 flight to St. Nord was cancelled and hire of an airplane was necessary in order to get the spare axle/bearing from Longyearbyen. Hire was arranged through an agreement Univ. of Århus has for science support flights from Longyearbyen to St. Nord.

Wednesday 22 July

Position: 81° 15.00' N, 09° 29.6' W, temperature -1 °C, 1023 hPa, wind 3 knots from the ENE. Ice drift 0.35 knot to the SE. Rain in the morning, clearing up at noon and a glorious afternoon and evening. The ice floe has rotated 180 degrees during the last 24 hours. Hire for the air drop of the spare part was finalized and scheduled for tomorrow to take advantage of the weather conditions.

Thursday 23 July

Position: 81° 06.31' N, 09° 14.8' W, temperature +1 °C, air pressure 1022 hPa, wind 7 knots from the N. Ice drift 1.0 knot towards the S. At about 1600 hours the Dornier airplane piloted by Tom-Are Stoelsdokken dropped the spares from about 30 meter altitude. The well wrapped box landed 30 meter from the hovercraft and its content was in good order. The aircraft made a search for the abandoned camp site with the stored equipment, photographed the site and returned to Longyearbyen. Started the job with replacement of the axle/bearing assembly at 2000 hours. The work went without significant obstacles, the drive belt was put on and tightened to specifications.

Friday 24 July

Position: 80° 51.30' N, 09° 26.5' W, temperature -2 °C, pressure 1016 hPa, wind 25 knots from the N. Ice drift 0.9 knot towards the S. Snow and 20-30 knot winds from the early morning. Work on the propeller drive unit went on until 0330 hours, but no testing done. During the day, all open water areas closed and there was one solid ice cover in all directions. The stove would not burn properly - the temperature in the cabin went down to +9 Centigrades

Saturday 25 July

Position: 80° 45.76' N, 10° 35.5' W. Temperature -1 °C, air pressure 1014 hPa, wind 12 knot from the N. Ice drift 0.2 knot towards the ESE. Overcast and rain during the afternoon and evening. The ice floe has rotated 360 degrees during the last 24 hours. The abandoned camp with the equipment is now 18.8 nm away.

Sunday 26 July

Position: 80° 45.89' N, 10° 50.9' W, temperature 0 °C, air pressure 1018 hPa, wind 5 knots from the WSW. Ice drift 0.4 knot in a cycloid motion. to the S. Light snow, fog. Tested the forward thrust. Surprisingly, the vibrations are still there as pitch is applied beyond a certain level. Change of the axle/bearing assembly gave improvement, but did not solve the problem.

Monday 27 July

Position: 80° 49.83' N, 10° 53.3' W, temperature 0 °C, air pressure 1020 hPa, wind 8 knots from the SSW. Ice drift 0.6 towards the NE. Overcast and fog all day. Pursued the

engine problem. Rear starboard engine mount was loose and the bolts were tightened. The stove was unhappy and would not burn properly because the hovercraft had a list in its parking position. Had to reposition the lumber under the keels.

Tuesday 28 July

Position: 80° 53.68' N, 11° 01.7' W, temperature -1 °C, air pressure 1022 hPa, wind 11 knots from the WSW. Ice drift 0.4 knot in a cycloid pattern. Fog is coming and going. Started driving the hovercraft at 1015 hours towards the west to reach the landfast ice. After two hours the hovercraft suddenly got a list which could not be corrected by the skirt control and the craft was parked on an ice floe for inspection. A pivoting angle which was part of the skirt control had got stuck. The problem was corrected and the journey continued. The fog made it difficult at times to avoid dead ends. Most surprising was recognition of the conflicting impressions of the real ice conditions compared to conditions derived from the satellite images due to the limited resolution. At 2048 hours we reached the edge of the landfast ice and parked about 3.1 nautical miles southeast of Krøyer's Holmer. The sea was dead calm, but the fog was dense all evening. This moment marked the end of 11 months on the drifting sea ice. The occasion was celebrated with a moment of reflection, Drytec Minestrone soup (just add hot water) and a glass of the last red wine from the Polarstern collection. Land is seen on the radar at 16 nautical miles and Krøyer's Holme at 3.1 nautical miles.

Wednesday 29 July

Position: 80° 36.50' N, 13° 24.1' W, temperature -2 °C, 1020 hPa, wind 7 knots from the NE. Low clouds and poor contrast until the afternoon, good visibility in the evening. We are parked at the very edge of the landfast ice. Put the hovercraft upon wooden planks to avoid melting. Checked out possible sites for better parking, but the flat areas are small and too narrow for maneuvering. A young polar bear appeared in the evening and started biting the hovercraft skirt below the food box on deck. Made a 10 cm long tear. Started the engine and the bear run away.

Thursday 30 July

Position: 80° 36.50' N, 13° 24.1' W, temperature -2 °C, air pressure 1026 hPa, wind 8 knots from the ENE. We are parked at the edge of the landfast ice. Worked on illustrations all day. Danish Air Force Challenger surveillance plane was overhead at 1400 Z, and on return at 1630 Z made a low pass over our abandoned camp site at 80° 54.69' N, 12° 01.0' W (1200 Z) and took photographs.

Friday 31 July

Position: 80° 38.05' N, 13° 34.9' W, temperature +3 °C, pressure 1028 hPa, wind 3 knots from the S. The parking site on the landfast ice was only meters away from the edge with heavy "traffic" of large pieces of drifting sea ice driven by the tide all along the edge. If a break-off occurred, it would be difficult for the hovercraft to proceed under these circumstances. At 0200 Z, we took advantage of open water along the edge and the calm weather to move towards the north and parked at 80° 37.83' N, 13° 34.55' W on 80 cm thick landfast ice. At 1100 Z, we suddenly discovered we were moving, and relocated again to 80° 38.05' N, 13° 34.9' W to a very thick floe. The position is less than 1 km from the eastern tip of Krøyer's Holmer. Worked on reporting the rest of the day.

Saturday 01 August

Position: 80° 38.05' N, 13° 34.9' W. Temperature 0 °C, air pressure 1029 hPa, wind 8 knot from the NNE. Parked on landfast ice. A glorious day. The drift ice is a solid pack within the entire field of view. Worked on the weekly report. Five Common Eider rested 5 m from the rear of the hovercraft in the morning.

Sunday 02 August

Position: 80° 38.04' N, 13° 34.9' W, temperature +7 °C, air pressure 1025 hPa, wind 3 knots from the SW. Parked on landfast ice. A glorious day. Moved the hovercraft a few meter and put wooden planks under to avoid melting in. Dense drift ice as far as we can see. Worked on the weekly report.

Week forty-nine of ice drift (03 Aug. - 09 Aug. 2015)

New web-site: <http://sabvabaa.nerdc.no> for updates

See the web-site: <http://www.aari.ru> for the Russian ice drift station North Pole - 2015

Towards the end of an expedition

As the FRAM-2014/15 ice drift was approaching the marginal ice zone and the ice activity was expected to intensify, we terminated the data acquisition on 03 July 2015 (Fig. 1, upper panel, point marked with black "X"). The surrounding ice field with abundant pressure ridges was too difficult for any diesel driven icebreaker to reach our location with a reasonable effort. An attempt to transfer the cargo to *Polarstern* by helicopter on 06 July was aborted due to the separation between the ship and the camp. Our option to use the sealing vessel *Havsel* was subsequently reaffirmed, but the vessel would not become available until mid-August. To make use of the interim period, the plan was to drive the hovercraft to Independence Fjord and work there in cooperation with the new Villum Research Centre.

The hovercraft left the FRAM-2014/15 camp on 08 July heading north, but advanced only 4 nautical miles before the ice became too difficult and a mechanical problem surfaced. The propeller pitch loading problem was partly fixed within the following week. However, the ice conditions to the north were too difficult for hovercraft driving, and remained so for the next four weeks. As time progressed, the separation between the location of the hovercraft and the abandoned ice camp increased to over 20 nautical miles. Since the ice conditions to the west were considerably better, it was decided on the 28 July to drive towards the landfast sea ice to the west near Krøyer's Holmer, a distance of 25 nautical miles and wait for the drifting ice camp to catch up (Fig. 1, lower panel). It now became clear, that the remaining amount of fuel would not be sufficient to reach Station Nord in Independence Fjord.

Unfortunately, the ice field including the ice floe with the abandoned camp site, did not show any significant southward drift, but kept moving back and forth in an East-West direction at the northern end of what is known as the Northeast Water (polynia) (Fig. 2). At the same time, a narrow belt of drifting sea ice kept blocking any attempt to leave the location near the southeastern part of Krøyer's Holmer where the hovercraft was temporarily parked (Fig. 3).

The situation changed on the 08 August (Fig. 4, upper panel). Guided by the fantastic tools represented by satellite imagery and the global positioning system, we downloaded an image obtained by the Sentinel-1 satellite that day from the <http://ocean.dmi.dk> web-site and geo-referenced it by assigning latitude and longitude to a limited number of locations on land. The image was then transferred to our navigation PC and overlaid the hovercraft GPS navigation (Fig. 4, upper panel). We could now drive directed by the

Fig. 1. Upper panel: Location map with the drift track of FRAM-2014/15. The black letter "X" marks the termination of the science program. White frame refer to area of the satellite image below.

Lower panel: Sentinel-1 satellite image for 08 August obtained from <http://ocean.dmi.dk>

Fig. 2. Landsat images displaying the ice situation during the first part of week 49.
Image processing courtesy of M. Babiker, NERSC.

Fig. 3 Upper: Landsat image with details of the ice distribution around Krøyer's Holmer. Position of the parked hovercraft indicated by red star. Image processing courtesy of M. Babiker, NERSC

Lower: View from the nearest of Krøyer's Holmer of the hovercraft parking site. Landfast sea ice in the foreground and drifting sea ice beyond the hovercraft.

Fig. 4. Upper: Sentinel satellite image from 08 August (<http://ocean.dmi.dk>) overlaid by GPS navigation. The image was acquired one day before the trip was made.

Lower: Sentinel satellite image obtained the same day as the trip was made. Yellow "X" indicate camp location at the time of image acquisition and yellow "dot" indicate the position of the hovercraft . Image processing courtesy of M. Babiker, NERSC.

Fig. 5 Back in camp after 32 days "on the run".

information of the sea ice distribution displayed in the satellite image, and the target was the position of the abandoned camp derived from a satellite tracker. The tracker position was obtained from our web-site <http://sabvabaa.nersc.no>. The transit was made in dense fog on Sunday 09 August. We encountered a large ice floe near the target location and decided to park and wait for the visibility to improve. Four determinations of the separation between the hovercraft and the camp showed 694- 720 meter (Fig. 4, lower panel). We moved on the next day and found the camp intact at the edge of the large floe (Fig. 5).

The sealing vessel *Havsel* is expected to arrive about 17 August.

Wild life

Kittiwakes were in abundance at the easternmost of Krøyer's Holmer. We have not seen a single bird at the location of the camp. Two walrus were seen on the way from the landfast ice.

Life in the High Arctic treats me well.

Yngve Kristoffersen

Week fifty of ice drift (10-18 Aug. 2015): FRAM-2014/15 recovery

The fate of the sea ice platform

The FRAM-2014/15 camp reached the ice edge about mid-July (Fig. 1 and 2). The ice edge is a dynamic transition zone where the solid sea ice cover from the north rapidly disintegrates and permits melting to intensify. Smaller floes progressively move unconstrained driven by the wind, currents and the tides. A local “jet stream” of ice during the third week in July dramatically accelerated floe dispersal (Fig. 2). The sea ice drift in August was to the southwest and then back in a northeast direction south of Nordostrundingen (Figs. 3 and 4). In detail, the drift track was dominated by a pattern of nested cycloids generated by the influence of tidal currents.

Fig. 1. The drift of FRAM-2014/15 northeast of Greenland.

Fig. 2 The ice situation as it developed during the second half of July. The two upper satellite images are courtesy of Danish Meteorological Institute. Processing of the lower image courtesy of M. Babiker, NERSC.

Fig. 3. Landsat images displaying the ice situation in early August while the hovercraft was parked on landfast ice. Image processing courtesy of M. Babiker, NERSC.

Fig. 4 The ice situation on 14 August (last useable image before camp recovery). Image courtesy of Danish Meteorological Institute

By 12 August, the camp site was still part of a floe at least over 1 km across, but the size appears only as a tiny spec on the satellite picture obtained on 14 August (Fig. 4). At this time, the floe started to deteriorate dramatically. Melt ponds had in several places penetrated the entire floe and weakened it. During relatively minor collisions with other floes, sections were knocked off and by the 17 August the size of the floe was about 100 meter long and 70 meter across (Fig. 5. lower right). The cargo placed on top of the pressure ridge had survived reasonably well for nearly six weeks during the height of the summer melt season. Some boxes had rolled off the ridge, but not into any melt ponds. The sequence of events during the last months of the life of the ice floe are shown in Fig. 5.

10 April 2015

23 July 2015

09 August 2015

18 August 2015

Fig. 5. The state of the sea ice cover in the vicinity of the camp from April to recovery on 18 August 2015.

General sea ice conditions and ice camp recovery

The surface of first year sea ice in August 2014 at the FRAM-2014/15 camp site and vicinity was level with distant minor pressure ridges. The location was $87^{\circ} 30' N$, $156^{\circ} E$ in the Makarov Basin. The hovercraft was used to deploy five autonomous bathymetry buoys over a 6 km wide area with no problems during the first week of September. During the winter, several ridging events transformed the level ice to a network of pressure ridges which in many cases implied under-thrusting and locally more than double normal ice thickness. When daylight returned, hovercraft driving was not possible except locally, and the mechanically thickened sea ice rendered the area inaccessible to diesel-driven ice breakers given any reasonable effort. An attempt to transfer cargo by helicopter to *POLARSTERN* at $82^{\circ} N$ on July 6 was aborted due to time constraints. At the closest point, the ship was 11 nautical miles away.

We estimate that during the last half of July, the ice conditions became relaxed enough for recovery by an icebreaker without assistance of helicopter.

Recovery by the sealing vessel *HAVSEL*

The sealer *HAVSEL* had been under charter around Svalbard up until 15 August. *HAVSEL* left Longyearbyen at 1400 hours that day for Northeast Greenland and the FRAM-2014/15 ice floe. Guided by satellite imagery received from NERSC, the course was north along the coast of East Greenland landward of the outflow of ice from the north (Fig. 6)

Fig. 6 Track of the sealing vessel *HAVSEL* to recover the FRAM-2014/15 expedition.

The vessel arrived the floe position at 0600 hours on 18 August in fog (Fig. 5, lower right). All equipment and waste was recovered from the ice floe (Fig. 7), the hovercraft was refueled and the craft and the vessel departed at 1600 hours. Heavy ice was met around midnight and the parties stopped for the night. The transit continued the next morning after breakfast with *HAVSEL* and the hovercraft moving in tandem. At lunch time the hovercraft parked on an ice floe and the vessel hove to to allow the crews a joint meal (Fig. 8, upper panel). As the hovercraft made another stop on an ice floe in the late afternoon to await the arrival of *HAVSEL*, one of the two rods bracing the propeller housing, broke off. The housing vibrated and before coming to rest, the tip of the four-blade propeller shaved off the fiber glass surface on the inside of the housing, and one of the propeller blades broke off. The belt driving the propeller was now removed, and the journey continued with the hovercraft under tow in a hover-up position. It had been the intent to tow the hovercraft after *HAVSEL* during the open ocean crossing of the Fram Strait, but now the tow had to be effected immediately. The transit across the Fram Strait went smooth in calm seas (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7. All equipment and camp waste have been recovered from the ice floe.

Fig. 8 Upper: A rest stop on the way south along the coast of Northeast Greenland

Lower: *HAVSEL* with the hovercraft under tow leaving the ice edge in the Fram Strait.

Arriving Svalbard - Mission completed

HAVSEL and the hovercraft arrived Longyearbyen at 1500 hours 22 August and docked at the Coal Pier (Kullkaia). The expedition was welcomed by NERSC representative Lasse Petterson and the research vessel *Håkon Mosby* fully decorated by flags at Bykaia, a nearby dock site (Fig. 9). Professor Snorre Olaussen (UNIS) presented champagne at the pier out of personal enthusiasm over the year-long achievement (Fig. 10). The hovercraft was subsequently towed to shore in hover-up position and pulled up towards its regular parking area. Later the Governor of Svalbard arrived and greeted us welcome and stayed for a longer informative chat about objectives and events taking place during the ice drift (Fig. 11). A small press conference was held in the mess of *HAVSEL* (Fig. 12, upper panel) and rounded off by a presentation of a song dedicated to the ice drift, written and presented by professor Tor Gammelsrød (Fig. 12, lower panel).

Fig. 9. The research vessel HÅKON MOSBY wishing us welcome.

Fig. 10. Champagne to salute mission completed presented by professor Snorre Olaussen (second from the left) with Dr. John K. Hall on the dock.

Fig. 11. Governor of Svalbard, Odd Ingerød being briefed about the year on the ice.

Fig. 12 Upper: From the press conference in the mess of HAVSEL.
Lower: T. Gammelsrød presenting his ode to SABVABAA

Acknowledgement

We thank our cooperating partner A. Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Germany for showing us the confidence in deployment of FRAM-2014/15. The two support missions by the 333 Squadron of the Norwegian Air Force and one by the Danish Air Force ensured that we could continue the science operations at a high level in spite of the field challenges during the winter. A. Heiberg, University of Seattle provided helpful advice at the planning stage. Technical advice from Griffon Hoverwork, Southampton on hovercraft maintenance, from Chief Engineer H. Berge (retired) on mechanical issues, from PhD. student G. Hope on computer issues and Senior Engineer O. Meyer on electronics issues, were all crucial to maximize up-time throughout the year and contributed to the safety of the expedition. The backing of the Blodgett-Hall Polar Presence LLT providing the hovercraft platform and support supplemented by Lundin Norway and the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate made the first Norwegian ice drift in 118 years possible.

A year in the High Arctic on the drifting sea is over. Life treated us well and the endeavor ended well.

Yngve Kristoffersen and Audun Tholfsen

Epilogue

An expedition like FRAM-2014/15 requires a scientific idea, a logistic solution, preparations and funding.

The scientific idea

The scientific idea behind the FRAM-2014/15 expedition grew out of results obtained from the legendary U.S. ice island Fletcher's Island or T-3 (radar target # 3) which was discovered on the coast of Arctic Canada about 1948 and drifted out of the Arctic Ocean through the Fram Strait in 1983 after three loops in the Beaufort Gyre. Lamont-Doherty Geological Observatory of Columbia University of New York operated a geophysical program which included acquisition of seismic data and a PhD student, John K. Hall had several tours of duty. The data showed apparent wavy sea bed in areas on the Alpha Ridge, and was interpreted as sediments deposited under the influence of bottom currents – a paradigm at the time. Mysteriously, 3 out of the more than 400 short (3 meter) sediments cores obtained from the ice island in the area contained 50-70 million year old sediments at the sea bed – yet nobody questioned why? One of the cores contained a one meter long interval of black mud and has received a lot of scientific attention. The black mud suggests an oxygen-poor oceanic environment.

After 1991, new multi-channel seismic data started to become available and the activity accelerated after 2001 as the circum-arctic nations had a need to document claims to extend their respective Exclusive Economic Zones. The data showed a drape, about 200 meter thick present everywhere in the deep Arctic Ocean except in an area on the Alpha Ridge (25 meter). A new look at the T-3 seismic data from Alpha Ridge after year 2000 revealed deformed sediments at the sea bed and massive submarine slides within an 200 x 600 km area. The icebreaker *Healy* traversed the outskirts of this area in 2005 and the modern multi-channel data showed sediment had been removed and deformation decreased with depth below the sea bed. The multitude of observations were now explained as the possible effect of a pressure wave from the impact of asteroid fragments: This idea was published in the *Norwegian Journal of Geology* in 2007 after earlier attempts had been rejected by two other journals.

The idea of an asteroid impact was exciting, but more important was the realization that this area represented a treasure chest for access to Early Cenozoic and Late Cretaceous stratigraphy without the need for scientific drilling.

The logistic approach

We brought a small hovercraft to the North Pole in 1991 on the icebreaker *Polarstern*, but the craft was of limited use. In 1992, the Norwegian Research Council funded a small feasibility study which included video recording of the sea ice surface from 150 meter altitude over a distance of 250 kilometer and field test of a hovercraft north of Svalbard. This study was the basis for an application in 1993 from the University of Bergen, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Centre, A. Wegener Institute of Polar and Marine Research (GER) and Scott Polar Research Institute (UK) to the European Marine Science and Technology program for funds to test hovercraft as a science platform

in the Arctic Ocean - the response was negative. The report from the feasibility study later caught the interest of Rieber Shipping, a provider of ice-going vessels for many scientific expeditions to Antarctica. The company Board decided in 1996 to acquire a medium-sized hovercraft (4 ton pay load) to be stationed in Svalbard to serve as a research platform for hire. However, the idea was not well received by the Governors's office and not pursued further.

In 2004, Dr. John K. Hall, marine geophysicist with the Geological Survey of Israel visited University of Bergen to discuss the seismic data over Alpha Ridge acquired from the ice island T-3 by him as a graduate student in the late 1960-ties. The issue of how to get to Alpha Ridge came up and the hovercraft alternative was tabled. The enthusiastic discussion was concluded with the statement "let us buy one". The contract for a polar research platform based on hovercraft technology was signed in Southampton in the fall of 2007 and the craft arrived in Longyearbyen in June 2008.

Preparing for sea ice operations

Efficient use of the hovercraft required: 1) driving skills over sea ice; 2) learning the strength and weaknesses of the hovercraft technology, and 3) adapting and/or developing geological/geophysical tools tailored to a hovercraft platform. The hovercraft arrived at the start of the International Polar Year and by chance became the platform for an IPY-project: "High school students - building scientific and polar curiosity through participation in a scientific field camp on drifting sea ice". This activity involved 16 high school students selected from all over Norway to spend a week on the drifting sea ice doing similar measurements as during Nansen's drift with the ship FRAM, but now with modern technology. A total of eight week-long trips from Longyearbyen to the ice edge were made in 2008 and 2009. The objective of trips in the following years were to obtain rock samples from the sea bed on Yermak Plateau, an natural prolongation of the continental margin north of Svalbard. This activity funded by the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate brought back over 300 kilos of rocks from basement outcrops on the continental and volcanic part of the plateau. The hovercraft ventured up to 90 nautical miles north of the ice edge on trips lasting up to three weeks. A first venture into the Arctic Ocean was an attempt to reach a work area on the Lomonosov Ridge in 2012 accompanied by the Swedish icebreaker *Oden*. The summer and fall light conditions had serious impact on trafficability and the time was spent on surveys over the rift valley of Gakkel Ridge at 85° N. A short operation in the Fram Strait in the fall of 2013 was together with the Norwegian Coast Guard vessel *Svalbard*. In preparation for FRAM-2014/15 endeavour, the hovercraft *Sabvabaa* had transited over 4.000 kilometer over sea ice, but all during the summer and early fall.

The hovercraft has a limited pay load (2.2 ton) and equipment weight is an issue. This is a particular concern for sediment coring and dredging. The moving sea ice cover provide the force to pull a sediment corer out of the bottom and the required winch capacity is limited to what is needed to lift the equipment through the water column. A sediment corer boosted by the hydrostatic water pressure was developed, tested and patented for use with the hovercraft. In this way the sediment coring capability including 3000 meter kevlar line, a capstan winch and the corer weighed less than 300 kilo in total.

Funding

The proposal for the FRAM-2014/15 expedition was first submitted in the fall of 2013 at a time of change of government in Norway and a petroleum industry in a state of budget cut psychosis. Less than half of the funds needed for operational expenses were at hand by the time of departure, but overruled by the consideration that "it is now or never". The backing of the Blodgett-Hall Polar Presence LLT providing the hovercraft platform and support supplemented by Lundin Norway and the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate made the first Norwegian ice drift in 118 years

